

The FASTK Protein Family: Exploring Non-canonical Mitochondrial RNA Processing

OHKUBO, Akira

Abstract

Mitochondrial gene expression is essential for oxidative phosphorylation. Transcription of the human circular mitochondrial DNA initiates at two distinct divergent promoters, one on each strand, leading to two almost genome-length polycistronic transcripts. Therefore, the expression level of each gene is mainly controlled through post-transcriptional events. RNA processing triggers the post-transcriptional maturation. As most mRNAs and rRNAs within the polycistronic transcripts are flanked by tRNAs, cleaving off these tRNA junctions releases individual transcripts. However, this 'tRNA punctuation model' does not explain the processing of mRNAs that lack flanking tRNAs, and the molecular mechanisms underlying this non-canonical RNA processing remain unknown. To answer this long-standing question, we exploited the role of the FASTK family proteins: emerging key mitochondrial post-transcriptional regulators. Here, we propose that the FASTK proteins regulate the expression of a broad range of mitochondrial transcripts, including poorly investigated non-coding RNAs, by fine-tuning the processing of canonical and [...]

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The FASTK Protein Family :
Exploring Non-canonical Mitochondrial RNA Processing

THÈSE

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intitulée :

**«The FASTK Protein Family :
Exploring Non-canonical Mitochondrial RNA Processing»**

Les Facultés de médecine et des sciences, sur le préavis de Monsieur J.-C. MARTINO, professeur ordinaire et directeur de thèse (Département de biologie cellulaire), Monsieur W. ROSSMANITH, professeur (Center for Anatomy and Cell Biology, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria), Monsieur M. MINCZUK, professeur (Medical Research Council Mitochondrial, Biology Unit, University of Cambridge, UK), Monsieur L. LOPEZ MOLINA, professeur associé (Département de botanique et biologie végétale), autorisent l'impression de la présente thèse, sans exprimer d'opinion sur les propositions qui y sont énoncées.

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Abbreviations

aaRS: aminoacyl-tRNA synthetase

ATP: adenosine triphosphate

BioID: proximity-dependent biotin identification

BrU: bromouridine

CI: complex I of mitochondrial respiratory chain

CYTC: cytochrome c

D-foci: degradation foci

DDX28: DEAD-box helicase 28

DHX30: DExH-box helicase 30

EMSA: electrophoretic mobility shift assay

ETC: electron transport chain

FACS: fluorescence-activated cell sorting

FAST_1: FASTK-like protein domain 1

FAST_2: FASTK-like protein domain 2

FASTK: Fas-activated serine/threonine kinase

FASTKD1: FAST kinase domain-containing protein 1

fMet: N-Formylmethionine

G4s: G-quadruplexes

GO: gene ontology

GRSF1: G-rich sequence factor 1

H-strand/L-strand: the heavy/light strand

HITS-CLIP: High-throughput sequencing of RNA isolated by crosslinking immunoprecipitation

HSP/LSP : heavy/light strand promoter

IMS: intermembrane space

KO: knockout

LC-MS/MS: liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry

lncRNA/sncRNA : long/small ncRNA

LRPPRC: leucine-rich pentapeptide rich domain containing protein

MRC: mitochondrial respiratory chain

MRG: mitochondrial RNA granule

MRPL/MRPS: mitochondrial large/small ribosomal subunit protein

MRPP1: mitochondrial RNase P subunit 1

mtDNA/mtRNA: mitochondrial DNA/RNA

mtPAP: mitochondrial poly(A) polymerase

mtSSB: mitochondrial single-stranded DNA-binding protein

MTS: mitochondrial targeting signal
ncRNA: non-coding RNA
nDNA: nuclear DNA
 O_H/O_L : replication origin of the heavy/light strand
OMM/IMM: outer/inner mitochondrial membrane
OXPHOS: oxidative phosphorylation
ORF: open reading frame
PNPase: polynucleotide phosphorylase
 $POL\gamma$: DNA polymerase γ
POLRMT: mitochondrial RNA polymerase
Poly(A): polyadenine
PPR: pentatricopeptide repeat
pre-: precursor
PTCD1: pentatricopeptide domain-containing protein 1
RAP: RNA-binding domain abundant in Apicomplexans
RBP: RNA binding protein
rFASTKD4: recombinant FASTKD4
ROS: reactive oxygen species
rRNA/mRNA/tRNA: ribosomal RNA/messenger RNA/transfer RNA
SLIRP: stem-loop interacting RNA-binding protein
ssRNA/dsRNA: single-stranded/double-stranded RNA
SSU/LSU: mitoribosome small/large subunit
TCA cycle: tricarboxylic acid cycle
TEFM: mitochondrial transcription elongation factor
TFAM: mitochondrial transcription factor A
TIA1: T-cell intracellular antigen 1
TOMM/TIMM: Translocase of the outer/inner mitochondrial membrane
UTR: untranslated region
VDAC: voltage-dependent anion channel
VSR: very short patch repair

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II. Abstract & Résumé

Abstract

Mitochondria are essential organelles present within most eukaryotic cells. As a legacy of their bacterial origin, mitochondria have retained their own genome (mtDNA) with a unique gene expression system. The mtDNA encodes key components of the mitochondrial respiratory chain (MRC) and its expression is therefore essential for ATP production through oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS). Genetic mutations in the mtDNA often lead to defects in OXPHOS, which can be accompanied by severe clinical symptoms.

The compact human mitochondrial genome contains 37 genes (two rRNAs, 22 tRNAs, and 13 ORFs) and is transcribed from two distinct promoters, one on each strand of the circular DNA, generating two almost genome-length polycistronic transcripts. The expression level of each single gene is mainly controlled in a post-transcriptional fashion. RNA processing triggers the course of the post-transcriptional maturation. As the polycistronic transcripts include mRNAs and rRNAs that are mostly flanked by tRNAs, the excision of the tRNA junctions by RNase P and RNase Z allows individual transcripts to be released from the polycistronic transcripts. This process is called the classic ‘tRNA punctuation model’. However, this model does not apply to the cleavage of tRNA-less junctions, which localize at the 3’ UTR of ND6, 5’ UTR of COX1, between ND5 and CYTB, and between ATP8/6 and COX3 mRNAs. The machinery in charge of the cleavage of these non-canonical junctions is currently unknown. However, recent work has shed light on several candidates for this non-canonical RNA processing, including the Fas-activated serine/threonine kinase (FASTK) protein family members. This protein family contains six members, FASTK and FASTKD1-5, which display three conserved putative RNA binding domains: the FAST_1, FAST_2, and RAP domains. Thanks to a N-terminal mitochondrial targeting sequence, all these proteins are transported to the mitochondrial matrix, where they regulate the expression levels of specific sense and antisense transcripts and the processing of non-canonical junctions.

In this PhD work, we investigated the roles of the FASTK protein family in non-canonical mtRNA processing. To this end, we generated human cell lines displaying single and combined knockouts of FASTKD3, FASTKD4, and FASTKD5 using the CRISPR/Cas9 technology. Transcriptome analysis of these knockout cells revealed defective processing of several canonical and non-canonical junctions, accompanied by altered expression of specific transcripts. The most striking phenotypes were obtained with the loss of FASTKD4 or FASTKD5 and with their combined knockout. Impaired processing of the non-canonical

junctions, particularly marked for the 5'UTR of COX1, ND5-CYTB, ATP8/6-COX3, were observed in the FASTKD4&5 double knockout cells. Furthermore, our work highlighted the role of these proteins in the processing not only of coding RNAs but also of their non-coding counterparts. This finding prompted us to postulate that FASTKD proteins may be involved in the processing and clearance of non-coding transcripts.

Loss of FASTKD5 had a major impact on mitochondrial translation, which was accompanied by defects in mitochondrial respiration. This phenotype is likely the result of a significant decrease in COX1 protein synthesis due to defective pre-COX1 RNA processing. The loss of FASTKD4, however, had a milder impact on translation and OXPHOS.

In addition to this work on mammalian cells, we investigated the role of FASTK proteins in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. This animal only contains one member of the protein family, FASK-1, which is mostly related to human FASTKD4. We found that the FASK-1 mutant worm displayed defective processing of non-canonical ND5 precursor transcripts. Together, our results highlight an evolutionarily conserved function of the FASTK protein family members in non-canonical mtRNA processing.

We further investigated the molecular function of FASTKD4, as a representative of the protein family, focusing on ND5-CYTB RNA processing. As the FASTK family proteins seem structurally related to the PD-(D/E)-XK nuclease superfamily, a class of viral enzymes that display endonuclease activity, we tested whether FASTKD4 could display an RNase activity *in vitro*. We purified recombinant FASTKD4 protein (rFASTKD4) and could show for the first time that this protein directly binds RNA using EMSA (electrophoretic mobility shift assay). However, using various biochemical experimental conditions, we did not find an RNase activity associated with rFASTKD4, suggesting that either this protein is not an endonuclease or that additional proteins are needed to promote the activity of FASTKD4. Strikingly, HITS-CLIP (high-throughput sequencing of RNA isolated by crosslinking immunoprecipitation) revealed that FASTKD4 preferentially binds to tRNA^E, which is complementary to the ND5-CYTB junction. This finding supports the hypothesis that FASTKD4 plays a role in ND5-CYTB RNA processing, albeit its precise mode of action remains to be elucidated.

In conclusion, this PhD work has revealed interesting findings on the function of the FASTK family proteins and raises new hypotheses about the mechanisms by which they regulate mitochondrial RNA processing.

Résumé

Les mitochondries sont des organites essentiels présents dans la vaste majorité des cellules eucaryotes. Comme héritage de leur origine bactérienne, les mitochondries ont maintenu leur propre génome (ADNmt) avec un système d'expression génique unique. L'ADNmt code pour des composants de la chaîne respiratoire mitochondriale et donc son expression est essentielle pour la production d'ATP par phosphorylation oxydative (OXPHOS). Des mutations génétiques de l'ADNmt mènent souvent à des déficits d'OXPHOS qui peuvent s'accompagner de symptômes cliniques sévères.

Le génome mitochondrial humain code pour 37 gènes (deux ARNrs, 22 ARNts, et 13 ORFs) et il est transcrit à partir de deux promoteurs distincts, un sur chaque brin de l'ADN circulaire, générant ainsi deux transcrits polycistroniques, faisant presque la taille du génome. Le niveau d'expression de chaque gène est principalement contrôlé de façon post-transcriptionnelle. Le processing de l'ARN est la première étape de la maturation post-transcriptionnelle. Comme les transcrits polycistroniques contiennent des ARNms et des ARNrs qui sont majoritairement flanqués par des ARNts, l'excision des ARNts par les RNases P et Z permet aussi de libérer chaque ARNm et chaque ARNr individuellement. Ce processus est appelé le 'modèle de ponctuation par ARNt'. Toutefois, ce modèle ne s'applique pas au clivage des jonctions dépourvues d'ARNts. Celles-ci sont localisées au niveau du 3' UTR de ND6, 5' UTR de COX1, entre les ARNms de ND5 et CYTB, et entre les ARNms ATP8/6 et COX3. La machinerie en charge du clivage de ces jonctions non-canoniques est actuellement inconnue. Cependant, des travaux récents ont permis de proposer plusieurs candidats pour ce type de processing non-conventionnel, dont des protéines de la famille FASTK (Fas-activated serine/threonine kinase). Cette famille de protéines contient six membres, FASTK et FASTKD1-5, qui présentent trois domaines conservés prédits pour se lier à l'ARN : les domaines FAST_1, FAST_2, et RAP. Grâce à une séquence d'adressage mitochondrial N-terminale, toutes ces protéines sont importées dans la matrice mitochondriale où elles contrôlent le niveau d'expression de transcrits spécifiques et le processing d'ARNs non-canoniques.

Durant cette thèse, nous avons étudié les rôles de la famille FASTK dans le processing non-canonique des ARNs mitochondriaux. Pour cela, nous avons généré des cellules humaines dont nous avons délété soit un membre de la famille FASTK (FASTKD3, FASTKD4 ou FASTKD5) soit une combinaison de ces gènes (FASTKD3&4 ou

FASTKD4&5) en utilisant la technologie CRISPR/Cas9. L'analyse transcriptomique de ces cellules knockout a révélé des perturbations dans le processing de plusieurs jonctions canoniques et non-canoniques, accompagnées d'une altération de l'expression de transcrits spécifiques. Les phénotypes les plus marqués ont été obtenus avec la délétion de FASTKD4 ou FASTKD5 et avec leur knockout combiné. Un processing déficient des jonctions non-canoniques, particulièrement le 5' UTR de COX1, ainsi que ND5-CYTB et ATP8/6-COX3, a été observé avec le knockout de FASTKD4 et FASTKD5. De plus, notre étude a mis en évidence le rôle de ces protéines dans le processing non seulement des ARNs codants mais aussi de leurs séquences complémentaires non-codantes (ARNncs). Ces résultats nous permettent de postuler que le mécanisme d'action des protéines FASTKD implique le processing des jonctions non-canoniques et l'élimination de certains transcrits non-codants, sans que nous puissions dire pour l'instant s'il existe un lien de cause à effet entre ces deux processus.

L'absence de FASTKD5 a eu, quant à elle, un impact majeur sur la traduction mitochondriale, accompagnée par des défauts de la chaîne respiratoire. Ce phénotype est probablement une conséquence de la réduction significative de la synthèse de la protéine COX1, causée par le processing dysfonctionnel de l'ARN immature pre-COX1. L'absence de FASTKD4 a causé un impact plus léger sur la traduction et sur la respiration cellulaire.

En plus de l'étude sur cellules humaines, nous avons étudié le rôle des protéines FASTK chez *Caenorhabditis elegans*. Cet animal contient un seul membre de la famille, FASK-1, qui est similaire à la protéine FASTKD4 humaine. Nous avons démontré que, chez le ver, la délétion FASK-1 induit des déficits du processing non-canonique des transcrits précurseurs de ND5. Nos résultats indiquent donc que la fonction des protéines de la famille FASTK dans le processing non-canonique de l'ARN mitochondrial a été conservée au cours de l'évolution.

Nous avons ensuite étudié la fonction moléculaire de FASTKD4, que nous avons choisi comme représentant de la famille FASTK, en nous focalisant sur le processing de la jonction entre ND5 et CYTB. Comme les membres de la famille FASTK semblent structurellement reliés à la superfamille des nucléases PD-(D/E)-XK, une classe d'enzymes virales montrant une activité endonucléasique, nous avons testé si FASTKD4 pouvait également avoir une activité RNase *in vitro*. Nous avons purifié une protéine FASTKD4 recombinante (FASTKD4r) et réussi à montrer pour la première fois qu'un membre de cette famille protéique est capable de se lier directement à l'ARN, en utilisant la technique d'EMSA (electrophoretic mobility shift assay). Cependant, en utilisant des conditions biochimiques variées, nous n'avons pas mis en évidence d'activité RNase associée avec FASTKD4r. Cela

suggère soit que cette protéine n'est pas une endonucléase, soit que des protéines additionnelles sont nécessaires pour promouvoir l'activité de FASTKD4. L'analyse HITS-CLIP (high-throughput sequencing of RNA isolated by crosslinking immunoprecipitation) a révélé que FASTKD4 interagit préférentiellement avec l'ARNt^E, qui est complémentaire de la jonction ND5-CYTB. Cette observation soutient l'hypothèse que FASTKD4 joue un rôle dans le processing de l'ARN de ND5-CYTB, bien que son mode d'action précis ne soit pas encore clair.

En conclusion, le travail de cette thèse a révélé des découvertes intéressantes sur la fonction de la famille FASTK et nous permet de proposer de nouvelles hypothèses quant aux mécanismes par lesquels les protéines de cette famille pourraient réguler le processing de l'ARN mitochondrial.

III. Introduction

3-1. The mitochondrion

3-1-1. The origin

Mitochondria are organelles present within most eukaryotic cells. It is widely accepted that they originated from an alpha-proteobacterium (Gray, 2014; Roger et al., 2017). According to the endosymbiotic theory, the ancestor of the modern eukaryotic cell, a probable relative of *Asgard archaea*, engulfed the alpha-proteobacterium more than 1.45 billion years ago. Throughout their co-evolution with the host cell, mitochondria gained unique features, some of which are essential to maintain cell integrity.

Mitochondria contain their own DNA, which they inherited from bacteria and retained, at least in part, throughout evolution. The mitochondrial genome was highly remodeled during evolution, and a majority of genes was transferred into the nuclear genome. Consequently, mitochondrial genomes vary in size, shape, and gene content, regarding different species, ranging from the largest 81 kbp animal mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) in the cnidaria *Isarachnanthus nocturnus* (Stampar et al., 2019) to the smallest 6 kbp mtDNA in the parasite *Plasmodium falciparum* (Tyagi et al., 2014). In some cells, such as parasitic syndiniales *Amoebophrya cerati*, mtDNA-lacking mitochondria, also called mitosomes, can be found (John et al., 2019).

The 16.5 kbp human mtDNA encodes only 37 genes, 13 of which encode functional proteins. Given that >1200 proteins have been identified as mitochondrial, around 99% of mitochondrial proteins are encoded in the nuclear genome and imported from the cytoplasm (Calvo et al., 2016). The human mtDNA is inherited exclusively down the maternal line, however recent studies have proposed that paternal inheritance also occurs as a rare event (Luo et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2020a).

3-1-2. The architecture

Mitochondria are membrane-bound organelles with around 0.2-1 μm in diameter. The lumen, named the mitochondrial matrix, is separated from the cytosol by two membranes: the outer mitochondrial membrane (OMM) and the inner mitochondrial membrane (IMM) (Figure 1). The space between the two membranes is termed the intermembrane space (IMS).

The OMM is a platform to communicate with the cytoplasm. It controls the traffic of metabolites, ions, proteins, and possibly RNA, via the voltage-dependent anion channel (VDAC; metabolites/ions transport) and the translocase of the outer mitochondrial membrane

(TOMM; protein transport). Of note, RNA import into mitochondria is highly controversial (Gammage et al., 2018; Jeandard et al., 2019). Furthermore, the OMM allows mitochondria to sense cytosolic signals and stimuli, sometimes resulting in mitochondrial fusion and fission, mitophagy (i.e. autophagy of mitochondria), and apoptosis. Mitochondria contact many other cellular organelles through specific proteins tethered to the OMM. Mitochondria-organelle contacts are key for a variety of mitochondrial functions including mitochondrial dynamics, mtDNA replication and distribution, mitophagy, and lipid and Ca^{2+} transfer (Lackner, 2019).

The IMS stores a large variety of metabolites and proteins, for example, cytochrome c (CYTC). While CYTC is a functional component of the electron transport chain (ETC), it is also known to induce cell death following its release from Bax/Bak permeabilized mitochondria into the cytosol, where it can trigger apoptosis through the formation of the apoptosome (Bender and Martinou, 2013).

The IMM harbours many different channels for selective transport. For instance, the translocase of the inner mitochondrial membrane (TIMM) transfers proteins into the matrix. K^+ and Ca^{2+} are transported into the matrix through ATP sensitive K^+ channel and mitochondrial Ca^{2+} uniporter, respectively. The mitochondrial pyruvate carrier specifically transfers pyruvate into the matrix, where pyruvate fuels the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle. The IMM includes a characteristic wrinkled shape named cristae, which provides a large surface area (Figure 1). Cristae harbour the respiratory chain complexes and the ATP synthase complex, where energy synthesis through oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) takes place.

The matrix contains all enzymes involved in the TCA cycle, which provides electrons to the respiratory chain to allow ATP production through oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS). It is also where the mtDNA is stored, and where subsequent gene expression takes place.

Figure 1. The basic architecture of mitochondrion. The lumen (matrix) is separated from the cytosol by two membranes, the OMM and the IMM, which delineate the intermembrane space IMS. The IMM displays a characteristic wrinkled shape named cristae, where respiratory chain complexes and ATP synthase for energy production are harboured. The ATP synthase is at the tip of the cristae. Modified from (Giacomello et al., 2020).

3-1-3. The functions: from ATP production to cell death

Mitochondrial functions vary greatly, ranging from metabolic regulation to programmed cell death (Figure 2). The most acknowledged function is the production of ATP through oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), and therefore mitochondria are often referred to as “the powerhouse of the cell.” Beyond energy production, mitochondria are involved in a variety of metabolic pathways. They generate materials needed for the synthesis of biomolecules, including nucleotides, fatty acids, cholesterol, amino acids, and iron-sulfur (Fe-S) clusters (Spinelli and Haigis, 2018). It is noteworthy that the Fe-S cluster biogenesis is considered as one of the most indispensable activities of mitochondria for cell life. Furthermore, mitochondria maintain cellular ion homeostasis (e.g. Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and K^{+}) to control diverse physiological pathways, including intracellular Ca^{2+} signalling (Rizzuto et al., 2012). These multifaceted functions largely rely on their dynamics and contacts with other organelles (Lackner, 2019).

Given that about 99% of mitochondrial proteins are encoded in the nuclear DNA (nDNA) and imported from the cytosol, nuclear-mitochondrial communication is indispensable for mitochondrial and cell homeostasis. For example, when unfolded proteins are accumulated within the mitochondrial matrix and the OXPHOS activity is perturbed, a

nuclear stress response is orchestrated, called mitochondrial unfolded protein response (mtUPR). In addition, as mentioned above, mitochondria, through cytochrome c release, participate in the intrinsic pathway of apoptosis (Bock and Tait, 2020).

Mitochondria also have central roles in inflammation, stress response, and innate immunity. Their involvement in these processes is largely mediated through the release of specific components, which once in the cytosol trigger a series of beneficial or deleterious reactions. Among these components, one can cite 1) mtDNA or mtRNA, which can both activate an interferon response upon cytosolic localization, 2) ROS, which can either play a deleterious function or can stimulate cell differentiation and proliferation (Bigarella et al., 2014; Perillo et al., 2020) and 3) calcium, which can be released into the cytosol during severe mitochondrial damages and trigger proteolysis and cell death (Banoth and Cassel, 2018; Fessler et al., 2020; Guo et al., 2020; Riley and Tait, 2020; Vringer and Tait, 2019).

The mechanisms of OXPHOS will be further described below.

Figure 2. A schematic representation of mitochondrial functions. Modified from (Pfaner et al., 2019).

3-1-3-1. Mitochondrial respiration

Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) is often referred to as the currency of cellular energy transfer, and its biosynthesis is an essential metabolic process. ATP can be biosynthesized through glycolysis in the cytoplasm and OXPHOS in mitochondria (Figure 3). Glycolysis

generates two molecules of ATP, two of NADH and two of pyruvate from a single molecule of glucose. When the amount of oxygen is limited, pyruvate is further converted to lactate by the lactate dehydrogenase, a process called anaerobic glycolysis. High lactate production also occurs in highly proliferative cells and cancer cells when oxygen is available: in this case, the process is called aerobic glycolysis or the Warburg effect. However, in most cases, when oxygen is available, cells usually generate ATP through oxidative phosphorylation, which takes place in mitochondria. Pyruvate generated from the glycolytic pathway is transported into the mitochondrial matrix by the mitochondrial pyruvate carrier, where it is further converted to acetyl-CoA by the pyruvate dehydrogenase to fuel the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle (also known as the Krebs cycle). Products of the TCA cycle include NADH, FADH₂ and succinate, which subsequently feed the electron transport chain (ETC; also called mitochondrial respiratory chain (MRC)) embedded in the IMM. The ETC is composed of four different complexes termed complex I (CI) to IV (CIV), which allow the transport of electrons with oxygen as the final acceptor. During the electron transfer, the energy released is used by the respiratory chain complexes to pump protons from the matrix to the IMS, thus generating a proton gradient. In addition to the respiratory chain complexes, the ATP synthase, also called complex V (CV), uses protons pumped during electrons flow on the ETC to generate ATP from ADP. This process, called OXPHOS, allows mitochondria to efficiently produce >30 molecules of ATP from a single molecule of glucose (two pyruvate molecules).

The five ETC complexes are composed of almost one hundred different proteins. While they are mostly encoded in the nDNA, some are generated from the mtDNA. All the complexes except complex II include mitochondrially encoded protein(s).

Polypeptides	Complex I	Complex II	Complex III	Complex IV	Complex V
mtDNA-encoded subunits	7	0	1	3	2
nDNA-encoded subunits	~39	4	10	10	~14
Assembly proteins	~11	~2	~9	~30	~3

Figure 3. Scheme of oxidative phosphorylation. mtDNA-encoded subunits are marked in different colors. Mechanisms of OXPHOS are described in the main text. CI (NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase) and CII (succinate:CoQ oxidoreductase) reduce CoQ to ubiquinol, consuming NADH or succinate, respectively. Electrons from the ubiquinol are then transferred to CYTC by CIII (ubiquinol-cytochrome c oxidoreductase). Subsequently, the oxidation of the CYTC by CIV (cytochrome c oxidase) occurs being coupled with the reduction of oxygen, which gives H₂O molecule. These biochemical reactions by CI, CIII and CIV couple the pumping of protons from the mitochondrial matrix into the IMS, which generate a chemio-osmotic gradient and electrical potential (mitochondrial membrane potential) across the IMM. This proton gradient, in turn, drives the ATP synthase (CV) to generate ATP. Modified from (Schon et al., 2012).

3-1-4. Human mitochondrial gene expression

The human mitochondrial genome is compact, circular DNA of about 16.5 kbp (Figure 4). It encodes 37 genes without introns, all of which are required for OXPHOS. These genes include 11 mRNAs bearing 13 open reading frames (ATP8/ATP6 and ND4L/4 mRNAs are bicistronic), which encode seven subunits of CI (ND1, 2, 3, 4, 4L, 5 and 6), one subunit of CIII (CYTB), three subunits of CIV (COX1, 2, and 3), and two subunits of CV (ATP6 and 8) (Figure 3). These ETC subunits are entirely synthesized within mitochondria. Two rRNAs (12S and 16S) and 22 tRNAs (one-letter code) encoded in the mtDNA are needed for mitochondrial translation. The complementary strands of mtDNA are denoted as light (L) and heavy (H) strand, based on their distinct base composition which gives different sedimentation

3-1-4-1. Compartmentalization of mitochondrial gene expression: nucleoids and mitochondrial RNA granules

Human mitochondrial gene expression appears to be compartmentalized within distinct foci called mitochondrial nucleoids, which contain mtDNA and mtDNA-associated proteins, and mitochondrial RNA granules (MRGs), which contain mtRNA and mtRNA binding proteins (Figure 5) (Bonekamp and Larsson, 2018; Jourdain et al., 2016; Pearce et al., 2017a).

Mitochondrial nucleoids localize in close association with the IMM, interspersed in between cristae. MRGs are present in close proximity with nucleoids and are also tightly associated with the IMM (Jourdain et al., 2016). Mammalian mitochondrial nucleoids are slightly elongated with a mean size of $80 \times 80 \times 100$ nm, and the average copy number of mtDNA per nucleoid is 1.4 in human cells and 1.1–1.5 in mouse cells, suggesting that most mammalian mitochondrial nucleoids likely contain a single molecule of mtDNA (Bonekamp and Larsson, 2018). One of the main protein components of nucleoids is mitochondrial transcription factor A (TFAM), whereas numerous other proteins, including mitochondrial replication factors (e.g. POL γ , TWINKLE, and mtSSB) and mitochondrial transcriptional machinery (e.g. POLRMT, TEFM, and TFB2M), can transiently associate with them. TFAM has a dual function since it regulates the structure of the nucleoids through compacting mtDNA, and acts as a transcription factor (Farge and Falkenberg, 2019). The TFAM/mtDNA ratio indicates the level of nucleoids compaction. A high amount of TFAM results in highly packed mtDNA, which is inaccessible to the replication and transcription machinery. In contrast, less concentrated TFAM leads to loosely structured nucleoids with active gene expression.

After transcription, nascent RNA is transferred from nucleoids to MRGs, where most post-transcriptional regulatory events, ranging from RNA processing to mitoribosome assembly, likely occur. Recent work from our laboratory, in collaboration with the laboratory of Prof. Suliana Manley (EPFL, Switzerland), has shown that MRGs are formed by liquid-liquid phase transition and the RNA seems to be essential in the formation of these structures that can be defined as liquid condensates (Rey et al., Nature Cell Biology in press; (Rey et al., 2019)). In addition to RNA, these structures contain many proteins, of which some have been characterized: they include proteins involved in RNA stability (FASTKD1), RNA processing (MRPP1-3, GRSF1, PTC2, FASTK, FASTKD5, and NLRX1), RNA modification (mtPAP, MRM1-3, RPU3-4, TFB1M, and TRUB2), mitoribosome assembly (DDX28, DHX30, GRSF1, PTC1, FASTKD2, ERAL1, GTPBP10, and NOA1) as well as several mitoribosome

subunits (MRPS7, MRPS9, and MRPL47) as listed in Table 1 (Jourdain et al., 2016; Maiti et al., 2018; Pearce et al., 2017a; Singh et al., 2018; Zaganelli et al., 2017). It is currently unclear if all post-transcriptional regulation events occur in the MRGs. Another RNA foci termed degradation foci (D-foci) is proposed to catalyze RNA degradation, since these putative structures include the mitochondrial RNA degradosome composed of PNPase and SUV3 (Borowski et al., 2013).

Figure 5. The spatiotemporal organisation of mitochondrial gene expression. Mitochondrial nucleic acids are highly packaged into nucleoprotein structures in the mitochondrial matrix with proteins involved in mitochondrial gene maintenance and expression: nucleoids hold mtDNA and mitochondrial RNA granules (MRGs). Nucleoids catalyse mtDNA replication, mtDNA repair, and mitochondrial transcription. Nascent polycistronic transcripts are then transferred into the MRGs, where post-transcriptional regulation, ranging from RNA processing to mitoribosome assembly, occurs. It is currently unclear if all post-transcriptional regulation steps happen in the MRGs. RNA degradation has also been proposed to occur in another distinct foci, termed D-foci. After mtRNA maturation and mitoribosome assembly, proteins are translated by mitoribosomes and co-translationally inserted into the IMM, where the ETC is assembled. Modified from (Pearce et al., 2017a).

SYMBOL	GENE NAME	FUNCTION
FASTKD1	FAST kinase domain-containing protein 1	RNA stability
MRPP1 (TRMT10C)	tRNA methyltransferase 10 homolog C	
MRPP2 (HSD17B10)	3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydrogenase type-2	RNA processing
MRPP3 (PRORP)	Mitochondrial ribonuclease P catalytic subunit	
GRSF1	G-rich sequence factor 1	
PTCD2	Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein 2	
FASTK	Fas-activated serine/threonine kinase	
FASTKD5	FAST kinase domain-containing protein 5	
NLRX1	NLR family member X1	
MTPAP	Mitochondrial Poly(A) RNA polymerase	
MRM1	Mitochondrial rRNA methyltransferase 1	
MRM2	Mitochondrial rRNA methyltransferase 2	
MRM3	Mitochondrial rRNA methyltransferase 3	RNA modification
RPUSD3	Mitochondrial mRNA pseudouridine synthase 3	
RPUSD4	Mitochondrial mRNA pseudouridine synthase 4	
TFB1M	Mitochondrial Dimethyladenosine transferase 1	
TRUB2	Mitochondrial mRNA pseudouridine synthase 2	
DDX28	Probable ATP-dependent RNA helicase DDX28	
DHX30	ATP-dependent RNA helicase DHX30	Mitorisome assembly
PTCD1	Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein 1	
FASTKD2	FAST kinase domain-containing protein 2	
ERAL1	Mitochondrial GTPase Era	
GTPBP10	GTP-binding protein 10	
NOA1	Nitric oxide-associated protein 1	Mitoribosome subunits
MRPS7	Mitochondrial 28S ribosomal protein S7	
MRPS9	Mitochondrial 28S ribosomal protein S9	
MRPL47	Mitochondrial 39S ribosomal protein L47	

Table 1. List of currently known protein components of mitochondrial RNA granules

3-1-4-2. Maintenance of mtDNA integrity through DNA repair and replication

The integrity of mtDNA is maintained by mitochondrial DNA repair and replication. It is known that compared to nDNA, the mtDNA can be easily mutated. This is mainly because the mtDNA is easily accessible to reactive oxygen species (ROS), which is a by-product of the ETC. Single-strand and double-strand breaks of the mtDNA are repaired through base excision repair (BER) and microhomology mediated end joining (MMEJ) respectively. However, many questions still remain to be answered to unveil the entire mitochondrial DNA repair system (Zinovkina, 2018).

As cells can contain up to 1000 mitochondria (and even more in the case of oocytes), and each mitochondrion has multiple copies of mtDNA, then a single cell can on average hold thousands molecules of mtDNA. This mtDNA copy number is controlled by DNA replication as well as mitochondrial dynamics (Falkenberg, 2018). mtDNA replication factors are distinct from nuclear factors and rather related to factors present in bacteriophages. The mtDNA is replicated and repaired by DNA polymerase γ (POL γ). POL γ is unable to recognize dsDNA as a template, therefore a DNA helicase, TWINKLE, is required to form a replication fork resolving a DNA duplex. The most acknowledged model of mtDNA replication is the classic strand-displacement model (Falkenberg, 2018; Robberson et al., 1972). According to this model, DNA synthesis is continuous on both strands. First, the replication is initiated at O_H then proceeds to generate a nascent H-strand. Meanwhile, the exposed parental H-strand is coated and protected by mitochondrial single-stranded DNA-binding protein (mtSSB). This mtSSB coating prevents the mitochondrial RNA polymerase (POLRMT) from initiating random RNA synthesis on the displaced strand. When the replication fork passes O_L, a stem-loop structure is formed. This stem-loop efficiently blocks mtSSB from binding and a short stretch of single-stranded DNA in the loop region therefore remains accessible, where POLRMT initiates RNA primer synthesis. The L-strand synthesis initiates by the replacement of POLRMT with POL γ at the 3' end of the primer. The synthesis of the two strands proceeds continuously until the two strands form full circle. Interestingly, a part of the O_H replication events prematurely terminates during the process, generating a short single-stranded DNA fragment called 7S DNA. The 7S DNA hybridizes with parental L-strand, which results in the displacement of parental H-strand. As a consequence, a particular triple-stranded displacement loop structure, named D-loop, is formed, the function of which remains to be elucidated. It is important to note that the entire molecular mechanism of the mtDNA replication has yet to be uncovered, and alternative models have been also proposed, for

example, the RITOLS (ribonucleotide incorporation throughout the lagging strand) model (Yasukawa et al., 2006).

3-1-4-3. Transcription

Bidirectional transcription of the human mtDNA initiates at distinct promoters on each strand, the HSP and the LSP, located within the major noncoding region (Figure 4). It generates near genome-length polycistronic transcripts called primary transcripts (Figure 6).

RNA synthesis relies on a DNA-dependent RNA polymerase POLRMT, which is structurally related to RNA polymerase of T7 bacteriophages (Ringel et al., 2011). Unlike bacteriophage RNA polymerases, POLRMT requires additional factors, TFAM and TFB2M (mitochondrial transcription factor B2), to recognize promoters and to initiate transcription. TFAM bound to mtDNA recruits POLRMT to the promoter, and TFB2M rearranges the conformation of POLRMT, which allows the opening of the promoter (Hillen et al., 2017; Ramachandran et al., 2017). Mitochondrial transcription elongation factor (TEFM) is known to aid POLRMT during elongation. Transcription of the L-strand is often prematurely terminated around the conserved sequence block 2 (CSB2) in the major noncoding region, resulting in a generation of 7S RNA (Nicholls and Minczuk, 2014). TEFM keeps a high processivity of POLRMT to prevent assembly of G-quadruplexes that inhibit the progress of the elongation complex at CSB2 (Agaronyan et al., 2015b; Posse et al., 2015). Given that a R-loop formed by 7S RNA play an important role in priming heavy strand DNA replication (Nicholls and Minczuk, 2014; Pham et al., 2006; Wanrooij et al., 2010), TEFM has been proposed to switch replication to transcription of the L-strand via regulating the elongation machinery (Agaronyan et al., 2015a). More recently, TEFM has been suggested to be involved in RNA metabolism in addition to transcription elongation *in vivo*, implying that the post-transcriptional regulation may initiate in a co-transcriptional manner (Jiang et al., 2019).

Transcription events from the LSP have been estimated to occur more frequently than those from the HSP (Attardi et al., 1990; Pietras et al., 2018). However, gene expression on each strand is post-transcriptionally regulated, resulting in a higher abundance of the H-strand transcripts, as described later.

Figure 6. Overview of mitochondrial gene expression. Adapted from (D'Souza and Minczuk, 2018),

3-1-4-4. Post-transcriptional regulation: RNA processing

After the all-in-one transcription, nascent RNA undergoes post-transcriptional regulation in a gene-specific manner, which reflects the distinct amount and half-life of each transcript (Chujo et al., 2012; Mercer et al., 2011).

Post-transcriptional maturation is initiated with RNA processing. As the polycistronic primary transcripts include mRNAs and rRNAs that are mostly flanked by tRNAs, individual RNAs are released through tRNA excision by RNase P (the 5' end cleavage) and RNase Z (the 3' end cleavage). This is known as the classic 'tRNA punctuation model' (Brzezniak et al., 2011; Holzmann et al., 2008; Ojala et al., 1981; Reinhard et al., 2017; Sanchez et al., 2011) (Figure 7).

The ancient and essential RNase P is characterized as one of only two ribozymes present in all kingdoms of life. However, in mammals, unlike nuclear RNase P containing a catalytic RNA subunit, mitochondrial RNase P is entirely proteinaceous and composed of three subunits, MRPP1-3. MRPP3, also known as PRORP, is the catalytic ribonuclease with

homology to PiIT N-terminus (PIN) domain-like metallonucleases, and its endonuclease activity is strictly dependent on MRPP1/2 (Holzmann et al., 2008; Reinhard et al., 2015). MRPP1, which is a tRNA methyltransferase, also known as TRMT10C, forms a strong sub-complex with MRPP2 and exhibits the N1-methylation of adenosine and guanosine at position 9 (m¹A9 or m¹G9 respectively) of tRNAs. A majority of human mitochondrial tRNAs includes this m¹A9 or m¹G9, which is important for the proper folding of at least one mitochondrial tRNA (Helm et al., 1999). The role of MRPP2 (HSD17B10) in the tRNA 5' end processing is not clear. While the entire role of the MRPP1/2 subcomplex in the 5' end processing remains unclear, this subcomplex has recently been proposed to enhance the efficiency of the 3' end processing by RNase Z, which suggests that the MRPP1/2 subcomplex may rather represent a kind of platform for tRNA maturation (Reinhard et al., 2017). ELAC2 (RNase Z), which belongs to the metallo-lactamase superfamily, is a dual-localized enzyme that is responsible for the 3' end processing of both mitochondrial and nuclear pre-tRNAs (Brzezniak et al., 2011; Rossmannith, 2011; Sanchez et al., 2011). Recent *in vivo* studies have revealed that both MRPP3 and ELAC2 are essential for mouse embryonic development and that tRNA processing is hierarchically organised such that the tRNA 5' end cleavage by RNase P precedes the 3' end cleavage by RNase Z (Rackham et al., 2016; Siira et al., 2018).

The tRNA punctuation model is not sufficient to explain all the RNA processing events in human mitochondria. After excision of tRNAs, there remain four non-canonical precursor mRNAs with tRNA-less junctions: the 3' UTR of ND6, the 5' UTR of COX1, between ND5 and CYTB mRNA, and between ATP8/6 and COX3 mRNA (Figure 7). How these non-canonical junctions are processed remains to be elucidated. Recently, the FASTK (Fas-activated serine/threonine kinase) family proteins, FASTK and FASTKD1-5, have emerged as promising candidates for non-canonical mtRNA processing (Jourdain et al., 2017). The study of their roles in non-canonical mtRNA processing has been the main focus of my PhD thesis, which will be further described below.

ND5-CYTB precursor RNA includes a non-coding sequence corresponding to antisense ND6, or non-coding ND6 (ncND6), and antisense tRNA^E (nctRNA^E) between ND5 and CYTB mRNA. An endonucleolytic cleavage has been estimated to occur at the 3' end of antisense tRNA^E (Mercer et al., 2011). While mature CYTB mRNA begins with a start codon at the 5' end, mature ND5 contains a long 3' UTR (Temperley et al., 2010b). We and others have recently reported that ND5-CYTB RNA processing is impaired in the loss of either FASTKD4 or FASTKD5 (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Boehm et al., 2017). This RNA processing impairment has also been observed in mice bearing a homozygous knockout of a

mitochondrial RNA binding protein PTC2 (Xu et al., 2008), which will be described in 3-1-4-10.

Pre-COX1 transcript contains a 5' UTR that corresponds to the non-coding sequence complementary to a cluster of tRNAs (tRNA^A, tRNA^N, tRNA^C, and tRNA^Y). Pre-COX1 is estimated to be processed within the short 12 nt non-coding sequence between antisense tRNA^Y and COX1 (5892-5903 of mtDNA) (Mercer et al., 2011; Temperley et al., 2010b). FASTKD5 has been proposed to be involved in this processing (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015). MRPP1 has been also postulated to play a role in this RNA processing, probably independently from its function in tRNA processing (Sanchez et al., 2011). The two proteins may cooperate for this RNA processing event.

ATP8/6-COX3 is the most exceptional non-canonical precursor RNA, because it lacks an extra non-coding sequence at the processing site between ATP6 and COX3 mRNA. This suggests that individual non-canonical RNA processing event may happen through independent mechanisms, which is also supported by the involvement of different sets of proteins (Table 2). FASTKD5 is the only known enzyme involved in this RNA processing event (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015). Interestingly, a recent RNase footprint assay has shown that MRPP1(TRMT10C), which is an indispensable subunit of the RNase P complex, binds around the ATP8/6-COX3 processing site in addition to tRNAs (Liu et al., 2013). This suggests that MRPP1 has a potential role in this RNA processing, whereas another study demonstrated that silencing of MRPP1-MRPP3 or ELAC2 does not influence the ATP8/6-COX3 junction cleavage (Wolf and Mootha, 2014). The junction between ATP6 and COX3 mRNA has been predicted to include a secondary structure (Mercer et al., 2011).

ND6 is the only protein-coding gene encoded on the L-strand. ND6 mRNA includes various lengths of 3' extension and the precise position of the 3' end of the mature ND6 mRNA is unclear (Slomovic et al., 2005). The heterogeneous ND6 mRNA population might include several processing or degradation intermediates mediated by the mtRNA degradosome, which is composed of a RNA helicase SUV3 and the 3' to 5' exoribonuclease PNPase (detailed in 3-1-4-5). Our group has reported that mitochondrial FASTK (mtFASTK) specifically binds to pre-ND6 transcript to block its degradation by the mtRNA degradosome, thereby generating mature ND6 mRNA (Jourdain et al., 2015). The involvement of the mtRNA degradosome in pre-ND6 RNA processing is supported by the association of the mtRNA degradosome with GRSF1 (G-rich sequence factor 1). GRSF1 is a RNA binding protein that binds to G-quadruplexes (G4s), melting these particular RNA secondary structures that would otherwise block the RNA degradation by the degradosome (Pietras et

al., 2018). This GRSF1-mediated G4 melting helps the mtRNA degradosome decay G4-rich L-strand transcripts and possibly the 3' end trimming of pre-ND6 protected by mtFASTK (Jourdain et al., 2015; Jourdain et al., 2013; Pietras et al., 2018).

Figure 7. Schematic representation of RNA processing in human mitochondria. The tRNAs cleaved off from the polycistronic primary transcripts by RNase P at the 5' end and then by RNase Z at the 3' end in order. This releases most individual rRNA, mRNA, and tRNA. Each RNA is then subjected to maturation. However, there remain four pre-mRNAs that include non-tRNA junctions (ND5-CYTB, ATP8/6-COX3, pre-ND6, and pre-COX1), which are processed by unknown mechanisms. Modified from (Hallberg and Larsson, 2014).

Noncanonical precursor RNA	RNA processing factors
ND5-CYTB	FASTKD4, FASTKD5, and PTC2
Pre-COX1 (5'UTR-COX1)	FASTKD5 and MRPP1
ATP8/6-COX3	FASTKD5
Pre-ND6 (ND6-3'UTR)	FASTK, PNPase, Suv3, and GRSF1

Table 2. List of human mitochondrial non-canonical precursor RNAs with proposed processing factors

3-1-4-5. Post-transcriptional regulation: RNA stabilisation and decay

Mitochondrial RNA degradation is mediated by the mtRNA degradosome, which is composed of polynucleotide phosphorylase (PNPase), which exhibits 3'-5' exoribonuclease activity, and an ATP-dependent helicase hSuv3p (Suv3) (Borowski et al., 2013; Lin et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2009). The mtRNA degradosome localises together with mtRNA in distinct foci named degradation foci (D-foci) (Borowski et al., 2013). The knockdown of PNPase results in a longer half-life of transcripts and the accumulation of RNA decay intermediates. Despite longer half-life, the amount of most mature transcripts is decreased by PNPase knockdown, accompanied by increased levels of their complementary ncRNAs. Interestingly, this is not the case with all the transcripts. For example, the mature ND3 mRNA level is rather elevated when PNPase is knocked down. Overexpression of a dominant negative mutant of Suv3 lacking ATPase and helicase activities leads to an accumulation of decay intermediates and a decrease in mature transcripts, which is also the case with the knockdown of PNPase (Szczesny et al., 2010). Overexpression of the inactive Suv3 also results in the accumulation of aberrant RNA species with extended 3' polyadenine (poly(A)) tails. In yeast, the helicase activity of Suv3 is especially important for the degradation of highly structured RNA (Razew et al., 2018). The human mtRNA degradosome has been shown to degrade double-stranded RNAs (dsRNAs) through a 3' but not 5' single-strand extension (Wang et al., 2009), which may explain why L-strand transcripts are much less abundant than H-strand transcripts despite a higher activity of the LSP (Attardi et al., 1990). The degradation of G4-rich transcripts derived from the L-strand by the human mtRNA degradosome is also facilitated by GRSF1, as described in 3-1-4-4 (Pietras et al., 2018). The mtRNA degradosome is unable to degrade small RNA molecules shorter than ~4 nt in length (Lin et al., 2012). REXO2 has been recently characterised as a mitochondrial dinucleotidase, which prevents an accumulation of dinucleotides that initiate aberrant promoter-independent transcription as primers (Nicholls et al., 2019). More recently, REXO2 has been postulated to cooperate with the mtRNA degradosome to degrade mitochondrial transcripts shorter than 40 nt, as well as degradation products resulting from the mtRNA degradosome activity. These very short transcripts appear to inhibit the catalytic activity of PNPase. Following transcription of both strands, the mitochondrial transcripts are prone to form dsRNA. A recent study has revealed that the mtRNA degradosome prevents the accumulation of mitochondrial dsRNA, which has a key role in the regulation of the innate immune system (Dhir et al., 2018) (see 3-1-4-12).

Transcripts derived from the HSP are stabilized by leucine-rich pentapeptide rich domain containing protein (LRPPRC) (Siira et al., 2017). The absence of LRPPRC leads to a decrease of all the mRNAs, except ND6 mRNA, but does not affect rRNAs and tRNAs (Ruzzenente et al., 2012; Sasarman et al., 2010; Siira et al., 2017). LRPPRC mainly associates and stabilizes translationally inactive mRNAs (Ruzzenente et al., 2012). Recent studies have shown that LRPPRC relaxes the secondary structures of the heavy strand-derived mRNAs, which promotes polyadenylation and translation (Chujo et al., 2012; Ruzzenente et al., 2012; Siira et al., 2017). LRPPRC forms a strong complex with a stem-loop interacting RNA-binding protein (SLIRP) (Harmel et al., 2013). SLIRP interacts with LRPPRC to stabilize it, but is dispensable for LRPPRC-mediated RNA polyadenylation (Lagouge et al., 2015).

3-1-4-6. Post-transcriptional regulation: RNA modification

Human mitochondrial rRNAs, tRNAs, and mRNAs undergo a variety of modifications that are important for their structure, function, and the downstream events of gene expression (Rebelo-Guiomar et al., 2019).

All the human mitochondrial mRNAs, except ND6 mRNA, undergo 3' polyadenylation catalysed by mitochondrial poly(A) polymerase (mtPAP) (Bai et al., 2011; Tomecki et al., 2004). This polyadenylation is also known to be facilitated by LRPPRC as described above in 3-1-4-5. The role of the poly(A)-tail has not been fully understood yet. Given that 7 of 11 mitochondrial mRNAs lack a 3' stop codon, the polyadenylation takes part in the genesis of stop codons. However, how polyadenylation regulates translation efficiency remains unclear. Polyadenylation has been shown to regulate the stability of mRNAs in a mRNA-specific manner. The loss of mtPAP leads to a decrease in the steady-state level of mRNAs encoding complex IV, whereas the amount of complex I mRNAs is not affected (ND3) or even elevated (ND1), which affects translation and results in the defective assembly of complex I and IV (Nagaike et al., 2005; Wilson et al., 2014).

The poly(A)-tail can be removed by the mitochondrial deadenylase PDE12 (Rorbach et al., 2011). Similar to the loss of mtPAP, overexpression of PDE12 leads to a decrease in the steady-state levels of COX1 and COX2 mRNAs, although ND1 and ND2 mRNA levels increase whereas the other transcripts are not affected, which results in defective assembly of complex I and IV (Rorbach et al., 2011). More recent studies showed that the knockout of PDE12 does not affect the steady-state level of mRNAs, which suggests that their priority substrates are not mRNAs (Pearce et al., 2017b). The same study also demonstrated that PDE12 selectively removes aberrant poly(A)-tails in tRNAs and rRNAs.

Recent studies have suggested that the mRNAs also undergo internal modifications, including methylation and pseudouridylation (Rebello-Guiomar et al., 2019). Such post-transcriptional modification might have a key role in the regulation of specific gene expression. For instance, m^1A is only found in ND5 mRNA, and this modification inhibits translation (Safra et al., 2017). This specific methylation is catalysed by TRMT10C, a mitochondrial methyltransferase known to modify tRNAs (see 3-1-4-4), and recognizes a particular secondary structure of ND5 mRNA that mimics a T-loop of tRNAs. This dynamic methylation has been proposed to have a key role during embryonic development to mark maternal transcripts and keep them stable until zygotic mitochondrial transcription is activated (Safra et al., 2017).

Human mitochondrial tRNAs undergo distinct modifications for maturation. The wobble base, which is the first position of anticodon, the position 34, is known as a key tRNA modification site (Rebello-Guiomar et al., 2019). As the third letter of the codon varies while coding for the same amino acid, the wobble base is subjected to different modifications (e.g. f^5C34 , τm^5U , and τm^5s^2U) to facilitate formation of a wobble base pairing with the target codon in a specific manner (D'Souza and Minczuk, 2018). The position 37 is also often modified to strengthen the codon-anticodon interaction. Pseudouridylation has been shown to occur at different positions of tRNAs to increase their structural rigidity. The 3' CCA, which is essential for tRNA aminoacylation, is not encoded within the genome and therefore post-transcriptionally added by tRNA-nucleotidyltransferase 1 (TRNT1) (Nagaike et al., 2001). Once tRNAs are matured and modified with the 3' CCA, they are loaded with cognate amino acids by mitochondrial aminoacyl-tRNA synthetases (aaRSs). While most these aaRSs are unique to mitochondria, lysyl-tRNA synthetase (LysRS) and glycyl-tRNA synthetase (GlyRS) are exceptionally encoded within the same nuclear genes as their cytosolic isoforms (Chihara et al., 2007; Tolkunova et al., 2000). These exceptional aaRSs are transferred into mitochondria because of internal mitochondrial targeting sequences. Of note, mitochondrial tRNA^{Gln} is exceptionally aminoacylated in a two-step manner. First, a Glu is loaded onto the tRNA^{Gln} by mitochondrial glutamyl-tRNA synthase (GluRS), then this Glu-tRNA^{Gln} is transamidated into Gln-tRNA^{Gln} by GatCAB amidotransferase (Nagao et al., 2009).

Mammalian rRNAs undergo the following modifications: ribose 2'-O-methylation, base methylation, and pseudouridylation (Rebello-Guiomar et al., 2019). Defects in these modifications have been demonstrated to impair mitoribosome biogenesis and translation (Boczonadi and Horvath, 2014).

3-1-4-7. Mitoribosome biogenesis

The 55S mammalian mitoribosome consists of a small 28S subunit (SSU) and a large 39S subunit (LSU) (Greber and Ban, 2016). The SSU contains the 12S rRNA with about 30 proteins, while the LSU is composed of the 16S rRNA with about 50 proteins. Mitoribosomes are unique and different from bacterial ribosomes. Mitoribosomes lost rRNA during evolution while their protein content increased (Ott et al., 2016). An important characteristic of mammalian mitoribosomes is the absence of 5S rRNA found in the central protuberance of the large subunit of nearly all prokaryotic and eukaryotic cytoplasmic ribosomes. The 5S rRNA is replaced with a mitochondrial tRNA (tRNA^V in human and rat or tRNA^F in bovine and porcine) in mitoribosomes (Brown et al., 2014; Chrzanowska-Lightowlers et al., 2017; D'Souza and Minczuk, 2018; Rorbach et al., 2016).

Despite recent advances in understanding the structure of mammalian mitoribosomes (Brown et al., 2014; Greber et al., 2015; Greber et al., 2014), the mechanisms of their assembly have been poorly understood. This process needs a perfect coordination between protein synthesis occurring in the cytosol and rRNA transcription occurring in mitochondria. Proteins involved in the mitoribosome biogenesis include mitochondrial DEAD-box RNA helicases DHX30 and DDX28 (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Tu and Barrientos, 2015), a mitochondrial RNA chaperone ERAL1 (Dennerlein et al., 2010), FASTKD2 (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015), GRSF1 (Antonicka et al., 2013; Jourdain et al., 2013), and a GTP binding protein GTPBP10 (Maiti et al., 2018). Because several of these proteins are found to colocalise with MRGs, it is likely that MRGs represent the sites where the small and large subunits of the mitoribosomes assemble.

3-1-4-8. Translation

Mitochondrial translation is a multistep process that employs distinct factors for initiation, elongation, termination, and recycling (Hallberg and Larsson, 2014). The MRC subunits encoded in the mitochondrial genome are co-translationally inserted in the IMM, which implies that the mitoribosomes are in close proximity to the membrane. MRPL45 has been proposed to anchor the LSU onto the IMM (Greber et al., 2014).

Mammalian mitochondrial translation initiation has been shown to be regulated by initiation factors mtIF2 and mtIF3 (Gaur et al., 2008; Haque and Spremulli, 2008). Mitochondrial translation is initiated with a N-terminal formyl-methionine (fMet) residue. mtIF2 facilitates the association of the fMet-tRNA^{Met} with the mRNA, and subsequent

translation initiation steps (Gaur et al., 2008). Since mammalian mitochondrial mRNAs lack a 5' UTR, and start with an initiation codon, how the first ribosome is placed appropriately remains to be elucidated.

Translation elongation has been shown to be controlled by various mitochondrial elongation factors, including EFTu (TUFM), EFTs (TSFM) and EFGM (GFM1) (D'Souza and Minczuk, 2018).

Translation termination is triggered by a stop codon. While the entire mechanism remains unclear, a mitochondrial translation termination factor mtRF1a has been proposed to be sufficient for translation termination of all 13 mitochondrial-encoded proteins (D'Souza and Minczuk, 2018; Soleimanpour-Lichaei et al., 2007). Interestingly, ND6 and COX1 mRNAs lack 3' end UAA or UAG stop codons. It has been shown that the formation of the UAG stop codon for these 2 transcripts results from a frameshift of the mitoribosome (Temperley et al., 2010a).

3-1-4-9. Non-coding RNA expression

In addition to the 37 mitochondrial genes, the human mtDNA also encodes non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs) (Dietrich et al., 2015; Dong et al., 2017; Gusic and Prokisch, 2020). In contrast to the gene-enriched H-strand polycistronic transcript, the L-strand polycistronic transcript only encodes eight tRNAs and the ND6 mRNA that span long stretches of non-coding sequences (Figure 4). Recent transcriptome studies have shown that various ncRNAs in human mitochondria are expressed, despite being less abundant than their complementary coding RNAs (Mercer et al., 2011; Rackham et al., 2011). Interestingly, the mitochondrial ncRNAs are specifically processed at distinct sites by unknown mechanisms, and only some specific transcripts are abundant (Rackham et al., 2011). Long ncCYTB, ncND6, and ncND5 (lncCYTB, lncND6, and lncND5), all of which locate adjacently in the mitochondrial genome, are known as particularly enriched ncRNAs in human mitochondria. They are mostly processed around the sequences complementary to tRNAs and their amount is dependent on RNase P and Z, which suggests that these tRNA processing enzymes may play a role in the processing of ncRNAs (Rackham et al., 2011). Nonetheless, a recent RNase footprint assay has shown that TRMT10C (MRPP1), which is an indispensable subunit of the RNase P complex, does not bind to ncRNAs as it does to tRNAs (Liu et al., 2013). Therefore, this RNase P/Z-dependent ncRNA processing model is questionable. While the functions and the physiological significance of these ncRNAs remain unclear, they might have regulatory roles in the stability of coding RNAs or/and other post-transcriptional regulation steps, since the

ncRNAs have been shown to form intermolecular duplexes (Rackham et al., 2011). This fine-tuning is estimated to be important especially in the regulation of low abundant mRNAs such as ND5 and ND6 (Chujo et al., 2012). Moreover, a recent transcriptome study showed that loci near the 5' end of the L-strand polycistronic transcript including ncCYTB, ND6, and ncND5 RNA have a tendency to form mitochondrial dsRNA with their complementary strand, whereas this is less frequent for ncRNA present at the 3' end of the LSP-derived polycistronic transcript (Dhir et al., 2018). These studies suggest that some specific ncRNAs seem to be stabilised by forming a duplex, and that this hybridization may result in an alteration of the expression of complementary mRNAs, which would be less accessible to a number of enzymes.

The knockdown of several RNA processing factors (MRPP1, MRPP3, ELAC2, PTC1, and PTC2) have been shown to lead to a decrease in the steady-state level of ncCYTB, ncND6, and ncND5 RNAs in a gene-specific manner (Rackham et al., 2011). Three out of these five proteins (MRPP3, PTC1, and PTC2) contain pentatricopeptide repeat (PPR) domains, which suggests that PPR proteins may have key regulatory roles in mitochondrial ncRNA expression (the PPR proteins are described below in 3-1-4-10). Since most ncRNAs are transcribed from the LSP, RNA degradation by the mtRNA degradosome and GRSF1 may play an important role in the ncRNA regulation as described above in 3-1-4-5.

Several chimeric mtDNA-encoded long ncRNAs have also been identified in mitochondria. For instance, sense mitochondrial ncRNA consists of the 16S rRNA together with 815 nt 5'-leader sequence derived from its complementary strand (Villegas et al., 2007). The sense mitochondrial ncRNA forms a long intramolecular duplex of 820 bp (Dietrich et al., 2015). The sense mitochondrial ncRNA is exclusively expressed in proliferating tumour cells but not in healthy cells, which suggests that this ncRNA may regulate cell proliferation (Villegas et al., 2007). Another example is long intergenic non-coding RNA predicting CARDiac remodeling (LIPCARN), of which the 5' half maps to ncCYTB and the 3' half aligns to ncCOX2 (Dorn, 2014). This aberrant ncRNA is especially enriched in patients with severe heart failure, which implies its potential function in the development of heart diseases (Yang et al., 2014). How these chimeric mitochondrial ncRNAs are generated remains to be elucidated. Furthermore, the mitochondrial genome transcribes some small ncRNAs and micro RNAs, the physiological role of which remain largely uncharacterised (Dietrich et al., 2015).

In addition to mitochondrially-encoded ncRNAs, there are reports of ncRNAs, especially long ncRNAs (lncRNAs) transcribed from the nuclear DNA (nDNA). These

nuclear lncRNAs are emerging as key regulators of nuclear gene expression. They include natural antisense transcripts of protein-coding genes, mRNA-like intergenic transcripts (lincRNAs), and primary RNA polymerase II (Pol II) transcript-derived unconventional lncRNAs (e. g. MALAT1, sno-lncRNA, circular intronic RNA, and circRNA). They exhibit diverse functions in gene expression, widely ranging from chromatin remodelling to posttranslational modifications as reviewed in (Yao et al., 2019). It has recently been reported that some of the nDNA-encoded lncRNAs such as MALAT1 and the H1 RNA component of nuclear RNase P can be imported into mitochondria, as well as shorter ncRNAs including 5S rRNA, tRNAs, and miRNAs. However, mitochondrial RNA import is highly controversial, and the role of these ncRNAs remains unclear (Gammage et al., 2018; Gusic and Prokisch, 2020; Jeandard et al., 2019).

3-1-4-10. Pentatricopeptide repeat domain proteins: major post-transcriptional regulators

The pentatricopeptide repeat (PPR) domain proteins are one of the major organelle post-transcriptional regulators, which recognize and bind RNA in a sequence-specific manner through their superhelix structure (Filipovska and Rackham, 2012; Manna, 2015). In mammals, only seven PPR proteins (POLRMT, LRPPRC, MRPP3, PTCD1-3, and MRPS27) have been identified, all localized within the mitochondrial matrix, (Lightowlers and Chrzanowska-Lightowlers, 2013) with some of them, MRPP3, PTCD1, and PTCD2 being the components of MRGs. Similar to the FASTK protein family, the PPR proteins play key roles in mitochondrial gene expression, ranging from transcription (POLRMT) and RNA processing (MRPP3 and PTCD2) to RNA stabilization and translation, (LRPPRC, PTCD1, PTCD3, and MRPS27) (Perks et al., 2018), as already described in previous chapters.

The pentatricopeptide domain (PTCD)-containing proteins, PTCD1-3, are key post-transcriptional regulators. PTCD1 and PTCD3 share homologies with assembly factors for MRC complex I in *Neurospora crassa* and for complex V in plant, respectively (Xu et al., 2008). PTCD1 associates with tRNAs and their unprocessed precursor RNAs, suggesting its potential involvement in tRNA processing or/and stability (Liu et al., 2013; Rackham et al., 2009). Recently, heart- and skeletal-muscle-specific PTCD1-KO mice have been characterised (Perks et al., 2018). This study revealed that PTCD1 binds to 16S rRNA and associates with FASTKD2 and RPUSD4. Consistent with the previous reports that FASTKD2 and RPUSD4 form a 16S rRNA maturation module (Antonicka et al., 2017; Arroyo et al.,

2016; Perks et al., 2018; Zaganelli et al., 2017), PTC1 was found to be essential for the pseudouridylation of 16S and the biogenesis of LSU. In addition, the loss of PTC1 led to increased mitochondrial transcription in contrast to a specific decrease in the steady-state level of 16S rRNA. Other studies have reported a potential genetic association of PTC1 with Alzheimer's disease (Fleck et al., 2019; Pa et al., 2019). PTC3 also regulates mitochondrial translation, but in a different manner from PTC1. Knockdown or overexpression of PTC3 does not affect the steady-state levels of mtRNAs, which suggests that PTC3 is not involved in either RNA processing or stability (Davies et al., 2009). PTC3 associates with 12S rRNA and the SSU to regulate mitochondrial translation but does not play a role in mitoribosome assembly (Lightowers and Chrzanowska-Lightowers, 2013). Another study also reported the association of PTC3 with the SSU via the C-terminus of mtIF3 (Haque et al., 2011). Unlike PTC1 and PTC3, PTC2 has been proposed to be involved in mRNA processing. A study of a mouse model with PTC2 gene disruption showed that the processing of the ND5-CYTB junction is impaired (Xu et al., 2008). Consistently, Xu et al. also found that CYTB protein biogenesis is decreased with tissue-specific reduction of complex I and III activity in heart and liver where PTC2 protein is highly expressed (Xu et al., 2008). Intriguingly, recent clinical studies have proposed PTC2 as a biomarker for Alzheimer's disease. The level of PTC2 protein expressed in brain together with autoantibody directed against PTC2 are significantly high in Alzheimer patients (Acharya et al., 2012; Nagele et al., 2011). Together, these observations suggest that both PTC1 and PTC2 may play a role in Alzheimer's disease.

In addition to their roles in mtRNA processing, PTC1 and PTC2 potentially regulate the processing or/and stability of several ncRNAs as previously described in 3-1-4-9.

3-1-4-11. Mitochondrial gene expression and mitochondrial diseases

Mitochondrial diseases are one of the most common inherited metabolic disorders, which are defined by either spontaneous or inherited mutations in both nuclear and mitochondrial genomes (Russell et al., 2020; Suomalainen and Battersby, 2018). Mitochondrial diseases affect around one in 2,000 individuals and they can present at any age and manifest in virtually any organ. Various manifestations of mitochondrial diseases are classified according to neurological and non-neurological symptoms: the former includes cognitive impairment, epilepsy, stroke, parkinsonism, myopathy, hearing deficit, visual impairment, etc., while the latter includes respiratory failure, cardiomyopathy, liver failure,

bone marrow failure, diabetes, etc. Despite remarkable improvements in the genetic and metabolic diagnosis of these severe progressive disorders, there are still no curative treatments.

Genetic mutations that disrupt mitochondrial gene expression essential for OXPHOS are a common source of mitochondrial diseases (Suomalainen and Battersby, 2018). A number of diseases resulting from altered proteins involved in mtDNA maintenance and expression, including MRPP1, MRPP2, ELAC2, FASTKD2, MTPAP, LRPPRC, PNPT1, TRMU, TRMT5, GTPBP3, etc., have been reported (Boczonadi et al., 2018) (Suomalainen and Battersby, 2018). In addition to these nuclear-encoded proteins, mutations in mtDNA also result in pathologies and presently, hundreds of different point mutations and deletions of mtDNA have been associated with a wide range of clinical manifestations (Stewart and Chinnery, 2015). Because a cell contains multi-copies of mtDNA molecules (ranging from hundreds to thousands highly depending on the cell type), the clinical severity resulting from a given mutation in the mtDNA is usually assessed by pathogenic heteroplasmy defined as the proportion of mutant over WT mtDNA. Once a certain threshold of heteroplasmy is reached, typically >60-80%, the cell manifests a defect in OXPHOS. In other words, the cell remains fully functional as far as the heteroplasmy level is below the threshold. For decades, it has been known that heteroplasmy level can change markedly during germline transmission. Studies have postulated that only a small proportion of the total number of mtDNAs are passed on from mother to offspring, resulting in randomly varied heteroplasmy levels in offsprings (Olivo et al., 1983; Upholt and Dawid, 1977). This widely accepted mitochondrial ‘genetic bottleneck theory’ makes the genetic research of mitochondrial disorders challenging. In addition to the inherited pathogenic mutations, spontaneous mutations in mtDNA are also a cause of mitochondrial diseases, especially in aging.

3-1-4-12. Mitochondrial genetic molecules and innate immunity

Mitochondria serve a platform for innate immune signalling: recent discoveries have suggested that the mitochondria appear to be a source of molecules for host defence, which provides a possible explanation for endosymbiosis (Grazioli and Pugin, 2018; Mills et al., 2017). For instance, mitochondrial ROS is employed for the digestion of phagocytosed pathogens. Mitochondria are involved in damage-associated molecular pattern (DAMP), and three major innate immune pathways, RIG-I/MAVS, NLRP3 and TLR9, are all dependent on mitochondria. mtDNA acts as a major signal in mitochondrial DAMP (mtDAMP), as well as

mtROS and cardiolipin. The release of mtDNA into the cytosol in necrotic cells is detected by cytosolic sensors, which eventually triggers the mitochondrial DAMP (Mills et al., 2017). The cytosolic mtDNA is sensed by TLR9, which in turn activates the NF- κ B signalling pathway. Also, leaked mtDNA activates the NLRP3 inflammasome. Finally, the mtDNA activates the STING pathway via cGAS, which leads to an increased interferon-regulatory factor 3 (IRF3)-dependent gene expression, including induction of type I interferons.

Similar to mtDNA, mitochondrial dsRNA has been recently characterised as a novel signalling molecule for mtDAMP (Dhir et al., 2018; Linder and Hornung, 2018). The mitochondrial dsRNA released into the cytoplasm via Bax/Bak pores is detected by a cytoplasmic dsRNA sensor MDA5, a major RNA virus sensor that, in turn, activates a type I interferon response through the MAVS signalling pathway. Dhir et al. also found that knockdown of PNPase leads to massive accumulation of mitochondrial dsRNA that escapes into the cytoplasm. Consistently, patients carrying mutations in the PNPase-encoding PNPT1 gene displayed mitochondrial dsRNA accumulation coupled with upregulation of interferon signature genes. The mtRNA degradosome has been thus proposed to prevent the accumulation of mitochondrial dsRNA and the activation of potent innate immune defence mechanisms against viral and microbial attack. However, it is important to note that, surprisingly, knockdown of Suv3, which also leads to accumulation of dsRNA in mitochondria, is not accompanied by its release into the cytosol. In *Drosophila melanogaster*, mtPAP knockout also leads to the accumulation of mitochondrial dsRNA similar to the loss of PNPase in mammalian cells, suggesting that the status of 3' end poly(A) extension by mtPAP dynamically affects the level of mitochondrial dsRNA presumably through controlling the mtRNA degradosome-dependent RNA degradation (Pajak et al., 2019).

3-2. The FASTK protein family

The Fas-activated serine/threonine kinase (FASTK) family proteins are key post-transcriptional regulators of mammalian mitochondrial gene expression, similar to the PPR proteins (Jourdain et al., 2017). This putative RNA binding protein family includes six members, FASTK, the founding member, and its homologs FASTK domain-containing protein 1 to 5 (FASTKD1-5) (Figure 8). While they all exclusively localize within the mitochondrial matrix, FASTK is the only member also with non-mitochondrial localization.

The founding member FASTK was originally introduced as a kinase (Tian et al., 1995). A recent study reported an ATPase activity of FASTK *in vitro*, which implies that FASTK may exhibit a kinase activity (Khan et al., 2018). However, critical active site residues are not conserved within the family and the kinase activity of these proteins has been seriously questioned (Jourdain et al., 2017). FASTK was initially characterised as an interacting partner of T-cell intracellular antigen-1 (TIA-1), an apoptotic effector (Tian et al., 1995). TIA-1 is a RNA-binding protein that regulates Fas receptor alternative splicing in the nucleus (Förch et al., 2000) and stress-induced translation silencing in stress granules (Li et al., 2004b) (Kedersha et al., 2005). In contrast, FASTK is known to inhibit Fas- and UV-induced apoptosis (Li et al., 2004b). FASTK was also proposed to associate with Bcl-xL, which is a member of the Bcl-2 protein family, which is composed of key regulators of mitochondrial apoptosis (Li et al., 2004a). These results are controversial and have not been reproduced in our laboratory. More recently, FASTK was found to localise within cytosolic RNA granules (stress granules and P-bodies) (Kedersha et al., 2005), which is consistent with the ability of this protein to bind TIA1. In stress granules, FASTK prevents the TIA1-mediated translation silencing in response to cellular stress (Li et al., 2004b). In addition to the cytosolic RNA granules localization, FASTK is also concentrated in nuclear speckles, where it regulates the alternative splicing of fibroblast growth factor receptor 2 (FGFR2) and Fas receptor (Izquierdo and Valcarcel, 2007; Simarro et al., 2007). FASTK and TIA-1 act independently in FGFR2 alternative splicing.

The mitochondrial isoform of FASTK (mtFASTK) is translated from an alternative translation initiation site, at position 34, followed by a cryptic mitochondrial targeting signal (MTS) (Figure 8A). mtFASTK was recently identified in the mitochondrial matrix, concentrated within the MRGs, where mitochondrial post-transcriptional regulation mainly occurs (Jourdain et al., 2015). Interestingly, as FASTKD, FASTKD1, FASTKD2, FASTKD5 also localize to the MRGs, whereas FASTKD3 and FASTKD4 are not particularly enriched

in these structures and appear to fill the entire mitochondrial matrix. As detailed in Figure 8, the FASTK family proteins regulate the steady-state level of a variety of mtRNAs, mainly mRNAs, in a distinct and specific fashion. Whereas some members appear to cooperate, others act in opposite directions. For instance, ND3 mRNA level is decreased by FASTKD1, FASTKD3, and FASTKD5, but increased by FASTKD4. Consistent with their functional complexity, the FASTK family proteins have been proposed to be involved in numerous steps of the post-transcriptional regulation: RNA stability alteration, RNA processing, RNA modification, mitoribosome assembly, and translation regulation (Figure 8B). Their precise molecular mechanisms, however, remain to be elucidated.

The importance of the FASTK family in mitochondrial and cellular integrity is underlined by the association of *FASTKD2* gene mutations and severe symptoms, such as MELAS (mitochondrial myopathy, encephalopathy, lactic acidosis, and stroke-like episodes) (Boczonadi et al., 2018; Ghezzi et al., 2008; Wei et al., 2020b; Yoo et al., 2017).

Although FASTK family proteins can exhibit various and even opposing functions in some cases, they share the same domain architecture: FAST_1 (FASTK-like protein domain 1), FAST_2 (FASTK-like protein domain 2), and RAP (RNA-binding domain abundant in Apicomplexans) domain (Figure 8A). While all these domains remain uncharacterised, FASTK proteins are likely to be RNA binding proteins, based on UV-crosslinked mRNA pulldown assays coupled with transcriptomic analyses (Baltz et al., 2012; Castello et al., 2012). The characteristic architecture of the C-terminal domain of FASTK proteins, which provides the signature of the protein family, is evolutionarily conserved. *In silico* analysis has suggested that the FASTK family appeared early in the evolution of animals (metazoa) (Jourdain et al., 2017). For example, the ancestral placozoan *Trichoplax adhaerens*, at the root of metazoan evolution, contains three FASTK homologs, whereas yeasts and plants are devoid of FASTK proteins. The FASTK family genes have undergone duplications and losses and, in turn, most vertebrate genomes encode the complete set of the family, whereas *Drosophila melanogaster* contains only two homologs. While the combination of the three signature domains together is only present in metazoa, numerous genes encoding two of the three domains (FAST_1 and RAP) are found in more ancient organisms such as green algae and Apicomplexa. These domains can also be found separately in different proteins. The RAP is the most ancestral and abundant domain, which is present in eubacteria, archaea, viruses, and plants (Lee and Hong, 2004). The FAST_1 domain is present in plants and animals, but seems absent in prokaryotes, while the FAST_2 domain is likely unique to metazoa. It is possible

that the RAP domain, which is the most ancestral domain, fused first with FAST_1 domain, then FAST_2 domain, to form the FASTK family proteins.

We have recently found that the ancestral RAP domain appears to be structurally related to PD-(D/E)-XK nuclease superfamily (Steczkiewicz et al., 2012), a class of viral enzymes that display endonuclease activity, particularly the bacterial very short patch repair (VSR) endonucleases (1VSR) which appears structurally most related to FASTKD4 (Boehm et al., 2017). In addition to be present in FASTK proteins, several other proteins involved in RNA processing contain a RAP domain. In *Arabidopsis thaliana*, the chloroplastic RAP domain-containing protein (RAP, At2g31890) is involved in the 5' end processing of chloroplast 16S rRNA (Kleinknecht et al., 2014). In *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*, Raa3 participates in the trans-splicing of chloroplastic *psaA* mRNA (the first group II intron), which encodes one of the core constituents of photosystem I (Rivier et al., 2001a). Raa3 has been found in a RNA-protein complex including Raa4, associating with a non-coding RNA *tscA*, and notably, Raa1, a membrane-associated protein bearing a FAST_1 domain (Jacobs et al., 2013; Merendino et al., 2006). Considering that Raa1 is involved in the same trans-splicing event, especially the *tscA* RNA processing (Glanz and Kuck, 2009), the RAP domain of Raa3 and the FAST_1 domain of Raa1 may cooperate during the *psaA* mRNA trans-splicing. This suggests and supports the hypothesis that FASTK family proteins may somehow be involved in RNA processing and that some of these proteins may display endonuclease activity. Given 1) that loss of some members of the FASTK family, including FASTKD4 (Boehm et al., 2017) and FASTKD5 (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015) leads to defects in the processing of transcripts flanked by non-canonical junctions, 2) the putative structural homology of FASTKD proteins with some PD-(D/E)-XK nucleases, and 3) that proteins containing the RAP and FAST domains participate in trans-splicing in algae, we hypothesized that members of the FASTK family could exhibit an endonuclease activity and directly participate in the processing of mitochondrial non-canonical precursor transcripts. In this context, my PhD work was initiated by assessing this hypothesis.

Our current knowledge of each member of the FASTK family in mitochondria is described below.

Figure 8. Schematic representation of the FASTKD family proteins and their various roles in the mitochondrial post-transcriptional regulation. (A) All members of the protein family are predicted to be RNA binding proteins and share the same domain architecture including FAST_1, FAST_2, and RAP domain. FASTK is the only member that has a non-mitochondrial isoform, while mitochondrial FASTK (mtFASTK) is translated from an internal translation start site that initiates with a cryptic mitochondrial targeting signal (MTS) marked by an arrow. The localization of FASTK family members within the mitochondrial RNA granules (MRGs) is also mentioned. (B) Proposed mode of actions of the FASTKD protein family, as described in the main text. Modified from (Jourdain et al., 2017).

3-2-1. mtFASTK

mtFASTK is concentrated within MRGs, where it specifically regulates ND6 mRNA, the only L-strand encoded mRNA (Jourdain et al., 2015). mtFASTK interacts with the 3' end of ND6 mRNA and the 3' UTR of pre-ND6 RNA in a RAP domain-dependent fashion. mtFASTK protects pre-ND6 transcript by blocking RNA degradation by the mtRNA degradosome, thereby generating the 3' end of ND6. Consistently, FASTK-KO mice show decreased mature ND6 mRNA levels and compromised MRC complex I activity.

While the FASTK-KO mice grow to maturity with no observable phenotypic defects (Simarro et al., 2010a), macrophages derived from these mice has been recently shown to display elevated nonopsonic phagocytosis activity, correlated with reduced MRC complex I activity and activated AMPK pathway (Garcia Del Rio et al., 2018).

3-2-2. FASTKD1

FASTKD1 localizes to MRGs and the knockout of FASTKD1 in HEK293 cells leads to an accumulation of ND3 mRNA and elevated MRC complex I activity (Boehm et al., 2017; Han et al., 2017). Therefore, FASTKD1 and mtFASTK seem to display opposite effects regarding the activity of MRC complex I.

3-2-3. FASTKD2

FASTKD2 is found within MRGs, where it strongly associates with 16S rRNA (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Popow et al., 2015). Accordingly, the knockdown and knockout of FASTKD2 in cultured cells causes a decrease in 16S rRNA, which, in turn, leads to defective mitoribosome assembly and translation (Antonicka et al., 2017; Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Popow et al., 2015). FASTKD2 has been proposed to form a 16S rRNA maturation module together with RPUSD3, RPUSD4, NGRN, WBSCR16, and PTC1, which is essential for pseudouridylation of 16S rRNA (Antonicka et al., 2017; Arroyo et al., 2016; Perks et al., 2018; Zaganelli et al., 2017).

Popow et al. reported that both knockdown and knockout of FASTKD2 in HEK293 cells cause a decrease in ND6 mRNA and in 16S rRNA (Popow et al., 2015). In contrast, another study by Antonicka et al. demonstrated that FASTKD2 knockdown in human fibroblasts does not alter the steady-state level of ND6 mRNA (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015). Thus, the putative function of FASTKD2 in the regulation of ND6 mRNA needs further investigation. It is especially important to know whether this RNA regulation is dependent on the cell type.

Consistent with a cell type specificity are the results showing that loss of FASTKD2 causes defective biogenesis and activity of the OXPHOS complexes in 143B osteosarcoma cells and in HEK 293 epithelial cells (Antonicka et al., 2017; Popow et al., 2015), but not in K562 myelogenous leukemia cells (Arroyo et al., 2016). A possible explanation of this cell type-specific effect of FASTKD2 depletion may be linked to the level of expression of other FASTK family proteins and their possible compensatory function.

As mentioned above, FASTKD2 gene mutations are associated with mitochondrial diseases.

3-2-4. FASTKD3

FASTKD3 regulates the steady-state level of several mRNAs, not localizing in MRGs (Figure 8) (Boehm et al., 2016; Simarro et al., 2010b). Knockdown and knockout of FASTKD3 lead to mildly perturbed mitochondrial respiration in cultured cells. The alteration in the steady-state level of mRNAs in FASTKD3-KO cell can be rescued by expression of full-length FASTKD3 protein (Boehm et al., 2016). Importantly, this rescue was not achieved by expression of mutant FASTKD3 protein lacking either the whole RAP domain or five residues corresponding to the 3' end of the RAP domain, which suggests that the RAP domain is crucial for the function of FASTKD3 (Boehm et al., 2016). FASTKD3 facilitates the translation of COX1 without altering its mRNA level, which is characteristic to FASTKD3 within the protein family (Boehm et al., 2016). Consistently, an interactome study has suggested that FASTKD3 associates with proteins involved in mitochondrial translation as well as RNA maturation (Simarro et al., 2010b).

3-2-5. FASTKD4

FASTKD4 protein is not enriched within MRGs, but rather present throughout the mitochondrial matrix, where it appears to be loosely associated with the IMM, given that the protein can only be solubilized by alkali treatment of mitochondrial membranes (Boehm et al., 2017; Wolf and Mootha, 2014). FASTKD4 associates with mtRNAs and its knockdown or knockout decreases the steady-state level of various mRNAs (Figure 8). An ethidium bromide-based mitochondrial transcription suspension assay revealed that COX1, COX2, and ND3 mRNAs are destabilised by shFASTKD4 (Wolf and Mootha, 2014). The selection of target RNAs may rely on the RAP domain, since expression of chimeric FASTKD4 protein of which the RAP domain was replaced with the RAP domain derived from either FASTK or

FASTKD1 in FASTKD4-KO cells totally changed the profile of affected RNA species (Boehm et al., 2017). We recently discovered that the knockout of FASTKD4 leads to a defective processing of ND5-CYTB non-canonical precursor RNA, along with a decrease of the steady-state level of mature ND5 and CYTB mRNAs (Boehm et al., 2017). This implies that FASTKD4 may play a role in this non-canonical RNA processing. Interestingly, we also found that the ancestral RAP domain appears to be structurally related to PD-(D/E)-XK nuclease superfamily based on *in silico* structural modeling, particularly the bacterial very short patch repair (VSR) endonucleases (1VSR) as the closest model of FASTKD4, suggesting that the RAP domain of FASTKD4 may exhibit an endoribonuclease activity responsible for the cleavage of the ND5-CYTB junction.

Despite the role of FASTKD4 in mitochondrial mRNA metabolism, its depletion neither caused a significant impairment in mitochondrial translation nor in mitochondrial respiration in cultured cells (Boehm et al., 2017).

3-2-6. FASTKD5

FASTKD5 is enriched in MRGs, where it regulates a variety of mRNAs and non-canonical RNA processing (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015) (Figure 8). Knockdown of FASTKD5 leads to an impaired processing of ATP8/6-COX3, ND5-CYTB, and pre-COX1 non-canonical precursor RNAs. Consequently, siFASTKD5 results in defective translation, particularly pronounced for COX1 protein synthesis, along with an impaired assembly of MRC complex IV. While FASTKD5-depleted cells show normal mitoribosome assembly, the amounts of both the SSU and the LSU are decreased, which suggests that the accumulation of non-canonical precursor RNAs may cause stalling and subsequent degradation of the mitochondrial ribosome (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015). RNA immunoprecipitation coupled with pair-end RNA-seq analyses showed that FASTKD5 binds with high affinity to mRNAs encoding complex IV subunits, which is consistent with its role in processing of COX1 and COX3 mRNAs. FASTKD5 protein has been shown to interact with several MRG components (FASTKD2, DHX30, GRSF1, and NOA1) and ribosomal proteins (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015).

A member of Nod-like receptor (NLR) protein family NLRX1, which is a regulator of innate immune system (Nagai-Singer et al., 2019), has been recently found to localize within MRGs, where it specifically interacts with FASTKD5 and acts as its negative regulator (Singh et al., 2018). Knockdown of NLRX1 results in an increase in the steady-state level of COX1, COX3, ATP8/6, ND5, and CYTB mRNA, all of which are processed from non-canonical

RNAs mediated by FASTKD5. In contrast, cultured cells overexpressing NLRX1 showed a decrease in the level of these transcripts, along with an impaired RNA processing of ATP8/6-COX3 and ND5-CYTB. NLRX1 binds to mtRNAs through the leucine rich repeats (LLR) domain, and competes with FASTKD5 thereby limiting its association with COX3 mRNA.

3-3. Aims of the PhD thesis

The aim of my PhD thesis work was to uncover the roles of the FASTK protein family in mitochondrial post-transcriptional maturation, particularly non-canonical mtRNA processing.

Specific aims of the project were:

1. To understand the mode of action of the protein family. To this end, we assessed the putative RNA binding ability and RNase activity using a recombinant protein of FASTKD4, selected as a representative of the FASTK family members involved in non-canonical mtRNA processing.
2. To extend our understanding of the role of the protein family in mtRNA processing. For this purpose, we generated human cell lines that contain single or double knockouts of FASTKD3-5 and characterised them through transcriptome analysis.

IV. Results

The FASTK family proteins fine-tune mitochondrial RNA processing

The attached paper manuscript contains the results of our work on the role of the FASTK family proteins in mitochondrial RNA processing.

The key results of this study show that:

- FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 are key family members that regulate the processing of canonical and non-canonical junctions, accompanied with altered expression of specific sense and antisense mitochondrial transcripts.
- The knockout of FASTKD5 results in severe defects in mitochondrial translation, accompanied with defective assembly of the respiratory chain complex and reduced oxygen consumption.
- FASTKD4 specifically binds to mitochondrial tRNA^E, which is complementary to the processing site of non-canonical ND5-CYTB precursor transcript.
- The function of the FASTK family members in non-canonical mtRNA processing is conserved from *C. elegans* to human.

We are currently wrapping up the preparation of a manuscript that we intend to submit very soon. This work was achieved thanks to a great collaboration between our laboratory, the laboratory of Prof. Michal Minczuk (University of Cambridge, UK), the laboratory of Prof. Florian Steiner (University of Geneva), and the laboratories of Prof. Oliver Rackham and Prof. Aleksandra Filipovska (Harry Perkins Institute of Medical Research, Australia). As first author of this paper, I contributed in the experimental design of the project, I performed most of the experiments, analyzed and interpreted the data, and I wrote the manuscript under the supervision of Prof. Jean-Claude Martinou. The deletion worm strain was generated and cultured by the Prof. Florian Steiner laboratory. The HITS-CLIP analysis was carried out by Dr. Lindsey Van Haute in the laboratory of Prof. Michal Minczuk. The transcriptome analyses of the FASTKDs-KO cell lines were performed in the Prof. Oliver Rackham laboratory and in the Prof. Aleksandra Filipovska laboratory.

The FASTK family proteins fine-tune mitochondrial RNA processing

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ABSTRACT

Transcription of the human mitochondrial genome and correct processing of the two long polycistronic transcripts are crucial for oxidative phosphorylation. According to the tRNA punctuation model, processing of these large transcripts occurs mainly through the excision of the tRNAs that flank most rRNAs and mRNAs. However, some mRNAs are not defined by tRNAs, and it remains largely unknown how these non-canonical junctions between different coding sequences are resolved. The FASTK family proteins are emerging as key players in non-canonical RNA processing. Here, we have generated human cell lines carrying single and combined knockouts of several FASTK family members to investigate their roles in non-canonical RNA processing. The most striking phenotypes were obtained with loss of *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* and with their combined double knockout. Comprehensive northern blotting and transcriptomics analyses of these cell lines revealed a defect in processing at several canonical and non-canonical RNA junctions, accompanied by an increase in specific antisense transcripts. Loss of *FASTKD5* led to the most severe phenotype with marked defects in mitochondrial translation of key components of the electron transport chain complexes and in oxidative phosphorylation. We reveal that the FASTK protein family members are crucial regulators of non-canonical and non-coding mitochondrial RNA processing.

INTRODUCTION

The circular 16.5 kbp human mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) encodes 37 genes comprising two rRNAs, 22 tRNAs, and 13 ORFs, all of which are essential for oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) (1). Mitochondrial transcription initiates at two distinct divergent promoters, one on each strand, leading to two almost genome-length polycistronic transcripts: the primary transcript generated from the heavy strand promoter (HSP) includes 8 monocistronic mRNAs, two bicistronic mRNAs (*ND4L/4* and *ATP8/6*), 14 tRNAs, and two rRNAs, while the complementary primary transcript derived from the light strand promoter (LSP) encodes only one mRNA (*ND6*) and 8 tRNAs that span long stretches of non-coding sequences (2,3). As a consequence of the polycistronic organisation of the primary transcripts, the expression level of each individual gene is mainly controlled through post-transcriptional events, including stabilization, processing and modification (4-6). Most mRNAs and rRNAs within the polycistronic transcripts are flanked by tRNAs, and cleavage at the tRNA junctions by RNase P (MRPP1-3) and RNase Z (ELAC2) allows excision of the individual transcripts (7-13). This phenomenon is referred to as the ‘tRNA punctuation model’ (14). However, this model does not explain the processing of mRNAs that lack flanking tRNAs. In human mitochondria, junctions lacking a tRNA are found at the 3’ UTR of *ND6*, 5’ UTR of *COI*, between *ND5* and *CYTB*, and between *ATP8/6* and *CO3* mRNAs. The machinery responsible for these non-canonical RNA processing events is currently unknown. However, recent work has identified several candidates involved in the process, including the Fas-activated serine/threonine kinase (FASTK) family proteins (11,15-18).

The FASTK family includes six RNA binding proteins (RBPs), FASTK and FASTKD1-5 (19-22), all of which are localized in the mitochondrial matrix (Figure 1A) (15,17-19,23-26). The available evidence to date suggests that the FASTK family proteins are broadly involved in post-transcriptional regulation, ranging from RNA maturation to translation, although the precise mode of action of different members of the family remains to be elucidated (19).

FASTKD2 was described as part of a protein complex together with RPU3D3, RPU3D4, NGRN, WBSR16 and PTC1D1, involved in pseudouridylation of the *16S* rRNA (18,27-29). Mutations in the *FASTKD2* gene have been identified in patients with a MELAS (mitochondrial myopathy, encephalopathy, lactic acidosis, and stroke)-like syndrome (30-33). All other members of the FASTK family have been found to alter the expression levels of various mitochondrial mRNAs with some degree of specificity. While they regulate the abundance of specific mRNAs as described in Figure 1A (15,17,18,23,25,26), some are also involved in the non-canonical mitochondrial RNA (mtRNA) processing events: mitochondrial FASTK (mtFASTK) and FASTKD4, for example, are specifically involved in the processing of pre-*ND6* and *ND5-CYTB* transcripts, respectively (15,17). In contrast, FASTKD5 is required for the processing of all the non-canonical junctions with the exception of the 3’ UTR of *ND6* (18).

Despite their functional diversity, the FASTK family proteins share three putative RNA binding domains: FAST_1, FAST_2, and the RAP domain (Figure 1A) (21). We and others have reported that the RAP domain seems structurally related to PD-(D/E)-

XK nuclease superfamily (17,21,34), suggesting that this domain in the FASTK proteins may have endonuclease activity. Furthermore, RAP domain-containing proteins have been found to participate in nuclear and chloroplast RNA processing or splicing (35-38). For instance, in *C. reinhardtii*, the chloroplast RAP-domain-containing Raa3 protein participates in the trans-splicing of *psaA* mRNA that encodes a protein involved in photosynthesis (39). Importantly, during trans-splicing of the *psaA* mRNA, Raa3 forms a complex with the FAST_1 domain-containing protein, Raa1 (40), supporting the hypothesis that these domains in the FASTK family members could be directly involved in mtRNA processing (17).

Here, we have investigated the role of different FASTK family proteins in mtRNA processing. We generated human cell lines with single or combined disruption of *FASTKD3*, *FASTKD4*, and *FASTKD5*. Transcriptomic analyses of these knockout cells demonstrated defective processing of several canonical and non-canonical junctions, accompanied by specific increases in particular antisense transcripts. Our results support the hypothesis that the FASTK protein family members are critical regulators of mitochondrial RNA processing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cell culture cells

143B cells were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), 2 mM L-glutamine, 100 U/ml penicillin, and 100 mg/ml streptomycin in 5% CO₂ at 37°C. HAP1 cells were cultured in Iscove's Modified Dulbecco's Medium (IMDM) supplemented with 4 mM L-glutamine, 25 mM HEPES, 3.024 g/L NaHCO₃, 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U/ml penicillin, 100 mg/ml streptomycin, 1 mM sodium pyruvate, and 50 µg/ml uridine in 5% CO₂ at 37°C.

Generation of CRISPR/Cas9 knockout cells

To generate *FASTKDs* KO cells, we used Multiplex CRISPR/Cas9 Assembly Systems (Addgene Kit #1000000055) (41). A single gRNA was cloned into pX330A or pX330S, and three gRNAs (*FASTKD3*, *FASTKD4*, and *FASTKD5*) were cloned into pX330A-1x3 following to the inventor's protocol (41). Co-transfection of HAP1 cells with the appropriate gRNA constructs together with a GFP expression plasmid (pCI-GFP) was performed using Lipofectamine LTX (Invitrogen) according to the manufacturer's instructions. 24 h after transfection, GFP positive cells were selected by fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS) using the Beckman Coulter MoFlo Astrios, and single cells were plated into individual wells of a 96-well plate. Screening of clones was performed by Sanger sequencing and immunoblot analyses.

Northern blotting

Northern blot analyses were performed as previously described (42). Briefly, 10 µg of total cellular RNA prepared using the TRIzol reagent was separated on denaturing formaldehyde 1% agarose gel for mRNAs and rRNAs, or 10% polyacrylamide gel

containing 7 M urea for tRNAs. RNAs were transferred to Hybond-N+ hybridization membranes (Sigma) and UV-crosslinked to the membrane. Membranes were hybridized with T7-transcribed [α - 32 P] UTP radiolabeled riboprobes. Hybridization was carried out overnight at 65°C in 50% formamide, 7% SDS, 0.2 M NaCl, 80 mM sodium phosphate (pH 7.4), and 100 mg/ml salmon sperm DNA. Imaging and quantification were performed using the Typhoon imaging system (GE Healthcare). Primers used for the preparation of PCR templates for the transcription of the riboprobes are listed in Supplementary Table S1.

Measurement of respiratory chain activity

Measurement of oxygen consumption was performed using a Seahorse XFe24 Flux Analyzer (Seahorse Biosciences). 60,000 HAP1 cells were seeded into XF24 cell culture microplates coated with 0.01% poly-L-lysine solution (Sigma) and grown overnight. Cells were incubated at 37°C for 1 h in Dulbecco's PBS with MgCl₂ and CaCl₂ (Sigma D8662) supplemented with 5 mM sodium pyruvate. Basal oxygen consumption was measured before further treatment. At the times indicated, the following compounds were injected: oligomycin (final concentration 2 μ M), FCCP (final concentration 1 μ M), rotenone and antimycin A (final concentration 1 μ M each). Each measurement loop consisted of 30 s mixing, 1 min waiting, and 2 min measuring oxygen consumption. After the measurement, the number of cells was counted for normalisation.

Preparation of whole cell lysates and mitochondria-enriched fractions

Whole cell lysates (WCLs) were prepared by lysing cells in RIPA lysis buffer (50 mM Tris pH 8.0, 150 mM NaCl, 1% Triton X-100, 0.5% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS, and an in-house protease inhibitor cocktail) for 30 min on ice followed by centrifugation at 16,000 g for 10 min at 4°C in order to remove insoluble material. For preparation of the mitochondria-enriched fraction, cell fractionation was carried out on ice in MB buffer (10 mM HEPES pH 7.4, 210 mM mannitol, 70 mM sucrose, 1 mM EDTA, and the in-house protease inhibitor cocktail) following 30 passages through a 25G x 1" Microlance needle (BD, 300400). Nuclei and unbroken cells were discarded after centrifugation at 2,000 g. The mitochondria-enriched fraction was then recovered by centrifugation at 10,000 g. Protein content was determined using the BCA Protein Assay Kit (Pierce).

Immunoblotting and dot blotting

Equal amounts of protein were analyzed by SDS-PAGE. For Immunoblotting, proteins were transferred electrophoretically to nitrocellulose or PVDF membranes (GE Healthcare) and exposed to the primary antibodies specified below. The blots were further incubated with anti-goat, anti-rabbit or anti-mouse HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies (Dako) as appropriate, and visualized using ECL. For dot blots, the mitochondria-enriched fractions were lysed on ice for 30 min in 50 mM Tris pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 5 mM EDTA, 0.5% NP40, in-house protease inhibitor cocktail, and 1U/ μ L RNasin Plus RNase Inhibitor (Promega). Soluble material was collected following centrifugation for 30 min at 21,000 g. Equal amount of protein were spotted onto a nitrocellulose membrane (GE Healthcare). The membrane was exposed to

antibodies and signals were visualised by chemiluminescence. The following primary antibodies were used: anti-FASTK (Abcam, ab97544), anti-FASTKD2 (Proteintech, 17464-1-AP), anti-FASTKD3 (Sigma-Aldrich, sab2701102), anti-FASTKD4 (Proteintech, 16245-1-AP), anti-FASTKD5 (Sigma-Aldrich, sab2700438), anti-dsRNA (J2; Scicons, 10010200), anti-mtHSP70 (Invitrogen, MA3-028), anti-VDAC1 (Santa Cruz, sc-8829), anti- γ tubulin (Santa Cruz, sc-17787), anti-GRSF1 (Atlas antibodies, HPA036985), anti-LRPPRC (Santa Cruz, sc-166178), anti-PNPT1 (Santa Cruz, sc-365049), anti-DHX30 (Abcam, ab85687), anti-RPUSD4 (Abcam, ab122571), anti-SUV3 (Santa Cruz, sc-365750).

Immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence analyses were performed on cells fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde for 15 min. Cell permeabilization and blocking were performed together by incubating the fixed cells in PBS containing 0.3% Triton X-100 and 1% pre-immune goat serum for 45 min. The same buffer was used to incubate cells with the specified primary antibody. After 90 min incubation, the cells were washed in PBS and incubated with the appropriate secondary antibody conjugated with AlexaFluor 488 or Alexa 594 (Life Technologies). Mitochondrial networks and nascent transcripts were stained respectively using MitoTracker Red FM (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and 5 mM BrU (Sigma) as previously described (15). Imaging was performed using a Zeiss LSM700 confocal microscope equipped with a 63 \times oil objective. All images were imported into ImageJ and uniformly adjusted for brightness and contrast. The following primary antibodies were used: anti-SSBP1 (Proteintech, 12212-1-AP), anti-BrU (Roche, 11170376001), anti-dsRNA (J2; Scicons, 10010200).

RNA-seq

RNA sequencing was performed on total RNA from three control and three of each of the five *FASTKD* knockout cell lines, using the Illumina NovaSeq platform, according to the Illumina Tru-Seq protocol as described previously (12,13,28). Raw reads were trimmed of adapter sequences using cutadapt v1.18 (43) with standard parameters. Trimmed reads were mapped against the NuMTS masked human genome sequence (Hg38) using STAR v2.7.3a (44) and GENCODE v34 gene annotation with a customized mitochondrial annotation. Salmon v1.2.1 (45) (-l ISR -seqBias ----gcBias) in alignment based mode was used to quantify gene expression from the transcriptome alignments produced by STAR with a sequence file produced by gffread v0.11.7 (46). Strand-specific coverage of the primary alignments of properly paired, full-length RNA fragments (excluding those with a length > 500 nt) across the mitochondrial genome was calculated with samtools v1.10 (47) and bedtools genomecov v2.26.0 (48), normalised to library size. Differential expression analysis was performed with DESeq2 by counts summarised with tximport (49).

Poly(A) analyses

Sequenced reads were aligned against the human mitochondrial transcriptome bowtie2 v2.4.1 (--nofw --fr) (50) using the GENCODE v34 transcript set combined with custom mitochondrial rRNA and mRNA sequences with an additional 50 adenine residues added to the 3' ends to allow mapping of polyA tails as we have described previously

(51). Properly paired alignments normalised to library size were calculated with samtools v1.10 (47) and bedtools genomcov v2.26.0 (48). Gene-level normalised coverage profiles were extracted and lengths of poly(A) tails analysed (48).

BioID

Using the GAL4/UAS expression system, 4-hydroxytamoxifen (4-OHT) inducible 143B cells were generated for temporal control of protein expression of FASTKD4 or FASTKD5 tagged with BirA (R118G)-Flag at the C-terminus (52). Briefly, the *FASTKD4* or *FASTKD5* coding sequence tagged with C-terminal BirA (R118G)-Flag was cloned into pF 5xUAS plasmid (a kind gift from Prof. John Silke, The Walter and Eliza Hall Institute of Medical Research) (52). Plasmids were packaged into lentivirus and used to infect 143B cells containing a genomic GAL4-ER^{T2}-VP16 cassette. Cells were selected using 3 mg/ml puromycin. Protein expression was induced following addition of 100 nM 4-OHT for 24 h and biotinylation was then induced by addition of 50 µM biotin for 1 h. Mitochondria were extracted from cells to minimize contamination with free biotin, and subjected to pulldown experiments following to the previously published protocol (53) with the following minor modifications: mitochondria were lysed on ice for 30 min without sonication; and proteins were eluted in 1x Laemmli buffer by heating at 95°C for 10 min and further analysed by LC-MS/MS.

LC-MS/MS

Peptides were desalted on C18 StageTips (54) and dried by vacuum centrifugation prior to LC-MS/MS injections. Samples were resuspended in 2% acetonitrile, 0.1% FA and nano-flow separations were performed on a Dionex Ultimate 3000 RSLC nano UPLC system connected in-line with a Lumos Fusion Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer. A capillary precolumn (Acclaim Pepmap C18, 3 µm-100Å, 2 cm x 75µm ID) was used for sample trapping and cleaning. A 50cm long capillary column (75 µm ID; in-house packed using ReproSil-Pur C18-AQ 1.9 µm silica beads; Dr. Maisch) was then used for analytical separations at 250 nl/min over 150 min biphasic gradients. Acquisitions were performed through Top Speed Data-Dependent acquisition mode using a cycle time of 1 s. Initial MS scans were acquired with a resolution of 240'000 (at 200 m/z) and the most intense parent ions were selected and fragmented by High energy Collision Dissociation (HCD) with a Normalized Collision Energy (55) of 30% using an isolation window of 0.7 m/z. Fragmented ions were acquired using the Ion Trap using a maximum injection time of 20 s. Selected ions were then excluded for the following 20 s. Raw data were processed using SEQUEST, MS Amanda and Mascot in Proteome Discoverer v.2.4 against a concatenated database consisting of the Uniprot Human protein database (73112 entries) and a FASTKD sequence. Enzyme specificity was set to trypsin and a minimum of six amino acids was required for peptide identification. Up to two missed cleavages were allowed. A 1% FDR cut-off was applied at both peptide and protein identification levels. For the database search, carbamidomethylation was set as a fixed modification, whereas oxidation (M), acetylation (protein N-term), PyroGlu (N-term Q), and Phosphorylation (S,T,Y) were considered as variable modifications. Data was further processed and inspected in

Scaffold 4.10 (Proteome Software, Portland, USA) and spectra of interest were manually validated.

High-throughput sequencing of RNA isolated by cross-linking immunoprecipitation (HITS-CLIP)

Covalent bonds between endogenous FASTKD4 protein and RNA in HeLa cells was induced by irradiation with ultraviolet (UV) light (150 mJ/cm²). After cell collection, mitochondria were extracted by differential centrifugation. Pelleted mitochondria were lysed and the samples were incubated overnight with 5 µg anti-FASTKD4 (Proteintech, 16245-1-AP) or anti-HA (Roche, 11867423001) antibody as a control, in the presence of proteinase and ribonuclease inhibitors. Protein-antibody complexes were then bound to Pierce Protein G Magnetic Beads (Thermo) and while still on beads, RNA was partially digested with micrococcal nuclease (NEB) for 10 min at room temperature, in the presence of TURBO DNase. The reaction was stopped by adding 12 µl SUPERasin (ThermoFisher Scientific). After washing and elution of proteins from the beads, proteins were digested with 4 mg/ml Proteinase K. RNA was end repaired with Antarctic Phosphatase and T4 Polynucleotide Kinase and used for library generation, following the manufacturer's protocol (TruSeq Small RNA library preparation kit (Illumina)). Indexed PCR product was run on a 6% PAGE TBE gel to remove adapter only fragments and purified with Zymo DNA Clean and Concentrator columns. Quality and concentration was assessed with a D1000 Screentape for TapeStation (Agilent). Libraries were subjected to high-throughput sequencing using the Illumina HiSeq platform. For the qPCR analysis, the protein-RNA complexes were similarly immunoprecipitated from WT and *FASTKD4*-sKO HAP1 cells, then the RNA was recovered without digestion. Anti-Flag (Sigma, F7425) antibody was used as control.

Processing and mapping of HITS-CLIP data

Quality trimming and 3'-end adaptor clipping of sequenced reads were performed with Trim Galore!. Sequenced reads longer than 20 nt were aligned to the human reference genome (GRCh38) with Bowtie2 (50). The alignment was split by template strand (Samtools) (47) and converted to BED files (Bedtools) (48), and peak calling was performed with Piranha (56).

Pulse labeling of mitochondrial translation

Pulse labeling experiments to evaluate mitochondrial translation were carried out as described previously (42). Briefly, HAP1 cells were incubated for 20 min in methionine and cysteine-free DMEM supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated FBS, 110 mg/L sodium pyruvate, and 2 mM L-glutamine. 100 µg/ml emetine dihydrochloride was added for 5 min to inhibit cytosolic translation, followed by addition of 200 µCi/ml ³⁵S-labeled methionine and cysteine mix (Perkin Elmer). Labelling was performed for 1 h, then cells were lysed. Equal amounts of each protein sample were resolved on 12-20% SDS-PAGE gels. Gels were stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue to confirm equal loading, then dried and exposed. Imaging and quantification were performed with the Typhoon imaging system (GE Healthcare).

Quantitative PCR (qPCR)

Total cellular DNA purified by phenol-chloroform extraction was analysed using GoTaq qPCR Master Mix (Promega) following the manufacturer's instructions. For RT-qPCR, cDNA was prepared from DNase-treated RNA using the GoScript Reverse Transcriptase (Promega) with random primers (Promega, C118A) or RNA-specific primers for strand-specific qPCR. Primers used for RT and qPCR are listed in Supplementary Table S1.

***C. elegans* strain generation and culture**

C. elegans strains were maintained on OP50 plates using standard conditions at 20°C. N2 (Bristol strain) was used as a wild type, and the deletion of *B0564.7* was derived from this background, using CRISPR/Cas9 as described (57). The deletion allele was described in Figure 7A. The sgRNAs targeted the following genomic sequences: atatctagaatgtggagccgtgg, cccacgctttgcaggacgattcc, ttcagaacacagaaacgagcgg, and ccgctggcttcgatccagtagtc (PAM sequences are underlined). The deletion allele was identified by single worm PCR and sequenced with the primers oFSa0222 (agtcatggatgcagcgaag) and oFSa0223 (gtggtgtcagagtgtctcat). For RNA analysis, worms from eight 9-cm nematode growth medium plates containing mostly adult, embryo and young larval stages were washed three times with PBS. Worms were pelleted after each wash by centrifugation for 2 min at 1000 g, and the washed worm pellets were resuspended in 2 ml Trizol reagent and frozen at -80°C.

RESULTS

The FASTK family proteins specifically regulate the levels of sense and antisense transcripts and non-canonical mtRNA processing

To obtain greater insight into the role of FASTK family members in mitochondrial post-transcriptional regulation, we generated human cell lines in which either a single member of the family or a combination of members were knocked out. Knockout (KO) cells were generated in the HAP1 haploid cell line using CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing, and the efficiency of each KO was assessed by Sanger sequencing (Figure 1B and Supplementary Figure S1) and immunoblotting (Figure 1C). We generated single KO cell lines for *FASTKD3* (*FASTKD3*-sKO), *FASTKD4* (*FASTKD4*-sKO) and *FASTKD5* (*FASTKD5*-sKO), and two double KO cell lines (*FASTKD3&4*-dKO and *FASTKD4&5*-dKO), as described in Figure 1B and Supplementary Figure S1. It should be noted that subsequent analysis of the cell line in which *FASTKD3* and *FASTKD4* genes were deleted also carried a mutation in one of the *FASTKD5* alleles. However, this did not result in a significantly decreased expression of FASTKD5 protein (Figure 1C), and we therefore considered this cell line as a *FASTKD3&4*-dKO.

Importantly, we found that the HAP1 cell line expresses all members of the family except FASTKD2, which is absent both at the mRNA (Supplementary Figure S2B) and protein levels (Supplementary Figure S2A). The reason for this lack of FASTKD2 expression is currently unknown. It has previously been reported that loss of *FASTKD2* leads to a dramatic decrease in *I6S* rRNA and *ND6* mRNA accompanied by a translation defect (24). However, these transcripts were expressed in HAP1 cells

(Figure 2A), which suggests that the absence of *FASTKD2* is likely compensated by other members of the family with similar activities, such as mtFASTK (15). In support of this hypothesis, FASTK protein was detected in HAP1 cells by immunoblotting (Figure 1C), while it was more difficult to detect in other cell lines (15) suggesting that over-expression of FASTK in HAP1 cells may compensate for the loss of *FASTKD2*.

We then characterized these different KO cell lines by immunoblotting to investigate the expression of other FASTK family proteins and known mitochondrial RNA binding proteins (mtRBPs) involved in post-transcriptional regulation of mitochondrial gene expression (Figure 1C). *FASTKD5* protein expression was decreased in *FASTKD3*-sKO cells and *FASTKD3* protein level was downregulated in *FASTKD5*-sKO cells, suggesting that the stability of these proteins may depend on their interaction, as has been shown for several other proteins, such as prohibitin 1 and 2 (58,59) and the mitochondrial pyruvate carrier subunits 1 and 2 (60), which are only stable as heterodimers. Furthermore, the absence of *FASTKD5* resulted in a significant decrease in MRPP1, ELAC2, and RPUSD4 proteins and an increase in SUV3 protein compared to controls (Figure 1C). This also suggests that these proteins could be associating with a larger complex formed by *FASTKD5* and *FASTKD3*.

In the light of these results, we analyzed the different KO cell lines for mtRNA expression. We carried out northern blotting to measure the steady-state levels of mitochondrial transcripts, including non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs), in control and the *FASTKDs*-KO cell lines (Figure 2). Of note, all the analyzed antisense or ncRNAs appeared as distinct bands with precise lengths, indicating that they are processed in a specific manner before degradation. The fact that the length of some ncRNAs is similar to the length of their complementary mRNAs suggests that the RNA processing of the two strands may occur simultaneously. This may imply that certain events in mtRNA processing occur either on double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) or that “mirror” tRNAs and other complementary processing signals are recognized by the mitochondrial processing machinery as we have found before (61). Some ncRNAs are clearly processed into shorter ncRNAs, which we refer to as small non-coding RNAs (sncRNAs), as shown in Figure 2A.

In the *FASTKD3*-sKO cells, the level of *ND2*, *ATP8/6*, and *ND3* mRNAs derived from the heavy strand were significantly increased compared to controls (Figure 2A and B), consistent with our previous study (26). However, light strand-derived transcripts were not particularly affected in these cells (Figure 2C).

Loss of *FASTKD4* caused the reduction of *ND5*, *CYTB*, *ND3*, *ATP8/6*, and *CO3* mRNAs as well as impaired *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing (Figure 2A, B and D), consistent with previous findings (17,25). In contrast to these heavy strand-derived transcripts, several transcripts derived from the light strand, *ND6*, *ncATP8/6*, and *ncCO1*, were accumulated in the absence of *FASTKD4* (Figure 2C). All sncRNAs except *sncCYTB* were decreased in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells (Figure 2E), which is in contrast to the accumulation of their cognate longer ncRNAs. This finding suggests that *FASTKD4* could be involved in the downstream processing of sncRNAs, in particular, *sncATP8/6* and *sncCO1*.

Loss of *FASTKD5* resulted in a significant accumulation of *ND1*, *ND2* and *CO2* mRNAs and a decrease in *ND5*, *ATP8/6*, *CO3*, and *CO1* mRNAs (Figure 2A and B). Furthermore, processing of *ND5-CYTB*, *ATP8/6-CO3*, and pre-*CO1* non-canonical

precursor transcripts, was impaired, as previously reported (18), and this defect was particularly striking for *ATP8/6-CO3* and pre-*CO1* RNA processing, resulting in very low levels of mature mRNAs (Figure 2A and D). By comparison to *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, the processing defect of *ND5-CYTB* in the *FASTKD5*-sKO cells was subtle. This indicates that *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing is mainly regulated by *FASTKD4*, and that *FASTKD5* may cooperate with *FASTKD4* in this process. On the other hand, among the transcripts derived from the light strand, only *ncATP8/6* RNA dramatically accumulated when *FASTKD5* was absent (Figure 2A and C). It is important to note that the *sncATP8/6* RNA level was reduced in the *FASTKD5*-sKO cells, as in *FASTKD4*-sKO cells. Again, this finding strongly suggests that *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* may cooperate in the processing of *sncATP8/6* RNA. Finally, loss of *FASTKD5* led to a decrease in *ND3* mRNA, whereas the opposite effect was noted in *FASTKD4*-sKO cells (Figure 2A and B). This indicates that for this particular transcript *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* may have antagonistic functions. It is noteworthy that the heavy strand-derived transcripts, *ND2*, *CO2*, and *ND3* mRNAs, accumulated in either *FASTKD3*-sKO or *FASTKD5*-sKO cells (Figure 2B). However, the molecular phenotypes of the two cell lines showed some distinct changes. If, as proposed above, the stability of these two proteins is interdependent, one would have expected similar phenotypes for both KO cells. The fact that there is residual *FASTKD5* in *FASTKD3*-sKO and some *FASTKD3* in *FASTKD5*-sKO cells may explain the observed differences between the two cell lines.

Next, we investigated mtRNA expression in the double KO cells. *FASTKD3&4*-dKO resulted in a decrease in *ND5*, *CYTB*, *ND3*, *ATP8/6*, and *CO3* mRNAs with impaired *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing (Figure 2A, B and D), which is similar to the phenotype of *FASTKD4*-sKO cells. Notably, the *ND3* mRNA level, which is antagonistically regulated by *FASTKD3* and *FASTKD4*, was decreased in the *FASTKD3&4*-dKO cells, as it was in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, indicating that *FASTKD4* predominates over *FASTKD3* activity in regulating the stability of *ND3* mRNA. Interestingly, light strand-derived transcripts were not significantly affected in the *FASTKD3&4*-dKO cells, in contrast to the single *FASTKD4*-sKO cells (Figure 2C). However, *sncCO1* and *sncCO2* RNA levels were most decreased in the dKO cells, similar to in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells (Figure 2E), further supporting the essential role of *FASTKD4* in the generation of *sncCO1* RNA.

Double knockout of *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* caused a decrease in *CO1*, *ATP8/6*, *CO3*, *ND3*, *ND5*, and *CYTB* mRNAs with defective processing of *ND5-CYTB*, pre-*CO1*, and *ATP8/6-CO3* precursor RNAs (Figure 2A, B and D). This phenotype is therefore the result of the combined effects of the sKOs, which suggests that these two proteins may play overlapping or cooperative functions. This is particularly striking for the *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing, which was completely absent in the dKO cell line (Figure 2A). However, the *ND1* and *ND2* mRNA levels, which were increased in the *FASTKD5*-sKO cells, were comparable to the controls in the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells as in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells (Figure 2B). *ncND5* was the only light strand-derived transcript that accumulated significantly in the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells (Figure 2C). This might be a consequence of the loss of *FASTKD4*, since we observed a similar phenotype in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, although this change was not statistically significant in the sKO cell line. The *FASTK4&5*-dKO additionally resulted in a

dramatic decrease in *sncATP8/6*, *sncCO2*, and *sncCO1* RNAs (Figure 2E). In contrast to our findings in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, the *FASTKD3&4*-dKO and the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cell lines only showed mild accumulation of ncRNAs, suggesting that the ncRNA levels might be compensated by other mtRBPs when multiple FASTKD proteins are lost.

We observed that the overall mitochondrial transcription level, as assessed by the level of 7S RNA, which is the most promoter-proximal transcript formed by the light strand transcription initiation, appeared normal in all the KO cell lines (Supplementary Figure S2C). Moreover, mtDNA abundance was also not altered in any of the KO cell lines (Supplementary Figure S2D). In addition, we carried out SSBP1 and BrU staining to assess mitochondrial DNA replication and transcription respectively, and in both cases, we found similar levels of immunostaining in all the KO and control cells (Supplementary Figure S2E). These findings are therefore entirely consistent with the hypothesis that the FASTK family proteins are involved in post-transcriptional regulation, and they fully support our conclusions from the northern blotting analyses (Figure 2) that the regulation of mtRNA abundance is a consequence of post-transcriptional events.

It is notable that the accumulation of ncRNAs in the different *FASTKD*-KO cells was often inversely correlated with the change in their complementary mRNAs (Figure 2B and C). For instance, the antisense transcript of *ATP8/6* accumulated following the loss of either *FASTKD4* or *FASTKD5*, whereas its complementary *ATP8/6* mRNA was decreased in these sKO cells. This suggests the possibility that the FASTKD proteins may regulate the levels of specific mRNAs through the processing and degradation of their antisense ncRNAs. This process would probably involve recruitment of the mtRNA degradosome, and indeed, the pattern of ncRNAs in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells is reminiscent of the phenotype of cells lacking PNPase, the catalytic enzyme of the mtRNA degradosome (62). Furthermore, PNPase was recently found to prevent the accumulation of mitochondrial dsRNA (63), which may potentially inhibit mtRNA processing due to duplex formation. Mitochondrial dsRNA can be quantified using the anti-dsRNA J2 antibody (63,64). However, we found that in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, the J2 immunostaining, as well as the quantification of mitochondrial dsRNA by dot blotting, were unchanged compared to controls (Supplementary Figure S4E and F). This might reflect the shifting balance between different sense and antisense RNAs, discussed above, that nevertheless leaves the overall abundance of dsRNA unchanged. Alternatively, since the J2 antibody only recognizes dsRNA that is longer than 40 nucleotides, it is possible that loss of *FASTKD4* does indeed lead to the formation of dsRNA, but that these duplex molecules are too short to be recognized by the J2 antibody.

Mitochondrial transcriptomics demonstrates the specific roles of the FASTKD proteins in stability and processing of both sense and antisense transcripts

In a complementary study, we carried out RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) using the procedures we have reported previously (12,13,28) to analyse the effects of the different *FASTKD* gene KOs on the mitochondrial transcriptome. We first investigated the abundance of rRNAs and mRNAs in each of our *FASTKDs*-KO cell lines (Figure 3A). In most cases, the RNA-seq data confirmed the results of northern blotting,

although some exceptions were noted: the RNA-seq data showed that loss of *FASTKD4* additionally caused a reduction in *ND1*, *ND2*, *ND4L/4* and *ND6* mRNAs, and the *FASTKD3&4*-dKO similarly caused a reduction in *ND1*, *ND2*, and *ND6* mRNAs. In addition, the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO resulted in an increase in the *16S* rRNA, which was not observed in either sKO. These findings, together with the northern blot data (Figure 2), indicate that the loss of *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* have the most significant effects on the stability of specific mRNAs. Interestingly, the differential effects on mtRNA levels observed when multiple FASTKD proteins are lost compared to the sKO cells, for example *16S* rRNA, indicate potentially redundant or synergistic roles in RNA metabolism at certain sites.

We next analysed the entire mitochondrial transcriptome for processing defects as a result of different *FASTKD* gene knockouts. The RNA-seq library construction approach enabled us to exclude mature tRNAs and retain unprocessed transcripts containing tRNAs that span adjacent coding regions in the mitochondrial transcriptome. In the *FASTKD3*-sKO cells, there were no processing defects for any heavy strand-encoded RNAs indicating that this protein does not play a major role in mitochondrial RNA cleavage (Figure 3B). However, its loss resulted in specific increases in *tRNA^Q*- and *tRNA^E*-containing light strand precursor RNAs. In the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, processing defects were observed at the junction between *ND2* and *COI* and at the *ND5-CYTB* junction. However, the most apparent processing defect was at the region between *ND1* and *ND2* (Figure 3B), consistent with the reduction of these two mRNAs (Figure 3A). In the *FASTKD5*-sKO cells, the processing defect at the *ATP8/6-CO3* junction was most pronounced (Figure 3B), consistent with the northern blotting data (Figure 2B and 2D). However, we also observed that in the absence of *FASTKD5* the processing of the *ND5-CYTB* junction and the 5' UTR of *COI* were also impaired (Figure 3B).

An investigation into the effects of the *FASTKD3&4*-dKO on RNA processing revealed processing defects at the junction between *ND2* and *COI* and at the *ND5-CYTB* junction that were also found in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells (Figure 3B), indicating that the primary processing role of *FASTKD4* may be at these non-canonical junctions. Interestingly, the processing defect found at the junction between *ND1* and *ND2* in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, was absent in the *FASTKD3&4*-dKO, suggesting that the loss of *FASTKD3* might compensate for the absence of *FASTKD4* at this cleavage site. These findings thus provide evidence for partially overlapping roles of the FASTKD proteins in mtRNA processing. The greatest enrichment of unprocessed RNA precursors was observed in the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells; the most prominent of these defects was at the junction between *ND5* and *CYTB*, while significant changes were also seen in the 5' UTR of *COI*, the *ATP8/6-CO3* junction, the *ND1-ND2* junction, and the junction between *ND4L/4* and *ND5* (Figure 3B). These findings indicate that both *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* play a role in mtRNA processing at the *ND1-ND2*, *ND4L/4-ND5* and *ND5-CYTB* junctions consistent with the data from northern blotting (Figure 2). On the other hand, the dKO cell lines revealed that *FASTKD5* is exclusively responsible for the specific cleavage of the non-canonical junctions at the *ATP8/6-CO3* junction and at the 5' UTR of *COI*. Notably, the large increase in precursors that were uncleaved at the *ND1-ND2* junction in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells was reduced in the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells. The loss of processing defects at specific sites at the expense of increased

processing defects at others in the dKO cells suggests that the FASTKD3-5 proteins have some redundant roles that may involve masking, or recruitment, of other mitochondrial enzymes.

It is interesting to note that processing of the normally tRNA-punctuated junctions between the rRNAs was not affected by the loss of any of the *FASTKD3-5* proteins (Figure 3C), suggesting that these proteins likely participate in the downstream processing of the non-canonical precursor RNAs, and possibly act downstream of MRPP3 and ELAC2. Interestingly, their loss may nevertheless stimulate a general response to defective processing because more efficient processing is observed at certain canonical MRPP3/ELAC2 processing sites, such as tRNA^T, in their absence. Alternatively, FASTKD proteins might act as adapters that increase the processing efficiency of tRNA-less precursor transcripts.

These data also allowed us to investigate how the loss of each of the FASTKD3-5 proteins affected the non-coding regions of the mitochondrial transcriptome (Figure 3B). Loss of *FASTKD4* resulted in the accumulation of transcripts that are antisense to the *ND2*, *CO2*, *ATP8/6*, *CO3* and *ND6* mRNAs, whereas loss of *FASTKD5* caused the accumulation of the *CO1* antisense RNA (Figure 3B). The *FASTKD3&4*-dKO cells resulted in an accumulation of the same ncRNAs found in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, suggesting that FASTKD4 plays the predominant role in the removal of these antisense transcripts. In the case of the antisense *ATP8/6*, this is the only transcript that accumulates in the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells but not in the *FASTKD5*-sKO cells. This suggests that, in WT cells, FASTKD4 may stabilise *ATP8/6* and *CO3* mRNAs indirectly, by removal of the antisense *ATP8/6* RNA. Alternatively, FASTKD4 could be involved in the cleavage around the antisense *ATP8/6* and *CO3* junction, consistent with the northern blot results (Figure 2C and 2E). The increase of specific ncRNAs is in contrast to the reduction of their complementary mRNAs and may suggest that the FASTKD proteins have a role in the clearance of the antisense transcripts during RNA processing and that in the absence of FASTKD proteins, the antisense transcripts accumulate. Impaired clearance of antisense RNAs can cause processing defects and destabilisation of their complementary mRNAs since the accumulated antisense transcripts may allow duplex formation, as we have shown previously (61). This duplex potentially precludes the processing of mRNAs and reduces their translation.

FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 are required for polyadenylation of *ND5* mRNA

To investigate further the consequences of impaired processing of mtRNAs in the absence of the FASTKD proteins, we analysed the effects on polyadenylation (Figure 4 and Supplementary Figure S3). We show that the polyadenylation is not affected in mRNAs, such as *CO2*, whose levels were not changed by the loss of specific FASTKD proteins, either in single or double KOs (Figure 4A). The polyadenylation status was also not affected in specific mRNAs, such as *ATP8/6* (Figure 4B), even though its levels were changed in the KO cell lines compared to control cells, indicating that the loss of specific FASTKD proteins affects more the abundance rather than the polyadenylation status of these mRNAs. The most dramatic finding was the reduction in polyadenylation of the *ND5* mRNA in both the *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* KO cells (Figure 4C). This is most likely due to impaired processing of the *ND5-CYTB* precursor RNA (Figure 2B, D and 3A, B). Interestingly, the polyadenylation status of

the *CYTB* mRNA was not affected, which implies that the polyadenylation may occur on the *ND5-CYTB* precursor RNA prior to, or independently of, the RNA processing event (Supplementary Figure S3). This finding is consistent with the conclusion that these two FASTKD proteins are involved in the processing of the *ND5-CYTB* junction.

FASTKD4 specifically binds to *tRNA^E*, which is complementary to the *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing site

The transcriptome analysis of the *FASTKDs*-KO cell lines indicated that the FASTKD proteins are involved principally in the processing of non-canonical RNA junctions. Furthermore, these proteins, especially FASTKD4, may play a role in the elimination of ncRNAs. To understand how FASTKD4 could achieve its function, we performed a HITS-CLIP analysis to identify which RNA species are bound by FASTKD4 (Figure 5 and Supplementary Figure S4A, B). We used cultured HeLa cells and endogenous FASTKD4 as a bait and found that FASTKD4 preferentially associates with mitochondrial *tRNA^E*, which is encoded on the light strand, opposite the *ND5-CYTB* junction (Figure 5A and Supplementary Figure S4A, B). This preferential binding was confirmed by RT-qPCR (Supplementary Figure S4C). Using UV cross-linked WT and FASTKD4-sKO HAP1 cells, we immunoprecipitated FASTKD4 from isolated mitochondria, purified the RNA from the immunoprecipitate, and performed RT-qPCR for various transcripts. We confirmed that *tRNA^E* was enriched in the FASTKD4 immunoprecipitate (Supplementary Figure S4C). However, we noticed that in addition to *tRNA^E*, other transcripts were also enriched which did not score positive in the HITS-CLIP analysis. This suggests that FASTKD4 may associate more generally with unprocessed polycistronic transcripts in addition to *tRNA^E*, or possibly also interact with other transcripts. Curiously, we observed that the *tRNA^E* level was not significantly altered in *FASTKD4*-sKO cells even though the *ND5-CYTB* precursor on the heavy strand was shown to accumulate (Supplementary Figure S2G).

The identification of preferential binding of FASTKD4 to *tRNA^E* is an intriguing result, given that this RNA is within the complementary sequence on the opposite strand of the *ND5-CYTB* junction, the processing of which is known to be impaired in the loss of *FASTKD4*. Around 40% of the HITS-CLIP reads covering *tRNA^E* included the 3' end of its coding sequence, namely A73, and the majority of these A73-containing reads additionally included a 3' extension with the CCA tail (Figure 5B). This indicates that FASTKD4 can interact with the post-transcriptionally modified, CCA-containing mature *tRNA^E*. However, the time course of this binding is still uncertain as we do not know whether FASTKD4 binds *tRNA^E* before or after its processing and maturation. Nevertheless, the binding of FASTKD4 to this specific region provides a mechanistic explanation for the role of FASTKD4 in the processing of the *ND5-CYTB* junction, as discussed later.

The FASTK family proteins are essential for expression of the mitochondrially encoded respiratory complex proteins

To investigate further the phenotypes of the FASTKDs-KO cell lines, we measured *de novo* mitochondrial translation in the presence of ³⁵S-methionine and ³⁵S-cysteine (Figure 6A). Loss of *FASTKD3* caused a specific increase in ND3 protein synthesis compared to controls, which is consistent with an increase of *ND3* mRNA (Figure 2B and 3A). *FASTKD4*-sKO cells showed a decrease in expression of the *ND3* and *COX3* proteins also in line with their mRNA levels. However, levels of newly synthesized ND5 and *COX1* proteins were increased following the loss of *FASTKD4* despite the low level of mature *ND5* mRNA (Figure 2B, D and 3B), and this was also found in the *FASTKD3&4*-dKO cells (Figure 6A). The reason for the poor correlation between mRNA level and protein translation in this case is currently unclear. One possibility is that the *ND5* coding sequence in the *ND5-CYTB* precursor transcript, which accumulates in *FASTKD4*-sKO cells, is translatable. On the other hand, we do not understand why *COX1* translation is increased in the absence of *FASTKD4*, given that the *COI* mRNA level is not affected. This suggests that in addition to playing some role in RNA processing, *FASTKD4* may also participate in the control of translation of specific mRNAs as it associates with factors that modulate RNA metabolism and translation such as LRPPRC and IARS2 (Supplementary Figure S5). Finally, the absence of *FASTKD4* was found to normalize the level of *ND3* mRNA, which was upregulated in *FASTKD3*-sKO cells. This is consistent with our earlier conclusion that at least in this specific case, *FASTKD4* can compensate for the loss of *FASTKD3*.

Loss of *FASTKD5* caused a reduction in protein synthesis of *COX1*, *COX3* and *ATP6* (Figure 6A) consistent with their decreased mRNA levels, as well as reduced *COX2* translation, which was not correlated with a change in mRNA abundance (Figure 2B and 3A). Remarkably, *COX1* protein synthesis was strongly perturbed in the cells lacking *FASTKD5*, consistent with the severe defect in pre-*COI* RNA processing (Figure 2B, D and 3B). *ND5* protein synthesis was not affected in the *FASTKD5*-sKO, which probably reflects the minor involvement of *FASTKD5* in the processing of the *ND5-CYTB* junction (Figure 2E, G and 3B). It is striking that while the *ND5* mRNA level is almost undetectable in the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells (Figure 2), the level of *ND5* protein was normal (Figure 6A). These results support the hypothesis that, at least for *ND5*, the protein may be translated from the *ND5-CYTB* precursor RNA.

Consistent with these results, using an antibody cocktail that recognizes subunits from all mitochondrial respiratory complexes (MRC) to assess their abundance, we found that Complex IV was most affected by the loss of *FASTKD5* (Figure 6B, C). This result was validated by oxygen consumption measurements of the different KO cells (Figure 6D). We found that both *FASTKD4*-sKO and *FASTKD3&4*-dKO cells had only minor defects in OXPHOS. In contrast, oxygen consumption was dramatically reduced in both the *FASTKD5*-sKO and the *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells. These findings indicate that *FASTKD5* is indispensable for OXPHOS because it is essential for *COX1* protein synthesis and the assembly of Complex IV.

DISCUSSION

Post-transcriptional control of human mitochondrial gene expression is regulated in time and space, with many events occurring within the mitochondrial RNA granules (19,65). Dysfunction of these post-transcriptional events can lead to numerous, often severe, mitochondrial pathologies (33,66). Here, we have characterised the FASTK family proteins that are emerging as key post-transcriptional regulators of mitochondrial gene expression and we have focused on their roles in mtRNA processing. Their function in non-canonical mtRNA processing is evolutionarily conserved. *C. elegans* is an ancestral model organism that has only one FASTK orthologue, FASK-1 (FASTK-related protein 1), to which mammalian FASTKD4 is the most closely related (17). *FAST-1* deletion strain resulted in a specific accumulation of *ND5*-containing precursor transcripts (*16S-ND3-ND5* and *ND3-ND5*), which lack tRNA junctions, and a decrease in mature *ND5* mRNA (Supplementary Figure S6).

Mitochondrial transcriptome analyses of HAP1 cell lines carrying single or double knockouts of *FASTKD3-5*, revealed that FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 control the maturation and abundance of a broad range of mitochondrial mRNAs, and furthermore, they also affect the fate of many of the non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs) in the mitochondrial transcriptome. The loss of *FASTKD4* resulted in impaired *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing, and the absence of *FASTKD5* caused defects in *ND5-CYTB*, pre-*CO1*, and *ATP8/6-CO3* RNA processing, as previously reported (17,18). None of these effects were seen in cells depleted of *FASTKD3*. The defective processing of the *ND5-CYTB* junction was observed in the single KOs of *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5*, and the effect was even more pronounced in the double mutant *FASTKD4&5*-dKO, suggesting that FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 may cooperate to ensure optimal processing of this junction. However, the interactions between members of the FASTK family can be more complex since we revealed antagonistic activities in the processing, or stabilization of some mRNAs. For instance, the *ND3* mRNA level was significantly increased in the *FASTKD3*-sKO and *FASTKD5*-sKO cells but decreased in the *FASTKD4*-sKO cells compared to controls. Interestingly, in both dKO cell lines (*FASTKD3&4*-dKO and *FASTKD4&5*-dKO), the *ND3* mRNA level was reduced, indicating that FASTKD4 may play the predominant role in regulating expression of the *ND3* mRNA. It is interesting to note that the processing of *tRNA^G* and *tRNA^R*, which are tRNAs that flank *ND3*, was boosted in the *FASTKD3*-sKO and the *FASTKD5*-sKO, whereas this was not observed in the *FASTKD4*-sKO and the dKO cells, suggesting that FASTKD4 increases the stability of *ND3* mRNA after it is cleaved from its precursor transcript.

The complex interactions between FASTKD members is also illustrated by the interdependence of FASTKD3 and FASTKD5 in terms of their mutual stability. Loss of one member of the family leads to a lower expression of the other, suggesting a close physical interaction between them as is found for other proteins that show a similar interdependence (58-60). However, we did not detect an interaction between FASTKD3 and FASTKD5 in the BioID analysis performed for both FASTKD4 and FASTKD5, whereas this analysis did reveal a physical interaction between FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 (Supplementary Figure S5). These data taken together, provide evidence that FASTK family members may interact to form large protein complexes,

capable of exerting a variety of regulatory functions depending on the specific combination of the FASTKD, and possibly other protein components. Among the proteins affected by loss of *FASTKD* family members, which may also participate in the formation of larger complexes, are the post-transcriptional tRNA processing and modifying enzymes, MRPP1 (TRMT10C), ELAC2 and RPUUSD4. In addition, the BioID experiments using FASTKD4 and FASTKD5, identified several other interacting proteins such as LRPPRC and GRSF1 which could constitute further components of the protein machinery that is functionally linked to RNA processing (Supplementary Figure S5) (13). This is supported by a recent study of mitochondrial protein interaction networks based on the BioID approach, which revealed that the FASTK family members and a subset of the mtRBPs, including those identified in this study, co-localise within the mitochondrial matrix (67).

De novo translation analyses revealed that the loss of *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* results in significant defects in mitochondrial translation and as a consequence, since all proteins encoded in the mitochondrial genome provide essential components of the electron transport chain, in compromised mitochondrial respiration. Importantly, the extent of the defect in oxygen consumption was proportional to the effect on non-canonical RNA processing. While the loss of *FASTKD3* did not result in a reduction in mitochondrial respiration, the loss of *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* either separately or together resulted in respiratory defects, which were particularly pronounced in cells lacking *FASTKD5*.

These experiments on translation levels also revealed that the level of mRNA does not always reflect their translation efficiency. For instance, ND5 protein synthesis was normal or even higher in the *FASTKD4*-sKO and *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells despite the very low expression level of its mRNA. This suggests either highly efficient translation of the residual *ND5* mRNA or the possibility that *ND5* can be translated from the increased levels of the *ND5-CYTB* precursor transcripts. In addition, ND4 protein synthesis was elevated in cells lacking *FASTKD5* regardless of its mRNA level. These findings highlight the concept that FASTK family proteins can distinctly modulate mitochondrial translation.

The mitochondrial transcriptome analyses revealed that the FASTKD proteins are also involved in the cleavage of certain tRNA junctions such as the cluster of tRNAs between *ND1* and *ND2* and *tRNA^E* between *ncCYTB* and *ND6*. This implies that the FASTKD proteins may recruit the tRNA processing enzymes at some specific sites. However, the processing of some other tRNA junctions, for example *tRNA^D* between *CO1* and *CO2*, were facilitated following the loss of the FASTKD proteins. These data show that the FASTKD proteins specifically facilitate or inhibit tRNA processing, which largely affects the metabolism of mRNAs.

The transcriptome analyses also indicated that FASTKD4 seems to be involved in the cleavage of the tRNA-less junction between antisense *ATP8/6* and *CO3*. In this case a mechanism other than recruitment of known RNA processing enzymes must be responsible, as knockout of MRPP3 and ELAC2 does not affect this site (11-13). For this event FASTKD4 could exhibit its own intrinsic nuclease activity or recruit an as yet unidentified nuclease. Furthermore, northern blotting revealed that the processing

of some specific sncRNAs, *sncATP8/6* and *sncCO1*, appears to be perturbed in cells lacking *FASTKD4*, suggesting that the FASTKD proteins may also be involved in ncRNA processing. Furthermore, the FASTKD proteins can have opposing functions in RNA processing. This is evident with the proximal processing site of the 5' UTR of *CO1* that is impaired in the absence of *FASTKD5*, while this junction is efficiently processed in the loss of *FASTKD4*. In fact, in the absence of *FASTKD4*, the non-coding mirror *tRNA^A*, *tRNA^N*, *tRNA^C* and *tRNA^Y* are specifically increased indicating that *FASTKD4* facilitates the cleavage of the junction between mirror *tRNA^Y* and the *CO1* mRNA. These findings are consistent with the significant reduction in COX1 protein synthesis in the loss of *FASTKD5*, and the increase of COX1 translation in the absence of *FASTKD4*, indicating that if there is a structured stem loop at the 5' end of *CO1* that is not processed by *FASTKD5*, it can obstruct mitoribosome recruitment and thereby inhibit its translation (Figure 7).

We have shown that several ncRNAs are differentially-regulated in the *FASTKDs*-KO cell lines, and curiously, our analyses reveal that like the coding transcripts, ncRNAs are precisely processed and in most cases their lengths are similar to the length of the complementary mRNA. This suggests that both strands may be cleaved simultaneously in the same reaction. To explain this observation we propose two contrasting hypotheses. First, that the initial substrate for processing could be a double-stranded RNA comprising the two long complementary polycistronic RNAs, and that only after initial cleavage of the dsRNA, would smaller fragments be separated by RNA helicases and subject to further maturation or degradation steps. Second, this could occur because antisense RNA sequences often fold into similar structures as their sense counterparts, such that “mirror” tRNAs and other complementary processing signals could be recognized by mitochondrial processing enzymes as we have observed before for the RNase P complex (61).

A striking result from the HITS-CLIP analysis revealed that *FASTKD4* preferentially binds to *tRNA^E*, which is complementary to the *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing site. Binding of *FASTKD4* could prevent *tRNA^E* from forming a duplex with its complementary region, which would have an inhibitory effect on *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing. If binding to RNA occurs prior to the processing of *tRNA^E*, *FASTKD4* may bind to the *tRNA^E* precursor transcripts containing *ND6* and its long 3' UTR and may regulate the processing of other light strand transcripts encoded in the 3' UTR of *ND6* including *ncND5*, *ncND4L/4*, *ncND3*, *ncCO3*, *ncATP8/6*, and *ncCO2*. Alternatively, the binding of *FASTKD4* to *tRNA^E* may reflect the possibility that this protein could, in addition to RNA processing, be involved in translation, given that a mitoribosomal protein *MRPS27* also preferentially binds *tRNA^E* as we have previously shown (68).

In conclusion, we have shown that *FASTKD3*, *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* regulate expression of a broad range of mitochondrial transcripts, including ncRNAs, through controlling the processing of specific canonical and non-canonical junctions. We propose a new model whereby the orchestrated roles of *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* are crucial for the processing of the non-canonical pre-*CO1* mRNA in mitochondria that can regulate its translational efficiency.

DATA AVAILABILITY

RNA-seq datasets have been deposited in the NCBI GEO with accession numbers GSE156556 (HITS-CLIP) and GSE156260 (mitochondrial transcriptomics). The mass spectrometry proteomics data have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE partner repository with the dataset identifier PXD020993 and 10.6019/PXD020993.

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supplementary Data are available at NAR Online.

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Authors contributions: A.O. conceived, designed and performed the experiments, undertook the data analysis and wrote the manuscript; L.V.H. carried out the HITS-CLIP experiments and generated Figure 5 and Supplementary Figure S4A-B. F.S. generated and provided *FASK-1* deletion *c. elegans* strain. D.R. and M.S. performed experiments and transcriptomic analyses, O.R. and A.F. analysed data, supervised their work, provided advice and wrote parts of the manuscript. J.C.M. conceived and supervised the project and wrote the manuscript. All authors commented and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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TABLE AND FIGURES LEGENDS

Figure 1. Generation of HAP1 cell lines carrying single or combined knockouts of *FASTK* family members. (A) Overview of the *FASTK* protein family and their proposed roles in mitochondrial post-transcriptional regulation. All proteins share a conserved C-terminal domain architecture of *FAST_1*, *FAST_2*, and the *RAP* domains. An internal translation start site exposes a mitochondrial targeting sequence (MTS) leading to expression of the mitochondrial *FASTK* (mt*FASTK*). (B) Description of the *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cell lines generated. (C) Expression levels of *FASTK* family proteins and mtRBPs involved in the post-transcriptional regulation in WT (control) and *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cells were measured by immunoblotting. γ -tubulin was used as a loading control for whole cell lysates. mtHSP70 and VDAC1 were used as mitochondrial loading controls. A representative result from two independent experiments is shown.

Figure 2. Loss of *FASTKD* proteins alters the abundance of coding and non-coding RNAs and perturbs non-canonical RNA processing. (A) The steady-state levels of rRNAs, mRNAs and ncRNAs in WT (control) and *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cells were measured by northern blotting. *5S* and *7SL* were used as loading controls. A representative result from three independent experiments is shown. (B-E) Relative abundance of mature rRNAs, mRNAs, ncRNAs derived from either the heavy strand (B) or the light strand (C), non-canonical precursor RNAs (D), and sncRNAs (E). The data from each of the *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cell lines were quantified by comparison to WT HAP1 cells (control) (n = 3). RNA loading was normalized to the content of *7SL* RNA. The dotted line shows the relative abundance of control (=1). Results are mean \pm SEM, *P<0.05, **P 0.001 to 0.01, ***P <0.001 (two-tailed unpaired t-test).

Figure 3. Mitochondrial transcriptome analysis of the *FASTKDs*-KO cells by RNA-seq. (A) Relative abundance of read counts normalised to total reads for mitochondrial mRNAs were analysed. Results are mean \pm SD *P<0.05, **P<0.01 (Wald test). (B-C) A complete map of mtRNA abundance and mean (log₂ fold change [KOmean/Ctrlmean]) determined by RNA-seq coverage from control, *FASTKD3*-sKO, *FASTKD4*-sKO, *FASTKD5*-sKO, *FASTKD3&4*-dKO, and *FASTKD4&5*-dKO cells, on the heavy and light strands (n = 3). Increases in coding regions (B) and rRNA regions (C) are shown in red, and decreases in coding regions (B) and rRNA regions (C) are shown in blue. The range of the log₂ fold changes are from -3 to 2.8.

Figure 4. *FASTKD4* and *FASTKD5* are required for efficient processing of the *ND5-CYTB* junction. Mapping of RNA-seq reads to polyadenylated reference sequences reveals no changes in *CO2* (A) or *ATP8/6* (B) mRNAs but a reduction in polyadenylation of *ND5* mRNA was identified in the *FASTKD4* and the *FASTKD5* KO cell lines (C), compared to control cells. The canonical 3' region of each mRNA is shown in dark grey and the section of polyadenosine is shown in light grey.

Figure 5. *FASTKD4* specifically binds to *tRNA^E* complementary to the *ND5-CYTB* RNA processing site. (A-B) Strand specific HITS-CLIP read counts corresponding to the 14600-14800 region of the mtDNA for anti-*FASTKD4* antibody (A). The pie-chart in (B) shows the fraction of *tRNA^E* reads that includes the last encoded position (A73) of *tRNA^E* (grey) and reads that are truncated on the 3' end of *tRNA^E* (dark blue). The inset shows all reads that include A73 of *tRNA^E* with the fraction of unprocessed RNAs containing an extended sequence (orange), the fraction of reads that end exactly at A73 (yellow), and the fraction of those that have a CCA addition (light blue).

Figure 6. Effect of *FASTK* family protein depletion on mitochondrial translation, respiratory chain assembly and oxygen consumption. (A) Levels of de novo mitochondrial protein synthesis were measured in WT (control) and *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cells by pulse incorporation of ³⁵S-labeled methionine and cysteine. Equal amounts of whole cell lysates were separated by SDS-PAGE and visualized by autoradiography. (B) Protein expression levels of specific subunits of each of the MRC complexes in WT (control) and *FASTKDs*-KO cells were evaluated by immunoblotting. Total OXPHOS Rodent WB Antibody Cocktail antibody was used to assess the efficiency of the MRC complex assembly. VDAC1 was included as a mitochondrial loading control. (C) Relative abundance of each assembled MRC complex was determined by quantification of the results of immunoblotting (n = 3). Loading amounts were normalized relative to VDAC1. The dotted line shows the relative abundance of control (= 1). Results are mean \pm SEM, *P<0.05, **P 0.001 to 0.01, ***P <0.001 (two-tailed unpaired t-test). (D) Oxygen consumption rate (OCR) in WT (control) and *FASTKDs*-KO cells was measured using the Seahorse analyzer. OCR was normalized

to the number of cells in each well. A representative result from three independent biological experiments is shown.

Figure 7. A model showing the proposed roles of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 in the RNA processing of the 5' UTR of *COI*. In the absence of FASTKD5, the proximal processing site of the 5' UTR of *COI* cannot be resolved and obstructs mitoribosome binding thereby precluding its translation. On the other hand, FASTKD4 facilitates the cleavage at the junction between mirror *tRNA*^Y and *COI* mRNA and the degradation of a cluster of mirror tRNAs (mirror *tRNA*^A, *tRNA*^N, *tRNA*^C and *tRNA*^Y) that could play a regulatory role in COX1 translation.

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SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

The FASTK family proteins fine-tune mitochondrial RNA processing

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Supplementary Figure S1. Sequence analysis of the *FASTKDs*-KO genes in the HAP1 cell lines.

Supplementary Figure S2. Characterization of the *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cell lines. **(A)** Protein expression levels in 143B (control) and WT HAP1 cells were assessed by immunoblotting. Whole cell lysates (WCL) and mitochondria extracted from the cells were analysed. mtHSP70 was used as a loading control. **(B)** mRNA expression levels in 143B (control) and WT HAP1 cells were analysed by RT-PCR. **(C)** Relative abundance of 7S RNA in WT (control) and *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cells were quantified by RT-qPCR (n = 4). The amounts of 7S RNA were normalised by *GAPDH*. **(D)** The relative abundance of mtDNA in the *FASTKDs*-KO cells compared to controls was measured by qPCR and normalised to total nuclear DNA (n = 3). **(E)** WT and *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cells were labeled with BrU and MitoTracker Red, and immunolabeled with anti-SSBP1, anti-BrU and J2 anti-dsRNA. Immunofluorescence was analysed by confocal microscopy. Scale bars indicate 20 μ m. **(F)** The amount of mitochondrial dsRNA in the *FASTKDs*-KO cells and controls was measured by dot blotting. VDAC1 protein was used as a loading control. **(G)** Steady-state levels of mitochondrial tRNAs in WT (control) and *FASTKDs*-KO HAP1 cells were measured by northern blotting. 5S was analyzed as a loading control.

Supplementary Figure S3. Polyadenylation status of mitochondrial mRNAs. Mapping of RNA-seq reads to polyadenylated reference sequences reveals effects on polyadenylation in all mRNAs of the *FASTKDs*-KO cell lines compared to controls. The canonical 3' region of each mRNA is shown in dark grey and the section of polyadenosine is shown in light grey.

Supplementary Figure S4. FASTKD4 specifically binds to *tRNA^E*. **(A-B)** Strand specific HITS-CLIP read counts corresponding to the 13401-16569 region of the mtDNA for control (anti-HA antibody) (A) and anti-FASTKD4 antibody (B). **(C)** The *tRNA^E* enriched through FASTKD4 immunoprecipitation from WT and *FASTKD4*-sKO HAP1 cells was quantified by strand-specific RT-qPCR. Anti-Flag antibody was used as a control. A representative result from two independent biological experiments is shown.

Supplementary Figure S5. BioID interactome analyses of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5. Log₂FC (FASTKD4-BirA/control) (A) or Log₂FC (FASTKD5-BirA/control) (B) was plotted against a sum of normalized total spectra. Only significantly enriched proteins are shown (Log₂FC \geq 1). Cells that do not express the bait protein were used as control. Mitochondrial proteins are shown in blue. Red dot represents BirA-tagged bait proteins. **(C-D)** Gene ontology analysis (GO - molecular function) of mitochondrial proteins identified by the BioID of FASTKD4 (C) and FASTKD5 (D). **(E)** Number of mitochondrial proteins found in either or both BioID data sets from FASTKD4 or FASTKD5.

Supplementary Figure S6. Function of the FASTK family proteins in the processing of tRNA-less junctions is evolutionarily conserved. **(A)** A schematic representation of *FASK-1* (*B0564.7*) deletion strain generated using CRISPR/Cas9 technology. Two sgRNAs each were used to cleave the genomic DNA near the start codon and in the last exon of the *FASK-1* locus. The deletion allele (*uge100*) contains a truncated start codon, a 26 bp insertion and a 3642 bp deletion that removes all of the *FASK-1* coding sequence except 153 bp of the last exon. **(B)** The steady-state levels of mitochondrial transcripts in WT (control) and *FASK-1* deletion strains were measured by northern blotting. *Act-1* was used as a loading control.

Supplementary Table S1. List of oligonucleotides used in this study. Sequences used for Gibson assembly are shown in bold. T7 promoter sequence is underlined.

Obtained KO		FASTKD3 gRNA		PAM
WT		5'-AATCTGATGGTATGGCATTAAATCACCTTGAGGAAGAAC-3'		
FASTKD3-sKO	Allele 1	5'-AATCTGATGGTATGGCATTAAATCAC - TTGAGGAAGAAC-3' - 1 bp		
	Allele 2	5'-AATCTGATGGTATGGCA -----AGAAC-3' - 16 bp		
FASTKD3&4-dKO	Allele 1	5'-AATCTGATGGTATGGCATTAAATCATTGAGGTGCCTCATTGAGGAAGAAC-3' CC > TTGAGGTGCCTCA		
	Allele 2	5'-AATCTGATGGTATGGCATTAAATCATTGAGGTGCCTCATTGAGGAAGAAC-3' CC > TTGAGGTGCCTCA		
FASTKD4&5-dKO	Allele 1	5'-AATCTGATGGTATGGCATTAAATCACCTTGAGGAAGAAC-3' WT		
	Allele 2	5'-AATCTGATGGTATGGCATTAAATCACCTTGAGGAAGAAC-3' WT		

		PAM	FASTKD4 gRNA		
WT		5'-ATGCACTGTCCCTCCTGAGAGAAGCTGCTCGTCAGGCC-3'			
FASTKD4-sKO	Allele 1	5'-ATGCACGTGCCTCCT - AGAGAAGCTGCTCGTCAGGCC-3' - 1 bp			
	Allele 2	5'-ATGCACGTGCCTCCT - AGAGAAGCTGCTCGTCAGGCC-3' - 1 bp			
FASTKD3&4-dKO	Allele 1	5'-ATGCACGTGCCTCCT - AGAGAAGCTGCTCGTCAGGCC-3' - 1 bp			
	Allele 2	5'-ATGCACGTGCCTCCT - AGAGAAGCTGCTCGTCAGGCC-3' - 1 bp			
FASTKD4&5-dKO	Allele 1	5'-ATGCACGTGCCTCCT - AGAGAAGCTGCTCGTCAGGCC-3' - 1 bp			
	Allele 2	5'-ATGCACGTGCCTCCT - AGAGAAGCTGCTCGTCAGGCC-3' - 1 bp			

		PAM	FASTKD5 gRNA		
WT		5'-CCTTCTGCCTTTGGTGCAGTCCGAAGTGTGCATACTGG-3'			
FASTKD5-sKO	Allele 1	5'-CCTTCTGCCTTTG - TGCAGTCCGAAGTGTGCATACTGG-3' - 1 bp			
	Allele 2	5'-CCTTCTGCCTTTGGGTGCAGTCCGAAGTGTGCATACTGG-3' + 1 bp			
FASTKD3&4-dKO	Allele 1	5'-CCTTCTGCCTTTGTGTGCAGTCCGAAGTGTGCATACTGG-3' + 1 bp			
	Allele 2	5'-CCTTCTGCCTTTGGTGCAGTCCGAAGTGTGCATACTGG-3' WT			
FASTKD4&5-dKO	Allele 1	5'-CCTTCTGCCTT --- GTGCAGTCCGAAGTGTGCATACTGG-3' - 2 bp			
	Allele 2	5'-CCTTCTGCCTT --- GTGCAGTCCGAAGTGTGCATACTGG-3' - 2 bp			

Figure S1, Ohkubo et al.

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Figure S3, Ohkubo et al.

Figure S4, Ohkubo et al.

Figure S5, Ohkubo et al.

Figure S6, Ohkubo et al.

Purpose	Name of oligo	Species	Sequence (5' to 3')	
Cloning	pF5UAS-FASTKD4-BirA-Flag_Fw1	Human	GGTACCTTCGAAGCTAGCATGGCAGCTCACCTGGTAAAG	
	pF5UAS-FASTKD4-BirA-Flag_Rv1		GCACGGTGTTATCCTTGGTACC CTTGCCAGCTCCTCAGC	
	pF5UAS-FASTKD5-BirA-Flag_Fw1		GGTACCTTCGAAGCTAGCATGGCAGCTACTCTCAAGTC	
	pF5UAS-FASTKD5-BirA-Flag_Rv1		GCACGGTGTTATCCTTGGTACCAGAGCAGAGGTGAATACTTTC	
	pF5UAS-FASTKD4/5-BirA-Flag_Fw2		AAGGATAACACCGTGCCACTG	
	pF5UAS-FASTKD4/5-BirA-Flag_Rv2		TCTCTAGAGTTAACGCTAGCTCACTTGTCTCATCGTCTTTGTAGT CACCACCTCTAGATTTTTCTGCACTACGCAGG	
RT-PCR	FASTK_Fw	Human	GGCCCGGGAGTCATGGTCT	
	FASTK_Rv		CTCCCCAGGGCTCTTCGCCT	
	FASTKD1_Fw		CTTGCCTAGCAGATCAGCA	
	FASTKD1_Rv		GACAAGGAACTTAAGTCCTGTG	
	FASTKD2_Fw		AGGATGTGCACTTGCCACACA	
	FASTKD2_Rv		TCTGGGGTGGCTTGAACCCA	
	FASTKD3_Fw		GCCCTTTCTATAAGGGTCCA	
	FASTKD3_Rv		AAGCTGAGAATCCACAGGG	
	FASTKD4_Fw		TCAGCCACCTCACCCATTTTC	
	FASTKD4_Rv		TGTACTTGAGCTTCCGCATG	
	FASTKD5_Fw		GCCATCAGGTATGGGAGATG	
	FASTKD5_Rv		TTTGCGGCCTAAGTACCTCC	
	GAPDH_Fw		GTCTCCTCTGACTCAACAGCG	
	GAPDH_Rv		ACCACCTGTTGCTGTAGCC	
	16S_Fw		GACCTGCCCGTGAAGAGGCG	
16S_Rv	ACGGGGGAAGCGCTTTGTG			
(RT-)qPCR	rRNAE_Fw	Human	GTTCTTGATGTTGAAATACAACGATGG	
	rRNAE_Rv		TATTCTCGCACGGACTACAACC	
	7S_Fw		CGTGATGTCTTATTTAAGGGGAACG	
	7S_Rv		GACCACCATCCTCCGTGAAATC	
	16S_Fw		GACCTGCCCGTGAAGAGGCG	
	16S_Rv		ACGGGGGAAGCGCTTTGTG	
	ND6_Fw		TGATTGTTAGCGGTGTGGTCTG	
	ND6_Rv		ACACTCACCAAGACCTCAACC	
	ND5_Fw		AACCACCTAACCTGACTTC	
	ND5_Rv		TGTAACGAACAATGCTACAGG	
	tRNAQ_Fw		ATGGGGTGTGATAGGTGGC	
	tRNAQ_Rv		AGAATCGAACCCATCCCTGAG	
	scAct1_Fw		GTCCGGTATGGGTCAAAAAGACTC	
	scAct1_Rv		CAATTCGTTGTAGAAGGTATGATGCC	
			<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	

Table S1, Ohkubo et al.

Purpose	Name of oligo	Species	Sequence (5' to 3')	
Northern blotting	7SL probe_Fw	Human	CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAGAGACGGGTCTCGCTATG	
	7SL probe_Rv		GCCGGGCGCGGTGGCGCGTG	
	5S probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAAAGCCTACAGCACCCGGTAT	
	5S probe_Rv		GTCTACGGCCATACCACCTG	
	12S probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGGTGACGGGCGGTGTGTACG	
	12S probe_Rv		ACTCAAAGGACCTGGCGGTGC	
	16S probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAATCCAACATCGAGGTCGTAACCCT	
	16S probe_Rv		CCGTGAAGAGGGCGGCATAACAC	
	ND1 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGTCTAGCGGAATCGGGGG	
	ND1 probe_Rv		CTACGCCCTGATCGGGCAC	
	ND2 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGGCTCTAGGGAGAGGGGT	
	ND2 probe_Rv		CACCCCTCTGACTCCGGCCT	
	COX1 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGACGGCGGGTCAAGAAGGTG	
	COX1 probe_Rv		TGGAGGCCGAGCAGGAACA	
	COX2 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGATACCCCGGTCTGTAGCGG	
	COX2 probe_Rv		GCCTCCCATCCCTACGCA	
	ATP8/6 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGGGGGCAATGAATGAAGCGAACAG	
	ATP8/6 probe_Rv		TGGCCACCATAATTACCCCA	
	COX3 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAATGCCAGTATCAGCGGGCGG	
	COX3 probe_Rv		GGCCCCAACAGGCATCAC	
	ND3 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAAGGCCAGACTAGGGCTAGGATGA	
	ND3 probe_Rv		CCACCCCTTACGAGTCCGGC	
	ND4 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGGATGTAAGCCCGTGGGCGA	
	ND4 probe_Rv		AAGCCCCATCGTGGGTCA	
	ND5 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGGGCGCAGACTGCTGCGAACA	
	ND5 probe_Rv		ACGCCGAGCAGATGCCAAC	
	CYTb probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGCCTCACGGGAGGACATAGCC	
	CYTb probe_Rv		CTCACTCTTGGCCGCTGCC	
	ncCYTB probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAAGACAGTCCCACCTCACACGA	
	ncCYTB probe_Rv		AATTGTCTGGGTGCGCTAGGAG	
	ND6 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGACGAATCAACCCTGACCCCTC	
	ND6 probe_Rv		GATTGTTAGCCGTTGGTCTG	
	ncND5 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGACCCCATCTTACCACCTCGT	
	ncND5 probe_Rv		GTTGGCATCTGCTCGGGCGT	
	ncND3 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGACCACCCCTTACGAGTCCGGC	
	ncND3 probe_Rv		AGGCCAGACTTAGGGCTAGGATGA	
	ncCOX3 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAATGACCCACCAATCACATGC	
	ncCOX3 probe_Rv		AAGACCCTCATCAATAGATGG	
	ncATP8/6 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGATGGCCACCATAATTACCCCA	
	ncATP8/6 probe_Rv		GGGGCAATGAATGAAGCGAACAG	
	ncCOX2 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGACGCCCTCCATCCCTACGCA	
	ncCOX2 probe_Rv		TACCCCGGTCTGTAGCGG	
	ncCOX1 probe_Fw		CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGATGGAGCCGGAGCAGGAACA	
	ncCOX1 probe_Rv		CGCGGGGTCAAGAAGGTG	
	ceAct-1_Fw		C. elegans	CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGATTGGCGTACAAGTCTTACGG
	ceAct-1_Rv			GACTTCGAGCAAGAATGGCC
	ceND1_Fw			CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGATTTTCTTACGATACCGC
	ceND1_Rv			GAAGACAAAATCGTCTAGGGC
	ceND5_Fw			CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGATATGAACCAAGACCTCACCG
	ceND5_Rv			GTAGGGGTGCAATAAATACAGC
ce12S_Fw	CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAGAAATGTCTGCCAATATCTTTTC			
ce12S_Rv	CCTCGGCAATTTATCGCTTG			
ce16S_Fw	CGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGAAATCATAGGGCAGAAGCCAGC			
ce16S_Rv	AGAGTTGATATGTCGACCTTTG			

Table S1, Ohkubo et al.

Additional results

This section will detail some of the key results obtained during our attempts 1) to uncover the molecular function of FASTKD4, and 2) to identify enzymes that are responsible for the processing of non-canonical junctions, focusing on ND5-CYTB RNA processing.

4-1. Molecular function of FASTKD4

The mode of action of the FASTK protein family remains unclear. Despite their functional diversity, the FASTK family proteins share the conserved C-terminal domain architecture of three predictive RNA binding domains: FAST_1, FAST_2, and RAP domains (Figure 8) (Jourdain et al., 2017). Interestingly, several proteins containing the ancestral RAP domain have been characterized as proteins involved in RNA processing or splicing in chloroplasts (Glanz and Kuck, 2009; Jacobs et al., 2013; Kleinknecht et al., 2014). Furthermore, FASTK, which can either be located in the cytosol/nucleus or in the mitochondria (Jourdain et al., 2015), regulates alternative splicing of specific transcripts in nuclear speckles (Izquierdo and Valcarcel, 2007; Simarro et al., 2007). Additionally, we recently reported that the RAP domain seems structurally related to the PD-(D/E)-XK nuclease superfamily, a class of viral enzymes that display endonuclease activity (Boehm et al., 2017). Based on these data, we hypothesized that the RAP domain of the FASTK proteins might exhibit RNase activity and thereby participate in the cleavage of non-canonical junctions. Here, we describe the results of the *in vitro* experiments we carried out to test whether FASTKD4, a representative member of the protein family, displays an endonuclease activity and if this protein directly binds RNA.

FASTKD4 does not exhibit an endonuclease activity *in vitro*

To test the hypothesis that the FASTK proteins could cleave non-canonical junctions, we purified a recombinant protein of a representative member of the protein family and assessed its putative RNase activity *in vitro*. We selected FASTKD4, as this protein is known to regulate ND5-CYTB RNA processing (Boehm et al., 2017). A full-length recombinant human FASTKD4 protein tagged with His6 at the N-terminus (rFASTKD4) was expressed in *E. coli* and purified through affinity chromatography (Figure 9A-B). We evaluated the RNase activity of this rFASTKD4 protein *in vitro* (Figure 9C). As substrate RNAs, we used *in vitro* transcribed transcript containing the ND5-CYTB junction with short extensions at both ends

(mirror pre-tRNA^E; 14573-14843 of mtDNA) and its complementary RNA. We found that rFASTKD4 was unable to cleave this precursor RNA either as ssRNA, or as dsRNA. We concluded that either FASTKD4 does not display an intrinsic nuclease activity or that the experimental conditions were not optimal to reveal this activity. In particular, other mitochondrial components may be missing in our assay, notably FASTKD5 and PTCD2, which have also been reported to play a role in the processing of the ND5-CYTB junction (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Xu et al., 2008).

To further investigate whether FASTKD4 carries a RNase fold, we decided to solve the 3D structure of FASTKD4. This work was performed by Dr. Xuan Yang, a postdoctoral fellow in our group, who has expertise in structural biology. He purified a truncated version of the protein and obtained its crystal structure for X-ray analysis. This analysis was done in collaboration with Dr. Kelvin Lau, a past postdoctoral fellow in Prof. Michael Hothorn's group (University of Geneva). This represents the first structure of a RAP domain, a domain that is found in a high number of proteins, in particular in plants. Although these are the results from Dr. Xuan Yang, we agreed to report them in this part of the thesis manuscript, rather than in an Annex, to facilitate the reading of this chapter of the manuscript and because this structural analysis is consistent with the negative results we described above.

Figure 9D shows the crystal structure of truncated FASTKD4 (Q309 to C-terminus) including all the three domains. Of note, the FAST_2 domain contains a short part that is not structured. We found that both the RAP domain and the FAST_2 domain form the C-terminal fold, and the FAST_1 domain is apart. The FAST_1 domain forms helical repeats probably because the first 308 amino acids were removed from the protein to facilitate its crystallization. Based on these structural features, we may need to define this C-terminal domain formed by the FAST_2 and RAP domains as one independent domain. Next, we docked the C-terminal fold of FASTKD4 with VSR endonuclease (1VSR) (Tsutakawa et al., 1999), which we recently reported as being the closest structural model of FASTKD4 (Boehm et al., 2017) (Figure 9E). As predicted by the Phyre algorithm, folding of both proteins showed similarities, confirming that FASTKD4, and possibly other FASTK family proteins, are structurally related to the PD-(D/E)XK nuclease superfamily. However, the endonuclease catalytic pocket does not seem conserved, since the two catalytically essential histidines of 1VSR (H64 and H69) are not present in FASTKD4 (Figure 9F). These histidines are replaced with a tryptophan (H64 to W566) and an asparagine (H69 to N560) in FASTKD4.

Given that another aspartate, which plays a critical role in the nuclease activity of the 1VSR, is conserved in the RAP domain of FASTKD4, we tested its function in cultured cells,

as previously reported (Boehm et al., 2017) (Figure 9G). Briefly, we generated FASTKD4-KO 143B cells stably overexpressing WT or D523A point mutant FASTKD4 fused to a Flag tag at the C-terminus. We then measured steady-state levels of mitochondrial transcripts to see if the mutant protein could rescue the impairment of ND5-CYTB RNA processing. The D523A mutant FASTKD4 protein rescued the phenotype similar to the WT protein, suggesting that D523 is dispensable for the function of FASTKD4. Taken together, all these results suggest that it is unlikely that FASTKD4 displays an RNase activity. The protein might have lost its nuclease activity during evolution.

Figure 9. FASTKD4 unlikely exhibits a RNase activity

(A-B) The purity of the 69.8 kDa rFASTKD4 protein was analyzed by silver staining (A) and immunoblotting (B). For immunoblotting, whole cell lysates extracted from WT and FASTKD4-KO HAP1 cells (see the paper manuscript) were used as controls. (C) A potential RNase activity of the rFASTKD4 was analyzed in vitro using single-stranded (ssRNA) and double-stranded (dsRNA) synthetic RNA that includes the processing site of ND5-CYTB precursor RNA (14573-14843 of mtDNA). The genomic regions of the substrate RNAs were schematically represented (left). The arrow shows where the RNA cleavage occurs. 5 nM RNA was incubated with 5-500 nM rFASTKD4. RNase A was used as a control. Reaction products were analyzed by northern blotting. (D-F) Crystal structures of truncated FASTKD4 protein. (D) An overall structure including C-terminal domains is

shown. FAST_1, FAST_2, and RAP domains are colored in light blue, dark blue, and orange, respectively. Pointed lines show missing residues. (E) The C-terminal fold (S444 to C-terminus) is docked with VSR endonuclease (1VSR; magenta). (F) Catalytically essential residues of VSR endonuclease (magenta) are compared with corresponding residues of FASTKD4 (yellow). (G) Steady-state levels of mitochondrial transcripts of WT and FASTKD4-KO 143B cells (Boehm et al., 2017) overexpressing GFP (control), WT or D523A mutant FASTKD4 protein were measured by Northern blotting. 7SL RNA was used as a loading control. Expression level of FASTKD4 protein was measured by immunoblotting. β -actin was used as a loading control.

FASTKD4 non-specifically binds to RNA *in vitro*

As the complementary study of the HITS-CLIP revealed that FASTKD4 preferably binds to tRNA^E (see the paper manuscript), we evaluated the RNA binding ability of the full-length rFASTKD4 protein *in vitro* through EMSA. The EMSA was performed using the rFASTKD4 and *in vitro* transcribed pre-tRNA^E, which includes tRNA^E with short extensions at both ends (14573-14843 of mtDNA) or with its antisense transcript (mirror pre-tRNA^E), and various other transcripts as controls (Figure 10). These experiments showed that FASTKD4 binds pre-tRNA^E as well as its complementary transcript (Figure 10A). Consistent with this lack of specificity, FASTKD4 was also able to bind with a similar affinity other transcripts including pre-tRNA^R, a cluster of four tRNAs (tRNA^Y-tRNA^A) (Figure 10B), a 62 nt short RNA corresponding to Δ tRNA^E-ND6 (Figure 10C) and other control RNAs (Δ ND4 and Δ ATP6; Figure 10D). No binding experiments were performed using dsRNA. Such an experiment is imperative to be performed, especially because the viral endonucleases described above are expected to cleave dsDNA.

We concluded that FASTKD4 is able to bind RNA directly, which had never been shown before. However, *in vitro*, FASTKD4 appears to bind RNA in a non-specific manner, which suggests that the specific binding revealed by the HITS-CLIP may be the result of a cooperation between FASTKD4 and other mitochondrial components missing in our *in vitro* assay.

Figure 10. FASTKD4 non-specifically binds to RNA *in vitro*.

(A-D) The RNA binding ability of rFASTKD4 was analyzed by EMSA. 5 nM synthetic RNA was incubated with 5-500 nM rFASTKD4. 500 nM BSA was used as a control. Reaction products were analyzed by northern blotting. ΔATP6 RNA was analyzed only in the absence or presence of 500 nM rFASTKD4 (D).

4-2. Exploration of the ND5-CYTB RNA processing machinery

Here, we will detail our attempts to identify endonuclease(s) responsible for the cleavage of the ND5-CYTB junction.

Human PTCD2 is involved in ND5-CYTB RNA processing

In addition to FASTKD4 and FASTKD5, a PPR domain-containing protein PTCD2 has been proposed to participate in ND5-CYTB RNA processing. However, its mode of action remains unknown. It has been reported that the deletion of PTCD2 in mouse causes impairment in ND5-CYTB RNA processing, resulting in defects in CYTB protein synthesis and the assembly and activity of MRC complex III, as described in 3-1-4-10 (Xu et al., 2008). To evaluate if this is also the case in humans, we generated a CRISPR/Cas9 KO 143B human cell line (Figure 11). Two different gRNAs, targeting exon 1 and exon 6 respectively, were cloned into plasmid lentiCRISPR v2 (addgene #52961) according to the inventor's protocol (Sanjana et al., 2014; Shalem et al., 2014a), and the plasmids were packaged into lentivirus and transfected to 143B cells. Genetic modifications of every allele of single clonal cells were determined by Sanger sequencing, as detailed in Figure 11A. As a consequence of these genetic modifications, the generated KO cell must express a truncated PTCD2 protein (up to 252E missing three residues corresponding to 18-20 aa; a full-length protein constitutes of 388 aa) that is expected to be non-functional. However, we were not able to confirm the loss of protein expression as good antibodies against PTCD2 are not commercially available.

As expected, the knockout of PTCD2 caused an impairment in ND5-CYTB RNA processing (Figure 11B), which is reminiscent of what we observed in FASTKD4 KO cells. Furthermore, we found that the steady-state levels of mRNAs (COX1, ND4L/4, and ND6) and ncRNAs (ncCYTB and ncND5) were decreased in the PTCD2-KO, while the ND3 mRNA level was specifically increased (Figure 11C). It is important to note that this RNA expression pattern differs from that in FASTKD4-KO 143B cells we have previously shown (Boehm et al., 2017). Notably, the ND3 mRNA level is antagonistically regulated by both proteins. Next, we investigated if this RNA regulation by PTCD2 is necessary for mitochondrial respiration. The loss of PTCD2 did not result in reduced oxygen consumption (Figure 11D) despite decreased components of the MRC complexes III and IV (Figure 11E). The level of nascent ND5 protein was increased despite a defect in ND5-CYTB RNA processing (Figure 11F), which is similar to elevated ND5 protein synthesis in FASTKD4-KO HAP1 cells (see the

paper manuscript). This finding indicates that both proteins may cooperate not only in ND5-CYTB RNA processing but also for ND5 translation.

We found that the knockout of PTCD2 affects expression levels of proteins involved in post-transcriptional regulation (Figure 11G). While the FASTK family protein levels were not affected, GRSF1 and RPUSD4 protein levels were decreased in the absence of PTCD2. Knowing that GRSF1 resolves G-quadruplex of transcripts derived from the LSP and facilitates their degradation (Pietras et al., 2018), PTCD2 may inhibit GRSF1 activity and thus increase the stability of the L-strand transcripts including ND6 mRNA and ncRNAs (Figure 11C). Given 1) that RPUSD4 is necessary for pseudouridylation of 16S rRNA and mitoribosome assembly (Antonicka et al., 2017; Zaganelli et al., 2017), and 2) the decreased expression of RPUSD4 protein in the loss of PTCD2, these findings suggest that PTCD2 may play a role in mitoribosome assembly or/and mitochondrial translation similar to other protein family members, PTCD1 and PTCD3 (Haque et al., 2011; Lightowlers and Chrzanowska-Lightowlers, 2013; Perks et al., 2018).

A

Figure 11. PTC2D2 regulates ND5-CYTB RNA processing. (A) Description of the PTC2D2-KO 143B cell line. (B-C) The steady-state levels of mitochondrial transcripts in WT (control) and PTC2D2-KO cells were measured by northern blotting. FASTKD4-KO cells (Boehm et al., 2017) were also analysed in (B). 5S and 7SL were used as loading controls. (D) The oxygen consumption rate (OCR) in WT (control) and PTC2D2-KO cells was measured using a Seahorse analyser. OCR was normalized by the number of cells. (E) Protein expression levels of respiratory chain complexes in WT (control) and PTC2D2-KO cells were measured by immunoblotting. Whole cell lysates (WCL) and mitochondria extracted from the cells were analysed. Total OXPHOS Rodent WB Antibody Cocktail antibody (ab110413) indicates levels of ETC components. mtHSP70 was used as a loading control for

mitochondria. **(F)** Levels of de novo mitochondrial protein synthesis were measured in WT (control) and PTCD2-KO cells by pulse incorporation of ³⁵S-labeled methionine and cysteine. Equal amounts of whole cell lysates were separated by SDS-PAGE and visualized by autoradiography. **(G)** Expression levels of proteins involved in mitochondrial post-transcriptional regulation in WT (control) and PTCD2-KO cells were measured by immunoblotting. γ -tubulin was used as a loading control of whole cell lysates. mtHSP70 and VDAC1 were used as mitochondrial loading controls.

PTCD2 shows a protein interaction profile similar to FASTKD4 and FASTKD5

We carried out BioID to reveal the protein interactome of PTCD2 and to investigate whether this protein associates with FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 for ND5-CYTB RNA processing (Figure 12). Mass spec analyses were carried out by Alexandre Hainard and Patrizia Arboit (Proteomics Core Facility, University of Geneva). The protein interaction network mainly included mitochondrial proteins and more than 80% of them were RNA binding proteins based on GO term - molecular function (Figure 12A-B). The PTCD2 interactome showed high similarity to the BioID results of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 (see the paper manuscript), which indicates that they are localized in close proximity within the mitochondrial matrix (Figure 12C). We observed that PTCD2 interacts with FASTKD5 and FASTKD2 but not with FASTKD4. Since FASTKD5 was also identified in the FASTKD4-BioID, FASTKD5 may mediate the activity of PTCD2 and FASTKD4 in ND5-CYTB RNA processing. TRMT10C (MRPP1), a subunit of RNase P complex, was found in the BioID datasets of PTCD2 and FASTKD4, suggesting that these proteins may regulate the processing of canonical tRNA junctions. Alternatively, MRPP1 may also participate in the cleavage of tRNA-less junctions associated with other enzymes, as previously proposed (Sanchez et al., 2011). We found that PTCD2 interacts with FASTKD2 and DHX30, both of which are involved in the mitoribosome assembly. FASTKD2 forms a 16S rRNA maturation complex with proteins including RPU5D4 of which the protein expression level is decreased in the loss of PTCD2 (Figure 11G). These findings indicate that PTCD2 might have a role in the mitoribosome assembly and translation like the other PTCD family proteins (Haque et al., 2011; Lightowlers and Chrzanowska-Lightowlers, 2013; Perks et al., 2018).

Together, these BioID analyses revealed that FASTKD4, FASTKD5 and PTCD2 are located in close proximity and may possibly form complexes. They also allowed us to identify some interesting proteins (e.g. LETM2 and ACOT1) whose functions have not yet been characterised in the context of mitochondrial post-transcriptional regulation, whereas the analyses did not enable us to identify novel RNase(s) responsible for the cleavage of the ND5-CYTB junction.

Figure 12. Protein interaction network of PTCD2 analyzed through BioID. (A) Log₂FC (PTCD2-BirA/control) (A) was plotted against a sum of normalized total spectra. Only significantly enriched proteins are shown (Log₂FC \geq 1). Cells that do not express the bait protein were used as control. Mitochondrial proteins are marked in blue. The red dot represents BirA-tagged bait PTCD2 protein. (B) Gene ontology analysis (molecular function) of mitochondrial proteins present in the PTCD2 BioID. (C) Numbers of mitochondrial proteins identified by the PTCD2 BioID are also present in either or both the BioID results of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 that we also carried out (see the paper manuscript).

Non-canonical RNA processing is not catalyzed by the exoRNase activity of PNPase

PNPase is a 3'-5' exoRNase that is the catalytic enzyme of the mtRNA degradosome as described in 3-1-4-5. Recently, we reported that the mtRNA degradosome is needed for the processing of the 3' UTR of ND6, because pre-ND6 is protected by mtFASTK, which prevents the complete RNA decay by the mtRNA degradosome (Jourdain et al., 2015). A more recent study revealed that the mtRNA degradosome prevents accumulation of mitochondrial dsRNA (Dhir et al., 2018). A duplex formation could inhibit the canonical tRNA processing, and potentially also the non-canonical RNA processing. This prompted us to investigate if PNPase is involved in the processing of the non-canonical junctions. To this end, we generated a 143B human cell line stably expressing shPNPase using pLKO.1-shPNPase plasmids as described previously (Jourdain et al., 2015) and studied whether the knockdown of PNPase affects the steady-state levels of mitochondrial transcripts (Figure 13). Consistent with a previous study (Borowski et al., 2013), the levels of mature rRNAs and specific mRNAs were dramatically decreased in the loss of PNPase (Figure 13B). While ATP8/6-COX3 precursor RNA level seemed to be slightly reduced by shPNPase, the processing of other non-canonical precursor transcripts was not affected. This finding indicates that PNPase is unlikely to actively regulate the processing of non-canonical junctions.

Figure 13. PNPase does not control non-canonical mtRNA processing. (A) Expression levels of the PNPT1 (PNPase) protein in cells stably expressing shPNPase (pLKO.1-shPNPase) or empty vector (pLKO.1) as a control were measured by immunoblotting. β -actin was used as a loading control. (B) The steady-state levels of mitochondrial rRNAs and mRNAs in controls and cells stably expressing pLKO.1-shPNPase or empty vectors were measured by northern blotting. 7SL was used as a loading control.

Materials and methods

Described here, are the material and methods that I used to obtain these additional results. Please also refer to the paper manuscript entitled “The FASTK family proteins fine-tune mitochondrial RNA processing”.

Cell culture and transfection

143B cells and HEK293T cells were cultured in Dulbecco’s modified Eagle medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), 2 mM L-glutamine, 100 U/ml penicillin, and 100 mg/ml streptomycin in 5% CO₂ at 37°C. Transfections were performed using polyethylenimine (PEI).

Viral production

Lentiviruses were produced as we previously described (Jourdain et al., 2015). Lentiviruses for FASTKD4 protein overexpression were produced in HEK293T cells by co-transfecting the constructs of interest cloned into the pWPT vector with the viral plasmids psPAX2 and pMD2G (Addgene). After 2 days, the supernatant was collected, filtered at 0.45 µm, and used to infect 143B cells. pLKO.1 including a PNPT1 shRNA sequence from (Jourdain et al., 2015) and plentiCRISPR v2 where PTCD2 gRNA was subcloned were also used to produce lentiviruses in the same protocol. After infection for >2 days, cells were selected with 3 mg/ml puromycin (Sigma) and analyzed.

Generation of CRISPR/Cas9 PTCD2 knockout cells

Either gRNA targeting exon 1 (CCAAAATCTGCAGCGCCTGCAGG) or exon 7 (AGAGAAGAAGCTCTACTCAAAGG) of PTCD2 locus (PAM sequences are underlined) was cloned into plasmid lentiCRISPR v2 (addgene #52961), following the inventor’s protocol (Sanjana et al., 2014; Shalem et al., 2014b). The two plasmids were packaged into lentiviruses and co-transfected in 143B cells. After puromycin selection, single cells were sorted by fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS) and were plated into individual wells of a 96-well plate. Screening of clones was performed by Sanger sequencing.

Affinity purification of recombinant FASTKD4 protein and activity assays

The coding sequence of the human FASTKD4 gene without its N-terminal MTS was cloned into pRK792 (Addgene 8830, a kind gift of Prof. Thomas Schalch, University of Leicester) in frame with N-terminal maltose binding protein (MBP) fused to a TEV protease cleavage sequence-His6. The assembly of plasmids was carried out using Gibson Assembly Master Mix (NEB, M5510). The protein was expressed in *E. coli* Rosetta (DE3) by the addition of 0.2 mM IPTG (isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactoside) at 16 °C for 18 h at OD600 = 0.7. Cells were lysed in 25 mM HEPES pH7.8, 1M KCl, 20 mM imidazole, 1mM DTT, 5 mM ATP, 0.01% DDM, and an in-house protease inhibitor cocktail (2 μ M pepstatin, 2 μ M leupeptin, 1 mM PMSF, 1 mM benzamidine, 1 μ g/mL aprotinin)) using French press under 10000 psi. After the elimination of MBP tag with 50 μ g/L TEV protease at 4°C for 1.5 h, soluble proteins were collected by ultracentrifugation at 100,000 g, then subjected to HisTrap Fast Flow Crude column (GE Healthcare). The elution was carried out with gradually increasing imidazole concentrations up to 500 mM. 250-500 mM imidazole fractions were pooled. The pooled proteins were concentrated using Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Unit (Millipore), then further purified through Superdex 200 10/300 GL column (GE Healthcare) in 25 mM HEPES pH 7.8, 150 mM KCl, 1 mM DTT, and an in-house protease inhibitor cocktail. Monomeric fractions of FASTKD4 protein were pooled and stored at -80°C in 50% (v/v) glycerol. Purified protein samples were resolved by SDS-PAGE and then followed by silver staining.

For the RNase activity assay, 5-500 nM rFASTKD4 protein was incubated for 30 min at 37°C with 5 nM synthetic RNA in 30 mM Tris pH 8, 40 mM NaCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM DTT, 1 mM ATP, 5% glycerol, 0.01% (w/v) NP40, and homemade protease inhibitor cocktail. Prior to the reaction, substrate RNA was heated at 75°C for 10 min then immediately cooled on ice for renaturation. To form dsRNA, synthetic RNA was heated with its complementary RNA at 75°C for 10 min in 20 mM Tris pH 7.4, 100 mM NaCl, and 0.2 mM MgCl₂, then gradually cooled down to room temperature. RNA products were separated on denaturing formaldehyde 1% agarose gel and analysed by northern blotting.

For the electrophoretic mobility shift assay (EMSA), 5-500 nM purified rFASTKD4 protein (or 500 nM BSA as a control) was incubated for 30 min at 37°C with 5 nM single-stranded synthetic RNA in the same buffer as the RNase activity assay supplemented with 1U/ μ L RNasin Plus RNase Inhibitor (Promega). RNA-protein complexes were separated on 5-8% polyacrylamide gel in 0.5x TBE pH 8.3 and analyzed by northern blotting.

***In vitro* transcription**

Synthetic RNAs were generated using T7 RNA Polymerase (Promega) following the manufacturer's instructions. DNA templates including a T7 promoter sequence at the 5' end were amplified by PCR and purified using Wizard SV Gel and PCR Clean-Up System (Promega). Synthesized RNA was purified using TRIzol reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

V. Discussion

The aim of my PhD thesis work has been to uncover the roles of the FASTK protein family in mitochondrial post-transcriptional control, mainly focusing on non-canonical RNA processing. While the results we obtained do not provide a conclusive answer on how the FASTK family proteins act molecularly, they establish these proteins as crucial regulators of both canonical and non-canonical mtRNA processing. The discussion will recapitulate some of the key results we obtained during this PhD work, and examine how they contribute to improving our understanding of the FASTK protein family and mtRNA processing. We will also discuss here our attempts to understand the molecular mechanisms of non-canonical mtRNA processing.

5-1. The FASTK protein family

5-1-1. The FASTK proteins control both canonical and non-canonical mtRNA processing

The FASTKD proteins specifically regulate the steady-state level of mtRNAs and mtRNA processing as summarized in Figure 8: mtFASTK is involved in the processing of the 3' UTR of ND6 (Jourdain et al., 2015); FASTKD1 specifically reduces the stability of ND1 mRNA (Boehm et al., 2017); FASTKD2 stabilizes ND6 mRNA and 16S rRNA (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Popow et al., 2015); FASTKD3 destabilizes ND2, ND3, COX2, ATP8/6, and CYTB mRNAs (Boehm et al., 2016); FASTKD4 increases the level of ND3, ND5, COX1-3, ATP8/6, and CYTB mRNAs and facilitates ND5-CYTB RNA processing (Boehm et al., 2017); FASTKD5 increases COX1, COX3, and ATP8/6 mRNA levels but decreases ND1-5, COX2, and CYTB mRNA levels, and is needed for the processing of ND5-CYTB, pre-COX1, and ATP8/6-COX3 precursor transcripts (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015).

During this PhD work, we generated HAP1 cell lines that contain single or double knockouts of FASTKD3-5 (FASTKD3-sKO, FASTKD4-sKO, FASTKD5-sKO, FASTKD3&4-dKO, and FASTKD4&5-dKO) and carried out mitochondrial transcriptome analyses to investigate the role of these proteins in post-transcriptional regulation. Loss of FASTKD3 had minor effects on the abundance of mtRNAs, and only ND3 mRNA was remarkably increased. In contrast, the absence of FASTKD4 or FASTKD5 caused major changes in a broad range of mtRNAs. Loss of FASTKD4 caused a decrease in ND3, ND5, ATP8/6, and COX3 mRNAs. The absence of FASTKD5 resulted in a significant accumulation

of ND1, ND2 and COX2 mRNAs and a decrease in ND5, ATP8/6, COX3, and COX1 mRNAs.

Moreover, the loss of FASTKD4 or/and FASTKD5 resulted in defects in the processing of tRNA-less non-canonical junctions, as we and others previously reported (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Boehm et al., 2017; Boehm et al., 2016). These defects, however, were not seen with the loss of FASTKD3. Loss of FASTKD4 specifically resulted in impaired ND5-CYTB RNA processing, and the loss of FASTKD5 caused defects in the cleavage of the ND5-CYTB junction, the 3'UTR of COX1, and the ATP8/6-COX3 junction. The defective processing of the ND5-CYTB junction was observed in both single KOs of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5. This processing defect was further pronounced when both proteins were lost, which suggests that FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 may have synergistic roles in the RNA processing and the loss of either one might be compensated for by the other protein. The FASTKD proteins have antagonistic effects on the amounts of some specific mRNAs, but these might be a consequence of the complex competitive association of the FASTKD proteins. For instance, ND3 mRNA level was significantly increased in FASTKD3-sKO and FASTKD5-sKO but decreased in FASTKD4-sKO. Nevertheless, the level of ND3 mRNA was lowered in the two dKO cell lines (FASTKD3&4-dKO and FASTKD4&5-dKO), indicating that FASTKD4 appears to have a predominant effect on the regulation of ND3 mRNA over FASTKD3 and FASTKD5. However, it is also possible that other post-transcriptional regulators compensated for the loss of the FASTKD proteins to maintain a balanced mitochondrial transcriptome, which is supported by the finding that MRPP1, ELAC2, and RPUSD4 protein levels were decreased, whereas SUV3 protein was increased, in the cell lines lacking FASTKD5.

The mitochondrial transcriptome analyses revealed that the FASTKD proteins are also involved in the cleavage of some specific tRNA junctions such as the cluster of tRNAs in the ND1-ND2 region and tRNA^E between ncCYTB and ND6. This implies that the FASTKD proteins may recruit the tRNA processing enzymes to some specific sites, which is consistent with the decrease in MRPP1 and ELAC2 protein levels we observed in FASTKD5-deficient cells. Regulation of the processing of specific tRNA junctions by the FASTKD proteins might critically affect downstream events including the cleavage of non-canonical junctions (Rackham et al., 2016; Siira et al., 2018). Interestingly, the loss of FASTKD3-5 may nevertheless stimulate a general response to defective processing because, in their absence, more efficient processing is observed at certain canonical processing sites, such as tRNA^T.

Alternatively, FASTKD proteins might act as adapters that increase the processing efficiency of tRNA-less precursor transcripts.

The RNA-seq further indicated that FASTKD4 is likely necessary for the cleavage of the junction between antisense ATP8/6 and COX3 RNA that is not flanked by tRNA. Furthermore, the northern blot analysis revealed that the processing of some specific sncRNAs, sncATP8/6 and sncCOX1, appears to be perturbed in cells lacking FASTKD4, highlighting the hypothesis that the FASTKD proteins are also involved in ncRNA processing.

5-1-2. The FASTK proteins regulate the stability of mitochondrial non-coding RNAs

Human mitochondrial transcription leads to 2 almost genome-length, polycistronic transcripts generated from either the HSP or the LSP (see the human mtDNA map shown in Figure 4). In contrast to the gene-rich HSP-derived transcripts, the post-transcriptional control of the LSP-derived transcripts, which include ND6 mRNA and eight tRNAs that span long non-coding regions, is poorly understood, and the involvement of the FASTK family proteins in the regulation of these transcripts remains unknown. Interestingly, the LSP-derived transcripts include numerous ncRNAs that are specifically processed and their stability is controlled in a post-transcriptional manner by unknown mechanisms (Rackham et al., 2011).

The mitochondrial transcriptomics we performed during this PhD work revealed that FASTKD3-5 regulate the amount of mitochondrial ncRNAs. Steady-state levels of some specific ncRNAs were increased in the knockouts of FASTKD4-5 genes. The increase of specific ncRNAs was in contrast to the reduction of their complementary mRNAs. This suggests that FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 have a role in the clearance of the antisense transcripts during the processing of sense transcripts. Impaired clearance of antisense RNA can cause processing defects and destabilization of their complementary mRNAs, since the antisense transcripts may form duplexes with their complementary mRNAs, potentially precluding their cleavage and resulting reduced translation (Rackham et al., 2011). Additionally, such long ncRNAs can potentially have particular secondary structures with specific functions, as extensively demonstrated in the nucleus (Yao et al., 2019). It will be interesting to investigate the secondary structures of these long ncRNAs and whether they associate with mitochondrial proteins to regulate their activities and mitochondrial gene expression.

The accumulation of specific light strand-derived transcripts and the decrease of their complementary heavy strand-derived transcripts in the loss of FASTKD4 or FASTKD5 is

reminiscent of knockdown effects of the mtRNA degradosome (Borowski et al., 2013; Pietras et al., 2018). This suggests that these FASTKD proteins may recruit the mtRNA degradosome to specific ncRNAs to promote their decay. The possible association of these FASTKD proteins with the mtRNA degradosome is interesting since we had previously found that mtFASTK is involved in the processing of the 3' UTR of ND6 through cooperation with the mtRNA degradosome (Jourdain et al., 2015). Interestingly, we also observed the overexpression of SUV3 protein in the cells lacking FASTKD5. Further studies will be needed to investigate the possible association of the FASTK family proteins and the mtRNA degradosome in the post-transcriptional regulation of ncRNA stability and processing.

5-1-3. The FASTK proteins regulate mitochondrial translation

It is known that the knockdown of FASTKD2 compromises overall mitochondrial translation, because as a component of the 16S rRNA maturation module, which includes RPUSD4, it is essential for its pseudouridylation (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Arroyo et al., 2016; Popow et al., 2015; Zaganelli et al., 2017). Other FASTK family members specifically regulate mitochondrial protein synthesis: the knockout of FASTKD1 causes an increase in ND1, ND3, ND4, and ND5 protein synthesis (Boehm et al., 2017); the loss of FASTKD3 leads to a specific decrease in COX1 protein synthesis (Boehm et al., 2016); the absence of FASTKD4 results in an increase in ND1, ND4, ND5, and ND6 protein synthesis and a decrease in ND3 translation (Boehm et al., 2017); the knockdown of FASTKD5 leads to a decrease in CYTB, ND2, ND1, COX3, ATP6, and COX1 protein synthesis (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015). Notably, COX1 protein synthesis is dramatically down-regulated when FASTKD5 is knocked down.

In this PhD work, we investigated the effects of the FASTK protein family on mitochondrial translation by characterising HAP1 cell lines that harbour single or multiple knockouts of FASTKD3-5. The loss of FASTKD3 resulted in a specific increase of ND3 protein synthesis as expected from the accumulation of its mRNA. However, COX1 translation was not affected, which was inconsistent with our previous report (Boehm et al., 2016). This difference might be explained by cell type-specificities (HAP1 cell vs U2OS cell). The loss of FASTKD3 in HAP1 cells may be compensated by other FASTK proteins or other mtRBPs. Similarly, it has been reported that loss of FASTKD2 has different impacts on mitochondrial respiration depending on the cell type (Antonicka et al., 2017; Arroyo et al., 2016; Popow et al., 2015). The loss of FASTKD4 resulted in a decrease in ND3 protein

synthesis that is consistent with the decrease of its mRNA, as well as an increase in ND5 and COX1 translation. The knockout of FASTKD5 resulted in a decrease in COX1, COX2, and ATP6 protein synthesis and an increase in ND4 translation. Importantly, COX1 protein synthesis was entirely inhibited in the FASTKD5-deficient cells, which is probably a consequence of the defective processing of the 5'UTR of COX1 precursor RNA. The double knockout of FASTKD3 and FASTKD4 resulted in an alteration of specific protein synthesis similar to the FASTKD4-sKO, including ND3 protein synthesis that is antagonistically regulated by both proteins. This suggests that FASTKD4 has a predominant effect on mitochondrial translation. The double knockout of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 showed a mitochondrial translation profile resulting from the combinatory effects of each single knockout. For example, ND3 protein synthesis was down-regulated in the FASTKD4&5-dKO cells as observed in the FASTKD4-sKO cells. However, interestingly, COX1 protein synthesis, which was elevated in the FASTKD4-sKO cells, was totally inhibited in the FASTKD4&5-dKO cells as in FASTKD5-sKO cells, indicating that FASTKD5 has a predominant effect on COX1 translation, probably due to its role in pre-COX1 RNA processing.

It is important to note that translation and mRNA expression do not always correlate. For instance, ND5 protein synthesis was boosted in FASTKD4-deficient cells but did not change in the absence of FASTKD5, despite a similar impairment in ND5-CYTB RNA processing. This suggests that, when mRNA levels are low, mechanisms that favour increased translation could be at work to ensure normal protein levels. Alternatively, it is possible that in addition to processed mRNAs, bicistronic precursor transcripts, for example ND5-CYTB transcripts, might be recognized and processed by mitoribosomes. Moreover, the loss of both proteins showed a competitive effect on the ND5 protein synthesis, suggesting that FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 have antagonistic roles in the translation of ND5 protein. It will be interesting to carry out mitoribosome profiling to investigate how ND5 protein synthesis is fine-tuned by the FASTKD proteins. Together, our data indicate that FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 specifically regulate protein synthesis even without altering the mtRNA amount, which suggests that FASTKD proteins may play a role in mitochondrial translation.

5-1-4. The FASTK proteins control the MRC assembly and mitochondrial respiration

As all the proteins encoded from the mtDNA are subunits of the mitochondrial respiratory chain (MRC) complexes, it is not surprising that loss of FASTK family proteins

can cause problems of MRC assembly and ATP production through OXPHOS. The knockdown of FASTKD2 causes an overall reduction in the assembly of all the MRC complexes except complex II, which is exclusively encoded in the nuclear DNA (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015). The other family members specifically regulate the OXPHOS complex formation: the knockout of FASTK causes a specific disassembly of the complex I and reduction of its activity, as a consequence of the defective processing of the 3'UTR of ND6 precursor RNA (Jourdain et al., 2015); the knockout of FASTKD3 results in a defective complex IV assembly and activity, consistent with a reduction in COX1 protein synthesis (Boehm et al., 2016); the knockdown of FASTKD5 also results in a specific disassembly of complex IV consistent with a defect in COX1 translation (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015).

During this PhD work, we investigated the effects of FASTKD3-5 on the expression of MRC in FASTKDs-KO HAP1 cells. We observed that the loss of FASTKD3 or FASTKD4 resulted in mild defects in the expression of a complex V subunit. Additionally, the loss of FASTKD4 caused an increase in the formation of complex IV, which may be a consequence of the elevated COX1 protein synthesis. The knockout of FASTKD5 caused decreased expression of of complex III and complex IV components. Consistently, oxygen consumption was significantly altered in the cells lacking FASTKD5.

Taken together, these findings indicate that among the three gene deletions, the knockout of FASTKD5 appears to be the most severe, probably as a consequence of its impact on COX1 expression.

5-1-5. Molecular function of FASTK family members

The mode of action of the FASTK protein family remains to be elucidated. As detailed in the results section (see 4-1), during this PhD work, we purified full-length recombinant FASTKD4 (rFASTKD4) protein and tested its putative RNase activity *in vitro* in order to assess the hypothesis that the RAP domain of the FASTK family proteins may exhibit RNase activity responsible for non-canonical mtRNA processing (Boehm et al., 2017). We could demonstrate a binding of the rFASTKD4 to RNA *in vitro*. However, we have not been able to detect any RNase activity associated with the rFASTKD4, and this observation was consistent with the 3D structure of FASTKD4 obtained in our laboratory (Yang et al., unpublished data). The overall structure of FASTKD4 was similar to 1VSR. However, the catalytically essential histidines of the 1VSR are absent in FASTKD4, and another catalytically essential aspartate, which present in both proteins, was found to be dispensable for the function of FASTKD4 in

cells. With all these results, we concluded that the putative RNase catalytic pocket of FASTKD4 is likely inactive. It would be interesting to introduce the key residues, the histidines found in 1VSR, in FASTKD4 and assess whether this would be sufficient to confer FASTKD4 an endonuclease activity.

Our data are not sufficient to exclude the possibility that FASTKD4 is the catalytic enzyme involved in ND5-CYTB processing. For example, the rFASTKD4 expressed in *E. coli* might have lacked essential post-translational modifications. Alternatively, the synthetic RNAs used for the *in vitro* RNase activity assay might not have been properly folded and therefore not recognized by the rFASTKD4, knowing that the non-canonical junctions are predicted to have particular secondary structures (Mercer et al., 2011). Finally, biochemical conditions such as salt concentration and divalent metal ions might not have been optimised for the *in vitro* RNase activity assay.

Our findings also do not exclude the possibility that other members of the protein family exhibit RNase activity. It will be imperative to analyse additional members to make a general conclusion about the whole protein family, particularly FASTKD5, which emerges as a key member of the family, especially in the context of non-canonical mtRNA processing.

The founding protein member FASTK was originally introduced as a kinase (Tian et al., 1995). Recently, FASTK has been shown *in vitro* to display an ATPase activity (Khan et al., 2018). Since the BioID results of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 indicated that both proteins seem to localize in close proximity to the ATP synthase, it is possible that these proteins need ATP for their function.

5-1-6. RNA interaction network of the FASTK proteins

There is growing evidence that the FASTK family proteins specifically associate with mtRNAs. mtFASTK binds to ND6 mRNA and its 3'UTR, which is necessary for pre-ND6 RNA processing (Jourdain et al., 2015). FASTKD2 specifically interacts with 16S rRNA and ND6 mRNA (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015; Popow et al., 2015; Van Nostrand et al., 2020). FASTKD4 seems to non-specifically bind to mtRNAs based on an IP-qPCR analysis (Wolf and Mootha, 2014), and FASTKD5 associates with 12S rRNA and all the mRNAs, except for ND3 mRNA (Antonicka and Shoubridge, 2015).

In this PhD thesis, we investigated the RNA binding ability of FASTKD4. As described in the previous section, we found that rFASTKD4 non-specifically binds RNA *in vitro*. In contrast, and surprisingly, the HITS-CLIP data revealed that FASTKD4 specifically binds to

tRNA^E in cultured cells. The reason for such selectivity in the cell may result from the presence of additional proteins that are missing in our *in vitro* assay. In addition, FASTKD4 is loosely attached to the inner mitochondrial membrane (Boehm et al., 2017; Wolf and Mootha, 2014), and thus we cannot exclude the possibility that lipids play a role in the specific binding of FASTKD4 to tRNA^E.

The HITS-CLIP data are striking, as they point to tRNA^E as the only transcript found to bind to FASTKD4. This binding is also striking because this transcript is complementary to the ND5-CYTB junction, which supports our hypothesis that FASTKD4 plays a role in the processing of this junction. At this point we still don't know how the binding of FASTKD4 to tRNA^E could be involved in the processing of ND5-CYTB precursor RNA. FASTKD4 might be a RNA chaperone needed for proper folding of tRNA^E, and thereby could prevent unfolded tRNA^E from forming a duplex with its complementary region, which could potentially have an inhibitory effect on ND5-CYTB RNA processing. If RNA binding occurs prior to the processing of tRNA^E, FASTKD4 can bind to tRNA^E precursor transcripts containing ND6 and its long 3'UTR, and this interaction may largely affect the processing and/or stability of light strand transcripts. Since we found that FASTKD3 and FASTKD5 also regulate tRNA processing at some specific sites, it would be interesting to investigate if they also associate with tRNAs. Interestingly, the binding of FASTKD4 to tRNA^E was not accompanied by a change in the level of this tRNA. These findings are reminiscent of a previous report about MRPS27, in which the authors revealed that this PPR protein specifically binds to tRNA^E without altering its level (Davies et al., 2012). Given that MRPS27 is a component of mitoribosomal small subunit, this may suggest that FASTKD4 plays a role in mitochondrial translation, potentially being recruited to mitoribosomes together with tRNA^E.

5-1-7. Protein interaction network of the FASTK proteins

Many recent studies have shown that the FASTK family proteins associate with each other and interact with other mtRBPs. mtFASTK interacts with FASTKD2, FASTKD5, GRSF1, DHX30, PNPT1, MRPP3, SLIRP, and YARS2 (Zaganelli et al., 2017). FASTKD2 associates with FASTKD5, POLRMT, GRSF1, PTC1, PTC3, PNPT1, SUV3, TRUB2, WBSCR16, NGRN, DHX30, IARS2, RPUSD3, and RPUSD4 (Antonicka et al., 2017; Arroyo et al., 2016; Perks et al., 2018; Zaganelli et al., 2017). It is important to note that FASTKD2 is known to form a 16S rRNA maturation complex with RPUSD4, RPUSD3, PTC1,

WBSCR16, NGRN, and TRUB2. FASTKD3 interacts with FASTKD2, LRPPRC, DHX30, PNPT1, IARS2, TARS2, and PTC1 (Simarro et al., 2010b).

In this PhD work, we carried out BioID experiments to characterise the protein interactomes of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5. As expected, both proteins were enriched with mitochondrial proteins involved in post-transcriptional regulation. Both proteins showed similar interactome profiles including mtRBPs such as LRPPRC and GRSF1. These findings indicate that the FASTKD proteins may require additional proteins for their functions. As both interactomes included some inner mitochondrial membrane (IMM) proteins such as LETM2 and ATP5F1B, FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 might localise in close proximity with the IMM or even associate with it, as previously suggested (Boehm et al., 2017; Wolf and Mootha, 2014). The BioID indicated that FASTKD4 may bind FASTKD5. Therefore, these proteins may interact to exhibit a synergistic role, for example, in ND5-CYTB RNA processing. Notably, the BioID analyses revealed that LRPPRC was most significantly enriched with both FASTKD4 and FASTKD5, suggesting that they may cooperate or compete with LRPPRC to regulate the stability of specific mRNAs (Chujo et al., 2012; Siira et al., 2017).

The interaction among the FASTK family members can also be illustrated by our finding that the knockout of FASTKD3 caused a decrease in FASTKD5 protein expression level, and the absence of FASTKD5 led to a reduction in the level of FASTKD3 protein. This suggests that FASTKD3 and FASTKD5 may associate and only be stable as a complex. Given that the loss of FASTKD5 also resulted in a significant decrease in the protein expression levels of MRPP1, ELAC2 and RPUSD4, these findings indicate that FASTKD3 and FASTKD5 may form a large complex with these mtRBPs. Furthermore, it is important to note that a recent large scale study of mitochondrial protein interaction networks based on BioID revealed that the FASTK family members and a number of mtRBPs are localized in close proximity in the mitochondrial matrix (Antonicka et al., 2020).

5-1-8. Evolution of mitochondrial genomes and the FASTK family

The FASTK protein family with its three signature domains (FAST_1, FAST_2, and RAP domain) appeared in the early evolution of metazoans. We found that this evolutionary appearance of the FASTK family almost synchronizes with a major mitochondrial genome remodelling: the clearance of introns that results in the reduction of the genome size. For instance, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Dictyostelium discoideum* with intron-containing mitochondrial genomes do not have FASTK proteins, whereas in later stages of evolution after

the appearance of the FASTK family (e.g. *Caenorhabditis elegans* and *Drosophila melanogaster*), mitochondrial genomes have lost introns. Considering that RAP domain-containing proteins are involved in RNA processing and splicing in chloroplasts and in the nucleus (Izquierdo and Valcarcel, 2007; Kleinknecht et al., 2014; Rivier et al., 2001b; Simarro et al., 2007), the FASTK family appears to have evolved to compensate for the loss of introns and to support the processing of the non-canonical junctions in the metazoan mitochondrial genomes, where genes are tightly packed. However, *Tricholax adhaerens*, at the root of metazoan evolution, exceptionally contains both introns in the mtDNA and the FASTK proteins, and further study will therefore be needed to validate this novel hypothesis.

5-2. Exploration of non-canonical mtRNA processing

5-2-1. Role of PTC2 in ND5-CYTB RNA processing

In addition to FASTKD4 and FASTKD5, PTC2 is also proposed as a factor involved in processing of the ND5-CYTB junction (Xu et al., 2008). We generated a CRISPR/Cas9 KO 143B human cell line and investigated how the absence of PTC2 affects mitochondrial gene expression. We observed that the loss of PTC2 caused an impairment of ND5-CYTB RNA processing, albeit to a lesser extent when compared to FASTKD4-KO cells. This finding indicates that FASTKD4 has a more effective role in ND5-CYTB RNA processing than PTC2. Importantly, apart from ND5-CYTB RNA processing, the levels of other mRNAs in the PTC2-KO cells was altered differently from those in FASTKD4-KO cells. Notably, the ND3 mRNA level was dramatically increased in the absence of PTC2, whereas it was decreased in the loss of FASTKD4, suggesting that PTC2 and FASTKD4 work in different functional modules. In this context, it will be interesting to identify the mtRNAs associated with PTC2 and to investigate whether PTC2 binds to the same substrate RNA (tRNA^E) as FASTKD4. Interestingly, the loss of PTC2 resulted in an elevated ND5 protein synthesis despite defective ND5-CYTB RNA processing, which is reminiscent of what we described with the FASTKD4-KO HAP1 cells. These findings indicate that PTC2 and FASTKD4 may have redundant or synergistic roles in the processing and translation of ND5.

To understand how the known factors of ND5-CYTB processing associate each other and to identify the unknown RNA processing machinery, we carried out BioID experiments and revealed the protein interactomes of PTC2, FASTKD4, and FASTKD5. None of their interactomes included proteins that could resemble RNases, which implies that these proteins may regulate ND5-CYTB RNA processing in an indirect manner. The PTC2 interactome showed high similarity to the BioID results of FASTKD4 and FASTKD5, and importantly, FASTKD5 was found in the PTC2 interaction network. These findings indicate that these three proteins are localized in close proximity within the mitochondrial matrix. We also found that PTC2 interacts with FASTKD2 and DHX30, both of which are involved in the mitoribosome assembly. FASTKD2 forms a 16S rRNA maturation complex with proteins including RPUSD4 of which the protein expression level was decreased in the PTC2-KO cells. These results indicate that PTC2 might associate with mitoribosomes, similar to the PTC family proteins, PTC1 and PTC3 (Haque et al., 2011; Lightowers and Chrzanowska-Lightowers, 2013; Perks et al., 2018).

5-2-2. Possible involvements of known mitochondrial RNases in non-canonical mtRNA processing

We here discuss several major mitochondrial RNases that could possibly be involved in the cleavage of non-canonical junctions.

A simple model involves RNase P (MRPP1-3) and RNase Z (ELAC2) in the cleavage of atypical junctions. The processing sites of pre-COX1 and ND5-CYTB correspond to “mirror tRNAs”. For example, the ND5-CYTB junction includes a sequence complementary to tRNA^E. This suggests that these mirror tRNAs can possibly be processed by the tRNA processing enzymes if they form a tRNA-like secondary structure. A recent study of the MRPP3 knockout mice revealed that the 5' end cleavage of tRNA by MRPP3 precedes the processing of non-canonical junctions and is needed for the generation of the non-canonical precursor RNAs (Rackham et al., 2016). It is important to note that mature ND5 mRNA level was not dramatically reduced in this MRPP3 knockout mice, unlike mature CYTB mRNA and other mRNAs derived from the non-canonical precursor transcripts. This specific effect appears to be a consequence of the organization of ND5 within the mitochondrial genome. In other words, ND5 mRNA can be theoretically processed from the polycistronic primary transcript by ELAC2 and another endoribonuclease. Nonetheless, MRPP1 remains an interesting candidate as its knockdown specifically impairs pre-COX1 processing, which suggests that it may play a role in pre-COX1 processing independent of its role in the cleavage of tRNA junctions, potentially associating with another endoribonuclease (Sanchez et al., 2011). On the other hand, the knockdown of ELAC2 does not affect the processing of mirror tRNA^E (ND5-CYTB), mirror tRNA^Y (pre-COX1) and the ATP8/6-COX3 junction (Brzezniak et al., 2011). Furthermore, a more recent study revealed that the knockout of ELAC2 *in vivo* causes a dramatic decrease in mtRNAs, but not a specific accumulation in the non-canonical precursor RNAs, implying that ELAC2 might not catalyse non-canonical RNA processing (Siira et al., 2018). Taken together, MRPP3 and ELAC2 are unlikely to be responsible for the processing of non-canonical junctions.

PNPase, the catalytic enzyme of the mtRNA degradosome, may also regulate mtRNA processing, since it was recently found to prevent the accumulation of mitochondrial dsRNA (Dhir et al., 2018). The duplex formation should principally inhibit the canonical tRNA processing, and potentially also the non-canonical RNA processing. The transcriptome analyses we carried out suggest that FASTKD4 and FASTKD5 may cooperate with the mtRNA degradosome for the clearance of ncRNAs during the processing of non-canonical

junctions. Furthermore, PNPase participates in the processing of pre-ND6, cooperating with mtFASTK (Jourdain et al., 2015). To study its effects on non-canonical RNA processing, we generated a human cell line stably expressing shPNPase. The knockdown of PNPase caused a decrease in specific mRNAs including ND5, CYTB, ATP8/6, and COX1. However, the ND5-CYTB and ATP8/6-COX3 precursor RNA levels were not significantly affected. This finding suggests that PNPase is unlikely to regulate the processing of these non-canonical junctions.

5-2-3. Attempts to identify a ND5-CYTB RNA processing enzyme

Given that FASTKD4, FASTKD5, and PTCD2 are unlikely to participate in the ND5-CYTB RNA processing as catalytic enzymes, we attempted to identify the unknown catalytic enzymes by purifying the active enzymes from a mitochondrial lysate following the protocol that Holzmann et al. used to identify the mitochondrial RNase P complex (Holzmann et al., 2008). Unfortunately, we could not observe a specific cleavage of an *in vitro* transcribed ND5-CYTB junction-containing RNA, even using a mitochondrial lysate. There are several possible explanations for this result. The lysis conditions might have been too harsh, resulting in the collapse of the RNA processing complex and/or denaturation of the key enzymes. The biochemical conditions of the *in vitro* RNase activity assay (salt concentration, temperature, pH, metal ions, etc.) might not have been optimal for the specific cleavage. Alternatively, the synthetic RNAs used as substrate were not properly folded and not recognized by the processing enzymes.

To identify proteins that associate with the ND5-CYTB precursor RNA in cells, we carried out a pulldown of crosslinked ND5-CYTB RNA-protein complex using 3'-biotinylated DNA probes that specifically hybridize with the ND5-CYTB region. Although the ND5-CYTB transcript was specifically enriched, the yield was very low and protein enrichment was not observed (data not shown). This finding suggests that the ~3500 nt long ND5-CYTB precursor RNA may include complex secondary structures associated with mtRBPs, which renders the transcripts poorly accessible to the DNA probes. Consistently, most non-canonical junctions are predicted to include particular secondary structures (Mercer et al., 2011). Such particular secondary structures may have a key regulatory role during the recruitment of the RNA processing machinery. It will be interesting to perform additional bioinformatic analyses to uncover possible consensus structural motifs or sequences at the non-canonical junctions, which have been possibly conserved during the evolution of mitochondrial genomes.

While these studies did not allow us to identify non-canonical RNA processing enzymes, other putative processing factors remain to be elucidated. For example, MRPP1 has been estimated to play a role in pre-COX1 RNA processing, which seems to be independent of its function as a subunit of the RNase P complex (Sanchez et al., 2011). Moreover, a recent study of mitochondrial protein interaction network based on BioID experiments uncovered novel proteins that localize within mitochondria (Antonicka et al., 2020). In this study, EXO2 was found to have a mitochondrial isoform. While its function in the mitochondrial gene expression remains unclear, EXO2 may have a major role in mtRNA stability and processing, since the enzyme carries a 5' to 3' exoRNase. Furthermore, the study revealed that several hnRNP family proteins (Geuens et al., 2016) are present in mitochondrial RNA granules (MRGs). As the hnRNP family proteins are largely involved in transcriptional and post-transcriptional controls of nuclear gene expression, including RNA splicing, these mitochondrial hnRNP proteins may play important roles in mitochondrial gene expression, provided these are bona fide mitochondrial proteins and not artifacts of the BioID approach. If these proteins are found to be indeed imported into mitochondria, then it will be imperative to investigate their roles in mtRNA processing.

VI. Conclusions

Post-transcriptional control of mitochondrial gene expression is crucial for ATP production through oxidative phosphorylation. The FASTK family proteins are increasingly considered to be key post-transcriptional regulators in mitochondrial gene expression, and their roles range from RNA maturation to mitoribosome assembly. However, their precise mode of action remains uncharacterised. Understanding their molecular mechanisms and primary functions, particularly during non-canonical mtRNA processing, was the main goal of this PhD thesis.

We focused our work on FASTKD4, which is the most evolutionarily conserved member of the family, and concluded that it is unlikely that this protein is an endonuclease, based on our *in vitro* assays and on the analysis of its 3D structure. Furthermore, our transcriptomic analyses of cells in which FASTKD genes were deleted revealed a complex pattern of RNA and protein alterations, indicating that these proteins are probably multifunctional and that they may not only play a role in RNA processing but also in translation. We hope that our work will open up new avenues to extend our understanding of how these proteins act during the unique mitochondrial gene expression.

VII. References

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